

Ethnocentrism as a Predictor of Cyberbullying & Cyber Victimization among adults: A Cross-Cultural Study

A doctoral thesis submitted to Gujarat University (Ahmedabad)

For the award of the degree of

Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Psychology

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Declaration

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A Cross-Cultural Study”**

Submitted by me to the Faculty of Arts, Department of Psychology, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad in fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy has not previously formed the basis for the award of any Degree, Diploma Associateship, Fellowship or other similar title or recognition. This is to declare further that I have also fulfilled the requirements of the Ph.D.

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In the name of Allah, the most Gracious, the most Merciful

All praise is due to Allah. We praise him, we seek His help, we seek His forgiveness, and we seek refuge in Allah from the evil within ourselves and our evil deeds. Whoever Allah guides, there is none to misguide him. Whoever Allah leads astray, there is none to guide him. I testify there is no God but Allah alone, without any partners, and that Muhammad, peace and blessings be upon him, is His servant and His messenger. (*Khutbah Al-Hajah: How to Begin a Khutbah Sermon in Arabic and English*, n.d.)

O mankind, indeed We have created you from male and female and made you peoples and tribes that you may know one another. Indeed, the most noble of you in the sight of Allah is the most righteous of you. Indeed, Allah is Knowing and Acquainted. (Sahih International, n.d.49:13)

I hope that through weaving my ideas into words, my feelings reach your heart. The conclusion of this thesis has led to a key realization: pleasure is not a place or a destination, but rather a continuous journey. A difficult process that brings life's great experiences to life's full manifestation.

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Mohammad Khalid Khawrin

Abstract

Legislation aimed at regulating internet use among adults has been prompted by media reports on the incidences of abuse on the internet, particularly among teenagers and adults, which are increasing at an alarming rate and are raising a lot of concern among organizations, academia, and parents of teenagers. Social networking services (SNS) and ethnocentrism have come under fire for being breeding grounds for cyberbullying, cyber victimization, and harassment by coworkers, classmates, friends, and acquaintances. However, there is a lack of rigorous research studies that specifically identify risk factors for adult internet abuse and investigate whether recent increases in online abuse, disrespect, and rage are the results of cyberbullying and victim behavior on social networking sites (SNS) or something else. This study sought to pinpoint the crucial elements and connections between ethnocentrism and cross-cultural online adult victimization in Ahmedabad, India, and Kabul, Afghanistan.

Humans are born with the ability to be hegemonies, but long-term favoritism of one person over another is problematic. Individuals occasionally cede dominance to clans, tribes, and countries, which can lead to a variety of issues, including bullying, abuse, conflict, mocking, taunting, etc. Additionally, ethnocentrism is the source of the cultural disparity used for hegemonic aims. Ethnocentric conduct, on the other hand, is altering one group's preference in this virtual technology.

Cyberbullying is another adverse effect of social networking sites, and it is primarily caused by ethnocentrism. It is one of the rising difficulties for both students and regular residents. Students do, however, encounter these problems on social networking sites. Cyberbullying is the act of intimidating and threatening another person via the use of internet communication. The need for the government and citizens to be concerned about this phenomenon has grown. Studies that concentrate on the problems of cyberbullying and ethnocentrism are few and far between. However, there are several hate-based inconsistencies in both virtual and non-virtual conversations due to cultural prejudices and ethnocentric group advantages.

An international syndrome of attitudes and actions is known as ethnocentrism. It is, in other words, a commitment to the group. The foundation of in-group bias might be easily triggered. One of the main issues of virtual conflict on the internet is cyberbullying. There are new ways of living thanks to the development of cyber technology. The phenomenon known

as "cyber victimization" occurs when someone suffers an injury online. Furthermore, the social and psychological conduct of Homo sapiens is impacted by this virtual injury.

This study's methodology employed an inductive approach to the development of new hypotheses. More specifically, cross-cultural research was applied to cover the two countries' data. A cross-cultural study, which was done to compare and systematize the differences and similarities between at least two cultures throughout the world, is a type of scientific research. The cross-sectional design was a subtype of the descriptive study design. On the other hand, through exploratory research, the research problems were elaborated. It is uncertain if ethnocentrism has any connection to cyberbullying and the behavior of those who have been cyberbullied. In other words, the inductive technique refers to the process of taking a result from a particular sample and applying it to the generalization of the result, which provides us with a new theory. There were 1550 questionnaires distributed. Out of these distributed questionnaires, between a thousand and five hundred were retrieved and other were discarded. Furthermore, the exclusion and inclusion criteria were applied to the data. Finally, we had 1416 participants from both cities of both countries. The data was collected through a random sampling technique. There were 707 participants from India (Ahmedabad) and 709 participants from Afghanistan (Kabul) who made up the sample, which was drawn from these two nations. For the sample, the age factor was taken into account between the ages of seventeen to thirty years old (17 to 30). There were 772 males and 644 females participated in this study. Additionally, this data was collected using a straightforward random sample method. For instance, participants might choose from a set of Yes or No cards that were put. The participant was at the same time taping one of the cards' backs. If the participant pressed "YES," the questionnaire was given and, after completion, it was collected from them, and vice versa, if they clicked "NO."

The research participants willingly and voluntarily took part and provided anonymous responses. Each questionnaire also had a unique serial number. Every student was asked to participate in the survey, and they were free to stop at any point. All individuals gave their consent to participate in the study. Students freely took part. During the academic year, May 2020 through December 2021, data was gathered. They have a 30-minute time limit to complete the questionnaire. The participants also received thorough verbal and written training.

Each participant also had the option to discontinue the questionnaire at any point if they so desired. In other words, they had full access to the questionnaire. All of the information

was gathered during their leisure time in various locations, including the open spaces and classrooms of each institution. Additionally, demographic information was gathered, including age, daily internet usage, social media use, and whether a person had engaged in cyberbullying in the previous year as a perpetrator, victim, or witness. The age component, which spanned from seventeen to thirty years, was also included in the data, and its mean was 21.65 years, respectively. Additionally, participants' daily internet usage varied from fifteen (15) minutes to twenty (20) hours per day. In other words, the average hours of internet surfing of the Indian participants was 3.58 hours per day, and the average hours of internet surfing of the Afghan participants was 3.17 hours per day.

The Statistical Program for Social Science (SPSS) version 24 has been used to analyze data using descriptive and inferential methods. Standardized questionnaires, including the Ethnocentrism scale, the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory (RCBI), and the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory-II (RCBI-II), were used to gather the core data for this study.

The results and findings of this study proved that the relationship between age and ethnocentrism, cyberbullying on the RCBI and RCBI-II scales, and cyber victimization on the RCBI-II scale factors was almost nil. On the RCBI scale, there is just one instance of age being associated with the cyber victim; this link was significant at the 0.05 level. Cyberbullying on the RCBI and RCBI-II Scales exhibited a substantial link with the ethnocentrism variable, and cyber victims on the RCBI Scale had a significant association at the 0.01 level. However, the RCBI-II scale behavior of cyber victims did not significantly correlate with the ethnocentrism component. At a 0.01 level, there was a significant correlation between cyberbullying conduct on the RCBI-II scale and a cyber-victim. On the RCBI scale, there was a 0.01 degree of correlation between cyberbullying activity and cyber victim behavior. The RCBI-II Scale on cyberbullying and cyber victims is more generic. The RCBI's scale for measuring cyber victims and cyberbullying, however, is more specific. According to statistical evidence, Afghan participants scored much higher than Indian participants did on measures measuring ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization.

Additionally, the ethnocentrism variable, cyberbullying behavior of the RCBI scale, cyber victimization behaviors of the RCBI, and the RCBI-II scales' variables were statistically significantly different, except for cyberbullying behavior of the RCBI-II scale, all participants of both countries displayed similar behavior.

The ethnocentrism, cyberbullying conduct on the RCBI-II and RCBI measures, and cyber victim behavior on the RCBI scale were substantially different between male and female participants. The RCBI-II scale's cyber victimization behavior, however, did not alter substantially from the baseline. In other words, compared to female participants, men were statistically more likely to engage in cyberbullying, cyber victimization, and ethnocentric conduct.

The gender-interaction of the ethnocentrism behaviors of India and Afghanistan revealed that both male and female Afghans exhibited higher degrees of ethnocentrism than the Indian gender. Afghan male participants exhibited greater cyberbullying (RCBI-II) activity than the Indian gender and Afghan female participants, according to cyberbullying (RCBI-II) behavior of Indians and Afghans with gender interaction. However, as compared to the Indian gender and Afghan male participants, Afghan female participants showed the lowest levels of cyberbullying (RCBI-II) conduct. Indian men were the least likely to have been victimized (RCBI-II) online compared to Afghan men. In addition, compared to Afghan female participants, Indian women were more frequently cyber victimized.

On the Cyberbullying (RCBI) scale, Afghan male participants scored the highest, and Afghan female participants scored higher than the Indian gender. The participants from India, however, scored the lowest on cyberbullying (RCBI). On the Cyber Victim (RCBI) scale, Afghan male participants scored the highest, and Afghan female participants scored higher than the Indian gender. On the RCBI scale, however, the Indian female participants received the lowest scores for cyber victimization.

Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) had less of an impact on the ethnocentrism of Indian individuals. Additionally, it did not significantly change the behavior of cyber victims (RCBI-II). On the RCBI scale, cyberbullying was highly impacted by the ethnocentrism of Indian individuals. On the RCBI scale, it had no appreciable impact on cyber victim behavior.

Ethnocentrism among participants from Afghanistan had a substantial impact on cyberbullying (RCBI-II). Additionally, add 0.067 points of cyberbullying (RCBI-II) to one point of ethnocentrism. However, it did not significantly alter the behavior of the cyber victim (RCBI-II). Additionally, on the RCBI scale, the ethnocentrism of the participants from Afghanistan had a substantial impact on cyberbullying. For instance, one point of ethnocentrism causes cyberbullying (RCBI) to rise by 0.091 points. On the RCBI scale, it also

had a considerable impact on how cyber victims behaved. For instance, a rise of 0.089 points in cyber victimization (RCBI) for every point of ethnocentrism.

Finally yet importantly, it is urged that both the Afghan and Indian governments have clear rules and regulations to guard against and stop any type of cyberbullying conduct that has negative knock-on effects. The road for legal authorities, academics, and non-academic groups is more clearly defined. Therefore, academic researchers are strongly encouraged to conduct further studies in this area of ethnocentrism and cyberbullying. Further research is required to fully understand ethnocentrism, including all of its negative effects and how it came into being. This will operate as a guiding principle for the manipulation and direct it toward its advantageous ends.

Every person is also able to take legal and preventative actions. Launching awareness campaigns using various channels, including the media, protests, conferences, etc. Understanding one another's goals and needs is facilitated by teaching one another about the new cultures of different societies. By demonstrating and establishing the negative effects of cyberbullying behavior on the general public, organizational stakeholders, and students, it may be curbed and prevented. It has been observed that schools and institutions must set policies and guidelines for handling professors, coworkers, and classmates who are subjected to cyberbullying by students. Everyone should check out anti-bullying websites, anti-ethnocentrism efforts, and family support organizations.

Criminal and forensic psychologists are advised to add this new arena to their investigation and scope of work that destabilizes individual psychological health and social lives. The psychological counselor must assist the victims and exhibit anti-cyberbullying, and ethnocentric attitudes. Programs for social awareness are also necessary to educate young people about the dangers of cyberbullying. Anti-cyber ragging laws and regulations should be made in India and Afghanistan to solve the existing problem. User-friendly Information about cyber rights must be accessible to everyone. These internet users are aware of their rights, nevertheless. This will also act as a warning to stop kids from abusing the internet. It is important to take into account the research's suggested solutions and those that the respondents favored. Bystanders should step in to defend the online victim, stop online bullying, and alert the relevant organizations.

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Operational Definition of Terms

Here are some operational definitions of the study, which are written below.

Ethnocentrism

Giving priority to the same national, caste, or ethnicity's culture is called ethnocentrism. In other words, giving priority to the culture of the in-group is also called ethnocentrism.

Tribe

It is the biological descendent of humans from one baseline is called a tribe. It is a biological identification.

Ethnicity

Collectively, all members of tribes from one biological baseline and same culture are called ethnicity. It is a bio-social identification.

Caste

According to the law, the division of society into groups based on the social structure function and low-income of citizens is called caste. This is an acquired identity.

Culture

It is the same pattern of behavior among the group members such as caste, race, nation, tribe, or any other formation of the group that is called culture.

Cyberbullying

Teasing peers through electronic gadgets is called cyberbullying.

Cyber Victimization

To be harmed by the peer through electronic gadgets is called cyber victimization.

Cyberbully or cyberbullying perpetrator

A person who just and only engages in bullying behavior through digital space is called a cyberbully or cyberbullying perpetrator.

Cyber victim

A person who becomes a digital victim of cyberbullying behavior only becomes a cyber victim because the cyberbullying action happened against him/her.

Cyberbullying perpetrator and victim

A person who simultaneously engages in cyberbullying behavior as a perpetrator and he also becomes a victim of digital behavior.

Cyber bystander

A person who has watched or heard digital behavior but was not involved in cyberbullying behavior and did not become a victim is called a "cyber bystander."

Bullycide

To commit suicide because of cyberbullying behavior. Or "the act or an instance of killing oneself intentionally as a result of bullying" (DICTIONARY, 2012).

Chapter I

Introduction

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

1.2 History of Ethnocentrism

1.2.1 The Concept of Ethnocentrism

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1.0 Introduction

Afghanistan is one of the strategically located countries at a crossroads between the Indian subcontinent and central Asia. However, Afghanistan is a multi-ethnic country famous for being a cultural country, but still, ethnic tension does exist, and that is due to a lack of proper planning, policy, and management by the concerned authorities (Afghan government). However, publically speaking, ethnocentrism is a taboo issue in Afghan culture. The ethnic tension in Afghanistan was a matter of great concern among the Afghan nation during the 1990s. Fortunately, the United Nations also pressured the importance of ethnicity. For instance, the political representation and interests of all ethnic minorities have been safeguarded in the Bonn Conference of 2001. Now, the ethnicities of Afghan people are overlapping and weaving with one another, with languages, culture, and religious sects (Ali, 2015).

Secondly, India is a well-known, crowded, multi-lingual, multi-religious, and multi-ethnic country. However, in this new era of the 2010s, it is trying to change into a mono-religion, a mono-ethnicity, and many other discords. These discords are happening in a different dimension of civilian life (Weiner, 1983). As the Time news agency reports, targeting and harming minorities on a religious and ethnicity basis, different cases have been reported (Ayyub, 2019). Moreover, hate crime is booming year by year. The incidents against minorities of communal violence raised 28 percent between 2014 and 2017 (Gowen & Sharma, 2018)

Both countries have ethnocentrism issues, which have created many hate crimes and changed the legislative process. Furthermore, the signs of ethnocentrism are available on virtual media via cyberbullying and cyber victimization acts are present in social media. Moreover, social media (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, WhatsApp, TikTok, etc.) has a prominent set of rules for manipulating social norms. Individuals or organized groups do these activities in social virtually in a real and manipulated way that has been used for many purposes. Social media's role is in formatting hate and radicalization online (Mirchandani, 2018).

Lastly, it is argued that mutual understanding of one another's culture is needed, which is to reduce the seriousness and boost hate crime. Therefore, ethnocentrism is one of the prominent dilemmas and dimensions to be understood because it is deeply rooted in culture. The relationship of ethnocentrism with cyberspace, particularly

bullying, and its victimization, is the starting point of hate crime, misunderstanding of culture, race, and ethnicity, which lead to prejudice and sophisticated crime, and instability in society. Lastly, it is said that ethnocentrism might have an underground relationship with the un-tolerated cultures of other groups (Pratama, 2019).

1.1 Background of the Study

Hegemony in human beings exists from birth, but preference for one individual over another for long periods creates problems. In some cases, individuals give hegemony to clans, tribes, and nations, and sometimes this causes many problems such as bullying, abuse, fighting, taunting, etc. The term “ethnocentrism” refers to judging another culture solely by the values and standards of one's own culture (LeVine, 2015).

Moreover, the cultural difference for hegemony purposes is rooted in ethnocentrism. On the other hand, ethnocentric behavior is changing one group's favoritism in this virtual technology. However, this technology brought many facilities, but it also had its negative impact. Furthermore, it is up to the users how they use it. When somebody misuses technology, it could be presumed to be because of ethnicity and cultural values. Recently, social networking sites have brought a new era of communication to this world. There are many social networking sites like Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, and many others that allow people to interact with and connect with people across the globe.

Furthermore, one of the negative impacts of social networking sites is cyberbullying, which is mostly because of ethnocentrism. It is one of the growing challenges for students and general citizens. However, students face these issues on social networking sites. Cyberbullying is the use of electronic communication to bully a person by sending messages that are intimidating and threatening in nature. It has become crucial for the government and people to be concerned about this phenomenon. There is little research that focuses on the issues of cyberbullying and ethnocentrism. However, the basis of culture and ethnocentric group privileges causes many hate disharmonies in virtual and non-virtual communications.

1.2 History of Ethnocentrism

Ethnocentrism is a global syndrome of attitudes and behaviors. In other words, it is in-group devotion. Practical evidence showed the basis of in-group favoritism could be easily activated. Moreover, it prefers to help start the in-group. It is the evolutionary model for grabbing power in an emergency (Hammond & Axelrod, 2006). Ethnocentrism is used in different disciplines, mainly in psychology. This concept is used for in-group biases, which is "the laboratory analog of real-world ethnocentrism," and this is the tendency to have in-group behavior against the out-group in assessing the behavior (Tajfel & Turner, 1986, p. 889). Because of the criminological aspect, because of ethnocentrism, crime happens to some extent (Gudjonsson, 1994). After all, the Oxford English Dictionary argued that McGee (1900) used "ethnocentrism" for the first time as an English word in a practical form (Bizumic, 2014).

Many scholars assumed that Sumner coined the concept of ethnocentrism in 1906, but this term was used before 1906 in the shows of German, Polish, and English people. Over and above that, several publications used this term many decades before Sumner. such as the publication of Gumplowicz in 1879 and 1881 (Bizumic, 2014). Ethnocentrism is a prominent topic in different fields and most of it is used in social sciences and psychology. It is intergroup relations and bias (Bizumic, 2014). The ethnocentrism term's meaning is cultural narrowness or belonging to a province. In other words, the tendency of individuals toward the core ethnic group or to be alike or unlike them is difficult for him/her in terms of acceptance or rejection (Jurczak et al., 1950). For this reason, they place Sumner as the pioneer of this term (Bizumic, 2014).

However, the concept of ethnocentrism has a contradictory and confusing meaning, which has been elaborated by Bizumic & Duckitt (2012) in their article. Khawrin (2021) argued that ethnocentrism is "a strong sense of ethnic group self-centeredness" that gives priority and benefits to its intergroup expressions (p. 308). Besides that, they give a strong sense of devotion and cohesion to intragroup expression. Moreover, they elaborated on this concept by saying that ethnocentrism is a different form of in-group positivity than out-group negativity (Bizumic & Duckitt, 2012).

On the contrary, out-group and in-group behavior can be distinguished by knowing the central tendency of ethnocentrism. Neuliep & McCroskey (1997) cited the Sumner (1906) article and defined the ethnocentrism as "the technical name for this

view of things in which one's group is the center of everything, and all others are scaled and rated concerning it" (p. 13). Moreover, it is a group's natural condition and can be found universally, and this can give power to the in-group with pride over the out-group (Neuliep & McCroskey, 1997).

Following this, Neuliep & McCroskey (1997) concurred with Hofstede that he was arguing, that a group's ego-centrism is called ethnocentrism. Moreover, it was demonstrated by behavior and attitude toward the in-group versus the out-group. In addition, all members of the group are biased in favor of their in-group. It is clear that ethnocentric groups feel virtuous and superior by their cultural standards and values, but the out-groups are seen as lower, puny, distressful, and immoral. Members of the in-group remain united by obedience, loyalty, cooperation, and solidarity, but out-groups are blamed for being trouble and hurdles. Neuliep & McCrosk (1997) mention this in their research by differentiating the out-group from the in-group along with the stereotyped and attitude angles.

In addition, Kam & Kinder (2007) are arguing differently. They are saying that ethnocentrism is "prejudice, broadly conceived," and that it repairs to the general human tendency to divide social life into righteous in-groups and evil out-groups. They are saying that it can mostly be found in the USA, but it has some relationship with politics. Furthermore, it can depend upon the conditions (p.320).

Subsequently, one is centrally important and superior to one's group rather than other groups. This centrally important group is called an "intergroup," and this leads to biases, prejudice, xenophobia, and violence within the in-group. This is in-group cohesion, trust, assistance, and coordination. Some studies show that ethnocentrism promotes brain oxytocin and this shows in-group favoritism. Moreover, oxytocin promotes emergency conflict and violence (De Dreu et al., 2011).

Afterward, Cunningham, Nezlek, & Banaji (2004) launched two studies to evaluate implicit and explicit ethnocentrism. They found that there is implicit and explicit ethnocentrism and these two phenomena have a difference from one another. Moreover, these two types are related to one another. Next, Durrant (2018) noted in his research that Hogg and Abram suggested that humans have a strong tendency to favor the members of the in-group, but at the same time, they have a negative tendency toward the members of the out-group. Moreover, De Dreu et al. (2011) mention that

neuropeptide oxytocin operates as a hormone and a neurotransmitter and that oxytocin plays a positive role in increasing ethnocentrism and behavior inside the group.

Above all, Bizumic (2015a) cited in his handwriting that Baracq (1902) and Banton (1998) discovered differently, and they coded that Gumpłowicz had given the premises concept, and he wrote a book in the German language in 1881 and elaborated the ethnocentrism concept. The author said that ethnocentrism phenomena are a "delusion" to "egocentrism" and "anthropocentrism," however, giving priority to one's ethnic group. Such as, ancient Greeks had a belief that others were barbarians; the French were believed to be more civilized than others; and Jews had faith that they were God's chosen people over gentiles (Bizumic, 2015a, p. 3).

Lastly, it is inferred from the written evidence that William Graham Sumner coined the "Ethnocentrism" term in the twentieth century. Sumner first defines ethnocentrism as the in-group promoting unity toward the out-group and the in-group showing antagonism. However, in the 1950s, other scholars disproved this meaning. Now, this term's meaning is accepted that one's culture is superior to another one, by which one culture's members judge other cultures by their attributes and values (LeVine, 2015).

1.2.1 The Concept of Ethnocentrism

About a century ago, German publications were generally used in the USA. Many US scholars were citing German articles, so Sumner was also one of them. For instance, it can be seen that Sumner's citations such as 1906, 1911, and 1913 are years of reference. In his 1906 article, Sumner cited Gumpłowicz's book about "Ethnocentrism." In which Gumpłowicz elaborated on ethnocentrism. There was a similarity between Sumner and Gumpłowicz's ethnocentrism expiation (Bizumic, 2014). However, it was Sumner (1906) who wrote the concept precisely and clearly about ethnocentrism, and he has not claimed the term "ethnocentrism." Because he cited Gumpłowicz and Gumpłowicz cited the unpublished articles. But still, we are due to Sumner because he was the pioneer to elaborate this concept clearly and use it in social sciences (Bizumic, 2014). McGee (as cited by Bizumic, 2014) utilized the notion in another study. While discussing his anthropological studies with the Seri Indians, his mode of thought was tribe-centered or ethnocentric because they perceived extraneous items, especially those of living nature, concerning the tribe.

Ethnocentrism is a sort of nepotism that emerged as a result of kin selection over millions of years. According to van den Berghe, common ancestry can be genuine or legendary, but it cannot be fully manufactured even if it is a myth. Several generations must believe in and embrace the concept of shared ethnic ancestry (Malesevic, 2004, p. 83). Ethnocentrism is a primitive sort of ideology that emerged in pre-modern communities and has now spread to modern mass society (Malesevic, 2004, p. 84). Yeh et al. (2021) argued that the demand for indigenous psychology is developing in response to Western psychology's ethnocentrism, which has failed to address the theoretical and social concerns of non-Western people due to its positivist limits (p. 199). This behavior is known as ethnocentrism or parochial altruism: the inclination to favor and preferentially connect with members of one's in-group (Durrant, 2018).

For future writers, it is good advice to cite German writer Gumpowicz's 1879 article for his credit, but Sumner was the first person who borrowed the term "Ethnocentrism" and elaborated it in English literature. Citing the exact person who would promote international collaboration in a publication (Bizumic, 2014). Lastly, it could be argued that ethnocentrism is the inherited belief in the superiority of one's own ethnic group's culture.

1.2.2 The Concept of Culture

This concept was defined as being individually different from one another. In other words, there is still no common concise among scholars for defining the culture. Tischler defined that culture was all that homo-sapiens practically do, use, produce, understand, and believe maturely and have a connection with the social groups they belong to (Pratama, 2019, p. 41). Along the same lines, Clifford Geertz mentioned that culture was an organized inheritance of thoughts, which meant continuous communication and enhancing their knowledge about life and behavior (Pratama, 2019, p. 41). Moreover, Edward Tylor argued that culture is multipart of knowledge, beliefs, arts, morals, law, customs, and behavior of a group of people (Pratama, 2019, p. 41). Furthermore, a full understanding of the matter of cultural superiority is called ethnocentrism (Pratama, 2019). Finally, it was argued that culture is the social norms and behavior of a society.

Figure 1 Ethnocentric Behavior

Note: This image was published by Google Search Engine (*Ethnocentric Behavior*, n.d.).

1.2.3 Culture and Ethnocentrism

"Culture" is the common behavior of a society. However, ethnocentrism is the solo behavior of a person who gives priority to their own group or society's cultural norms toward others. In other words, Pratama (2019) described ethnocentrism as the excessive tendency toward one's own group rather than others. Tischler also disrobed that ethnocentrism was the judgment of other cultures' people on the basis of their own culture. Finally, it was argued that culture and ethnocentrism are interrelated. In addition, ethnocentrism is the solo person's social harmony and stereotype in a multicultural society and group against others (Bizumic, 2015b).

Individual cultures are said to be made up of "memetic complexes," which operate as cultural filters, guiding individual and collective behavior. Ethnocentrism, xenophobia, and ethno nationalism are instances of memetic complexes that spread through the brains of people. These common memetic values and beliefs help bind members of a given ethnic group since they are passed down from generation to generation. As a result, memetic complexes frequently serve as ideological supplements

to genetic in-group bias. Given that memes multiply in the brain, which socio-biologists consider being a consequence of genetic competition; both genes and memes are to blame for ethnic group behavior. While memes, also known as brain viruses, have autonomy, they act in a genetically generated environment and follow the same evolutionary laws as humans (Malesevic, 2004, p. 86).

Smith has argued for the antiquity and persistence of ethnocentrism based on communal mythologies of shared lineage rather than biology. According to Smith, the pre-modern ethnicities from which many nationalisms sprang were "constituted not by lines of physical lineage, but by lines of cultural affinity manifested in distinctive myths, memories, symbols, and values held by a particular cultural unit of people" (Kidd, 2004, p. 4). Because of ethnocentrism and a lack of cultural awareness, even though service delivery and provision may unconsciously accept the white middle-class pattern as usual (Bendiksen et al., 1999).

1.3 History of Cyberbullying and Cyber Victimization

Cyberbullying and cyber victimization are compound terms. One part of their terms is the virtual world of digital space and another is the legal term. Generally, the virtual world is called cyberspace. The second part is about bullying and victims. The term "bully" is found in the 1530s literature (Donegan, 2012). Two or more people directly or indirectly tease one another. In this situation, the person who teases is called a bully, and the other person is called a victim. In other words, when an intimidator abuses the victim physically, morally, or virtually to gain power and dominance, it is called bullying (Donegan, 2012). The person who is performing the bullying act is called a bully, and the person whom s/he teases is called a victim.

In addition, bullying and victimization are common in all human societies. Their actions are different in every culture and have different dimensions such as ethical, moral, systematic, and traditional. For instance, in the U.S., people "believe that success and wealth go hand in hand" (Donegan, 2012, p. 34). This phenomenon of bullying automatically comes into being from an early age of life in school. Furthermore, kids in school are taught to be superior and be the topper of their class (Donegan, 2012). Hence, students learn illegal ways to be first and this leads to learning the wrongful

ways in education time. Moreover, these students carry on these things in their social life. Furthermore, this habit would continue to affect work-life also (Donegan, 2012).

1.3.1 Cyberbullying

Cyberbullying is one of the prominent virtual disharmony topics among universities. The new era of cyber technology expansion has brought new ways of life. It changes the interaction style of humans (Donegan, 2012). Though cyber technology has benefits, it also has depletion. Some transgressors misuse cyber technology in many ways, and one of them is cyberbullying. Cyberbullying is more widespread than any other cybercrime. In order to clarify, Donegan (2012) cited in his research that cyberbullying is an anonymous, hidden, and identity-changing activity that can potentially bully anyone that is named “victim” from a long distance more rapidly and harshly than traditional bullying. Following this, MySpace was the first social media platform that gave everyone a facility to have a unique, desirable account, which can be seen by many users and take action on the pros or cons of someone in cyberspace. Moreover, Facebook and Google+ are more apt to be abused through cyberbullying (Donegan, 2012).

Equally important, the use of cyber technology through which a person intentionally and repetitively harms, threatens, insults, and makes fun of him/her is called cyberbullying. Generally, this definition of cyber phenomenon has five main dimensions, such as a) interpersonal or relational aggression, b) intention of doing, c) occurring in systematic situations, d) repeated action, and e) taking place in cyberspace (Jenaro et al., 2018). These five characteristics define cyberbullying action.

1.3.2 Cyber Victimization

Cyber victimization is the condition in which a person receives harm through cyberspace. Furthermore, this virtual harm does affect Homo sapiens’ sociological and psychological life behavior. Rigby (cited by Gianesini & Brighi, 2015) noted that past research in European countries showed that victims suffered many emotional effects from cyber victimization. Those forms of harm are oral, physical, and social. Moreover, the severity of this virtual disharmony is measured by its incidence.

Besides this, Mascheroni & Cuman have been included in EU Kids Online research that measures cyberbullying in 25 European countries in 2010. At that time, the cyber victimization rate was 9%, but in 2013 it reached 12% (Baldry et al., 2018). In other words, cyber victimization refers to the process of victimizing others through the use of information and communication technologies. It can be a legal entity, a human being, or an individual.

Figure 2 Cyber Bullying and Cyber Victim Behavior

Note: The Cyberbullying and Victim Behavior was cited from Vishwas Website (*Cyberbullying: Adults Can Be Victims Too! | CSU, 2020*).

1.4 Purpose of Study

This academic research examines and assesses the level of ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization among adults. The concept of ethnocentrism means prioritizing one's own culture over others, which shows bias against the minor cultural group. Moreover, the virtual social disharmony, in other words, social media that could lead to hate and prejudice against the out-group, is going to be discussed in this cross-cultural research concerning their ethnocentrism via the cross-sectional method. In addition, it is a unique study that compares Afghan and Indian societies on the basis of ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization.

Some researchers mentioned that minorities are frequently harmed by actions that discriminate despite their good or even liberal intentions. To cope with this complication, it's important to distinguish ethnocentrism, which is harmful for society and nation-building (Gillborn, 2003).

The purpose of this study would provide a broader overview to law enforcement and its stakeholders, which would draw the road map for harmony, stability in society, and an overall protected right to chastity, saving every person. On the other hand, this research would guide governments in taking new decisions in virtual fields and the scope of the work. Indeed, diagnosing the disharmony act against outgroups, which can cause hate crime and biases regarding any minority, culture, ethnicity, or any other problem, is one of the responsibilities of academicians (Pratama, 2019).

1.5 Importance and Significance of the Study

- Understanding the Afghan and Indian social disharmony, which is rooted in ethnocentrism.
- Ethnocentrism could be the cause of the bias and prejudice of virtual social disharmony in social media.
- There would be a difference between Afghan and Indian ethnocentrism.
- There would be a difference in cyberbullying and its' victimization in both countries.
- Virtual social disharmony in regards to cyberbullying and cyber victimization would be different in both cultures.
- Ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization based on gender, age, and internet surfing would be different in both countries.
- Ethnocentrism could be the cause of cyberbullying and victimization of disharmony and targeting of minority groups' cultures in Afghanistan and India.
- This research would provide concrete information via; virtual social disharmony in regards to ethnocentrism with cyberbullying, for policymakers, internet surfers, internet providers, and academicians to take positive action in a fever of society and multi-cultural nation building.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study included Indian adult students who were studying in Ahmedabad city, Gujarat state of India, and Afghan adult students who were studying in Kabul province. In addition, the age of the participants ranged from seventeen to thirty years, and others were excluded. Furthermore, those participants who used Internet surfing via social media have been taken into account. The male and female genders of the participants have been observed.

1.7 Planning of the Study

Tentative Chapter Scheme as below:

Chapter 1 – Introduction

Chapter 2 - Review of literature

Chapter 3 – Research Methodology

Chapter 4 – Results and Discussion

Chapter 5 – Summary, Conclusion, Limitations, Suggestions, and Implementations

- References
- Appendices

This study was organized into five chapters. In chapter one, the background of ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization in the Indian and Afghan scenarios have been discoursed in detail. In addition, introduce the problem, research area, the importance of the topic, and scope of the study. The second chapter reviewed the literature and historical background on ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization. Furthermore, the chapter was covered according to the objectives of the study. In addition, the association of age, gender, educational level, and internet surfing was pinpointed with the mentioned variables. The third chapter was dedicated to research methodology. This consisted of research objectives, research hypotheses, research design, population, and sample, participants, descriptive and inferential statistical tests outlined, research tools, and final research analysis software. Furthermore, chapter four of the study elaborated on the results and its related findings.

There finding were elaborated. The last chapter covered the discussion, the summary of major outcomes, limitations, and suggestions of the study. Finally, the appendices were attached.

1.8 Theoretical Considerations

The theory is a systematic idea for explaining some important things base on academic studies. There are many theories. So, the relevant and important theories are discussed below.

1.8.1 Societal or macro-level theory

This theory indicates that crime is a result of social structure rather than hereditary predisposition or mental issues. According to Marxist conflict theory, the criminal justice system is a tool used by the dominant or privileged classes to maintain their power and privilege. The feminist analysis posits that power is gendered in society and that male authority is represented by in-laws who, for example, consider girls as the belongings of their fathers and husbands (Durrant, 2018; Howitt, 2009, p. 61). Furthermore, through a comprehensive research design, Green & Seher (2003) revealed ethnic conflicts and prejudice, which filled the social-psychological components of prejudice and the macro-political causes of ethnic conflicts (p. 509).

However, Braithwaite (2022) described Braithwaite and D'Costa's crime theory. They provide a broad but incompletely methodical examination of micro and macro dynamics in one big region of the world, including how armed conflict leads to crime. In other words, crime leads to further crime and armed conflict, and one war leads to another. In this pattern, leading from one violence to another, violence is called cascading crime (p. 591).

1.8.2 Community or locality theory

Crime and harm are not dispersed randomly around the globe. Crime is more prevalent in some areas of the city than in others. The explanations vary, but the consensus is that there is either something unique about various regions or those different areas provide distinct criminal opportunities. In general, crime is perpetrated near the offender's home base, although there is typically a buffer zone around the house where they do not transgress. They may not offend within that zone since the chance of being recognized is significant (Howitt, 2009, p. 61).

Many studies have found that a risk factor for juvenile and adulthood violence exists at the community level, according to Goldstein (2003). For example, at school,

in the family, among peers, in universities, and in the community there are significant possibility to violence factors. Furthermore, Goldstein (2003) increased that risk variables are said to have a cumulative effect on the likelihood of violence by the time a person reaches early adulthood.

1.8.3 Group and socialization influence theory

Social factors have a direct effect on criminal behaviors. In other words, groups and communities also affect criminality. It implies friends and child delinquent behavior also. This theory shows that an individual is influenced by a community and groups (Howitt, 2009). In a simple example, gang members of different violence (McNamara et al., 2017), moral reasoning, drug use, non-violent and violent delinquent behavior, and serious offending all involve a social learning process in which differential association, mutual reinforcement, and imitation among peers are important to moral reasoning, drug use, non-violent and violent delinquent behavior, and serious offending (Canter, 2012). Hawkins and Weis stated in a 1985 article that the influence of connection with different groups is dependent on skills and available opportunities by combining social learning theory and social control theory. When traditional skills or opportunities are limited, association with delinquent peers is more likely. When benevolent and authoritative socialization units (family, schools, etc.) are dysfunctional or unavailable, offending behavior is more likely (Canter, 2012).

1.8.4 Individual approaches

It is difficult to pinpoint precisely which personality traits are linked to criminal behavior. Traditional psychometric personality assessments have not yielded very compelling results in studies attempting to determine the features of certain criminal groups. Several personality traits are linked to criminal behavior. Psychopathy, as well as the related antisocial personality disorder, is a trigger for self-harming and criminal behavior (Howitt, 2009).

Many individual factors are significantly related to vile and criminal behavior. For instance, "high impulsivity, lower intelligence, poor conceptual thinking, egocentricity/low empathy, poor parental supervision, harsh and erratic parental discipline, cold and rejecting parental attitude, separation from a parent, large family size, and having a criminal parent" (Kebbell & Davies, 2006, p. 71).

1.8.5 Social Dominance Theory

Sidanius and Pratto introduce Social Dominance Theory (Romm, 2012). Social dominance theory is based on three main pillars such as age, sex, and an arbitrary type of grading which consists of “race, tribe, class, religious group, caste, nationality, clan, lineage”, and many other factors (*Social Dominance Theory and the Dynamics of Gendered Prejudice - YouTube*, n.d.).

Monroe et al. (2000) argue that the social dominance theory persuades us to adopt the holistic theory of prejudice and discrimination, which gives favoritism to the in-group and hostility to the out-group. This theory influenced “social, evolutionary psychology, and political sociology of groups’ conflicts and ethnocentrism” (p. 431). Furthermore, they added that all societies have some hegemonic elites among one another. This feature increased the prejudice in normalized groups and society. It leads to an inherited desire of orientation to be at the upper level among the related groups. As a result of this theory, the “in” and “out” groups’ prejudice issues. This leads to different problems through which crime takes place. These problems are racism, discrimination, ethnocentrism, etc. From a criminology perspective, to some extent, crime occurs because of ethnocentrism (Gudjonsson, 1994). On the contrary, proving in-group favoritism through outsiders’ clam was also difficult to generalize the result. This leads to the cohesion of group members and outsider hostility (Šimko, 2013).

Social dominance theory is an effort to provide a broad theory of prejudice and discrimination in intergroup relations based on a variety of theoretical sources, including social psychology, political sociology's elitism, and evolutionary psychology of group conflict and ethnocentrism (Monroe et al., 2000).

1.8.6 Realistic Group Conflict Theory

Group conflict and solution expressions are mainly used in the psychology of realistic conflict theory. This theory explains the group members’ negative behavior. For instance, racism, social dominance, bias, prejudice, political and religious moments with castes and ethnicities, discrimination, in-group favoritism, and many other traits which lead to negativity or negative behavior (Allen & Barter, 2016; Meeusen et al., 2013; Monroe et al., 2000, p. 432). As it is mentioned above, there are many theories,

and everyone has a significant influence on its condition. Therefore, this study is well defined in the social dominance theory and the realistic group conflict theory.

Chapter II

Literature Review

2

2.0 Introduction

2.1 Ethnocentrism

2.1.1 Culture

2.1.2 Ethnicity

2.2 Introduction to Cyberbullying and Cyber victim

2.3 Concept of Cyberbullying and Cyber victimization

2.3.1 Cyberbullying

2.3.2 Cyber victimization

2.4 Contesting of Social Dominance and Realistic Group conflict theories

2.0 Introduction

Many theories have been given in criminal and forensic psychology to understand human harming offenses against someone. This behavior influences others' lives from different angles, such as psychological, physical, mental, behavioral, social, and economic. Finding a theoretical framework for the mentioned issues is called a theory of criminal behavior. This phenomenon has been defined from multi-disciplinary perspectives. Some of these theories are listed below. For example, social dominance theory, realistic group theory, societal or macro-level theory, community or locality level theory, group and socialization influence theory, and individual-level theory (Howitt, 2009, p. 60). In addition, the concept of ethnocentrism with different perspective meanings is noted. Simultaneously, the concept of cyberbullying and cyber victimization behaviors in relation to different variables are mentioned.

2.1 Ethnocentrism

Before establishing the identity card system by the states, people were using ethnicity as an identity, which could help humans in different dimensions, such as in transactions, identifying one another, and many other benefits. To be specific, ethnicity was a kind of identity for Homo sapiens. Furthermore, those who were misusing or giving priority to their ethnicity were called ethnocentrism. To put it another way, those who compare their in-group with their out-group and think that the out-group is less important and that they are lower than their own in-group are called ethnocentrism. I have a life accident on social media regarding ethnocentrism.

In 2018, one of my colleagues had a sexual relationship with another female, even though he was married, whose case has been exposed among Facebook users in Afghanistan. Meanwhile, I shared the same Facebook posts to understand the exact situation. Suddenly, one of my best friends from China called me on Facebook Messenger and asked me to remove my Facebook post. I told him okay. Then I removed the post within 20 minutes. These rumors were made inside Kunduz University. Those days, my head of department asked me what I posted on Facebook. What do you think about that? I directly told him if our colleague wants to get married, to another one, it is good to have a clear relationship according to the laws. I meant to get a legal marriage since it is allowed in Islam. After that, I left the department. Within two weeks, my

department colleagues made a conspiracy theory against me. They were arguing that M K Khawreen made this Facebook post to degrade and defame his colleague. In addition, they were using the ethnocentric favoritism phenomenon against me. In reality, my colleague's ethnicity was different. When I came to know this propaganda, I was shocked. In those days, an academic steering committee was called. I also participated. After the discussion, suddenly my department HOD raised a question that you have launched propaganda in the Facebook post against your colleague. After hearing the long discussion, I was shocked, and finally, they were arguing that you want to have ethnic disputes in cyberspace. I finally told them that the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology (MCIT) of Afghanistan, has a special department for controlling these kinds of situations. Its name is Afghanistan Cyber Emergency Response Team (AFCERT), so please inform that department. However, the HOD was still insisting that you had done wrong things and asked for forgiveness. Finally, the case was rejected and was not proven against me. This was a practical example of my life experience of ethnocentrism in social media.

Hutchinson and Smith (as cited by Scupin, 2012, p. 124) noticed that "ethnicity" is a Greek word taken from "ethnos" or "ethnikos" which was referring to the non-Greeks who had some common lifestyle. Ultimately, Europeans used ethnicity as a word associated with race. Furthermore, Scupin (2012) elaborated on ethnicity more specifically, that it has two aspects 1) objective aspect and 2) subjective aspect. The objective aspect is the visible shared cultural symbols and practices among the people. In addition, the subjective aspect belongs to the inside common beliefs among the people. Furthermore, the subjective aspect gives the sense of "we-feeling" for "in-group" and the them-feeling of sense for "out-group" (p. 125). Hence, it is argued that ethnicity is summed up by cultural characteristics.

As every phenomenon has different dimensions for academic research, similarly, ethnocentrism also has different dimensions to be studied, such as in anthropological, economic, political, social, psychological, and other fields. Therefore, ethnocentrism is defined as a self-group-centered behavior. Huntington (1993) has written a controversial thesis and he is arguing that it is the "Clash of Civilizations" that the spread of ethnic strife, exemplified by "ethnic cleansing" at its extreme, has not been entirely random. It has been the most common and most violent amongst tribes from various cultures (p. 34). Ethnicity has a great problem for the world; ethnocentrism

(Axelrod & Hammond, 2003). Similarly, Borden (2007) launched a pre and post Generalized Ethnocentrism Scale for different cultures' "service-learning," which was significantly positive changed from strong ethnocentric behavior to normalized ethnocentric behavior. Because ethnocentrism is a strong discrimination dimension (Huntington, 1993).

In recent decades, "indigenous psychology," including cultural psychological research, has advocated for less ethnocentrism and more intercultural competency in psychology. Indigenous psychology, on the other hand, calls for a broader acceptance of non-Western indigenous concepts of science, thinking traditions, and research methods. Cultural psychology must be judged by the sincerity of its claims when it comes to the learning and teaching of appropriate competencies, as well as the destruction of ethnocentrically-based obstacles and knowledge deficiencies (Yeh et al., 2021, p. 233).

Many questions arise in the mind. Is there a distinction between culture, racism, and ethnocentrism? Understanding culture, ethnicity, and race is crucial before distinguishing among them.

Ethnocentrism is a "syndrome" of attitude and behavior towards an "in-group and out-group" that creates a problem for the out-group and does a favor for the in-group, such as praising the in-group and defaming the out-group (Francis et al., 1973). In other words, the in-group feels honorable and superior but the out-group is inferior and contemptuous. LeVine & Campbell (cited by Mounsey, 2007) argued in the article that ethnocentrism is the in-group priority and that this is the whole human behavior toward intergroup relations. Moreover, the in-group has cooperative relations with the out-group. Similarly, Shankarmahesh (2006) also argued in their article that ethnocentrism's in-group focus was less on its development than contempt for the out-group. Moreover, it shows that the out-group is anti-thesis, anti-values, beliefs, and morals of the in-group. Ethnocentrism is almost a worldwide psychological syndrome. In this condition, members of one group are helpful, which is called an in-group, but the out-group is not. In-group behavior can be influenced by one factor or one dimension such as language, accent, physical features, or common relations (Axelrod & Hammond, 2003).

Tajfel (as cited by Axelrod & Hammond, 2003) revealed in his research that the relationship of a group member becomes more prominent. Another research by Cashdan discovered that out-group aggression and in-group favoritism are two different dimensions that don't seem to be correlated (Axelrod & Hammond, 2003). Some researchers claim that “ethnocentrism is re-conceptualized as a strong sense of ethnic group self-centeredness, which involves intergroup expressions of ethnic group preference, superiority, purity, and exploitativeness, and intragroup expressions of ethnic group cohesion and devotion” (Bizumic & Duckitt, 2012, p. 887). Likewise, Bizumic & Sheppard (2021) defined ethnocentrism from the political psychological perspective that it is a global topic that promotes “self-centeredness and self-importance” toward others.

Every phenomenon has positivity and negativity. Similarly, ethnocentrism also has both aspects. The positive point of ethnocentrism is significantly proven that it is used for strong communication and understanding of in-group with its members. In other words, the low level of ethnocentrism shows the low level of in-group understanding among the members of the ethnic group (Chow, 2015). Ethnocentric behavior played a significant mediating role in predicting ethnic prejudice between the outgroup and low openness among the participants (Huxley et al., 2015). Ethnocentrism has many relationships with other phenomena, for instance, consumer and buying relationships with ethnocentrism, ethnocentrism relationships with services, and ethnocentrism relations with technologies (Pereira et al., 2002; Speece & Pinkaeo, 2002).

Giuliano (as cited by Green & Seher, 2003) has written regarding the Tartastan ethnic conflict. Ethnic mobilization is current issue support that helps devotion to one ethnic group. Moreover, the ethnicity has pre-existing faith and speeches that support the politician, and they add that there is a relationship between psychosocial and ethnic violence. Psychology sees ethnicity conflict as an inside feeling with bias.

Biologically, the relationship of one ancestor with its offspring is called race (Scupin, 2012). It is the best dimension for distinguishing one race from another. However, believing in the human race's superiority and inferiority is called racism. For instance, the biological dimensions for making differences among people are white, yellow, and black, or Caucasoid, Mongoloid, and Negroid (Scupin, 2012). On the other hand, ethnicity is a multidimensional phenomenon. Ethnicity is a sociological, political,

anthropological, economic, linguistic, and cultural phenomenon through which one Homo sapiens can be distinguished from another. Scupin (2012) cited that having a belief that one's ethnic dimension is superior and another's inferior is called ethnocentrism. For instance, especially in cultural status, society, language, economic status, political status, and many other factors, this superiority of one's own ethnicity and other inferiorities is called ethnocentrism. Furthermore, race is a purely natural phenomenon, but ethnicity is a multi-factorial acquisitive phenomenon that can be gained, lost, or changed. For instance, in Han people's behavior, which was discussed by Yeh et al. (2021), the majority Han group's "hegemonic dominance over notions of self-construal, mental spaces, morality, intelligence, health, and agency" might represent a threat to less powerful ethnic groups. Furthermore, China has a history of interracial conflicts caused by the force of the Han people's unilateral assimilation (p. 91).

In summary, we can say that ethnocentrism is in-group favoritism and out-group hostility. Ethnocentric behavior is an evolutionary process for interacting with members of one's own in-group and the evolutionary process for dealing with members of other groups. Moreover, in-group and out-group hostility causes different ethnic conflicts and wars. These outbreaks of violence are feasible in the digital era as well.

2.1.1 Culture

The term "culture" is taken from Latin words, which has primarily two meanings: one relates to an individual's body of information and manners; and the second refers to the common conventions, values, and beliefs that characterize a certain social group and are passed down from generation to generation (Bolaffi et al., 2003, p. 61). Culture, according to Huntington (1993), is a component of civilization. Villages, regions, ethnic groupings, countries, and religious groups, for example, all have unique cultures with varying degrees of cultural variability. Thus, civilization is the highest level of cultural identification that individuals have short of that which separates humans from other animals. Language, history, religion, customs, and institutions are all shared objective features, as are people's subjective self-identification (Huntington, 1993).

Culture is the holistic soft power of a society, which holds the society's members together by "shared beliefs, feelings, knowledge, and common history," and shows the possession of the in-group. Through culture, the members of society communicate with one another and conclude (Mantovani, 2012, p. 66). While, Birkbeck (1993) elaborates on culture as "values, ideas, and behaviors that may be associated with one or more than one social or national group" (p. 307).

Furthermore, Ray (1971) argued that a group member gives high value to culture and their own ethnic group compared to another group. For instance, Jews become ethnically prejudiced against non-Jews "gentiles and goys" marrying their daughters. Similarly, many Indians also do not allow different castes and Jati to marry. As an example, the great, Mahatma Gandhi also did not allow his son to marry a girl of another caste or Jati (Desai, 2015). Even so, Indians still have this behavior and prefer to marry within their caste (Dhar, 2013).

E. B. Tylor, a British anthropologist (as cited in Scupin, 2012, p. 134), elaborated on the cultural definition. They argued, "Culture is that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, arts, morals, law, custom, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man [kind] as a member of society." It seems this definition includes every era of all progress and technological advancement. Furthermore, Scupin (2012) added that culture is the previous societal collection that transformed generation to generation in a symbolic way. Which has two dimensions: "material and non-material" (p. 138).

2.1.2 Ethnicity

Technically, the Oxford Dictionary used the term "ethnicity" as "the fact of belonging to a particular nation or people that share a cultural tradition" (Dictionaries, 2022). On the other hand, anthropologists argue that ethnicity is the "absolute character" of in-group identity and "lived experiences," for instance, emotionally, socially, and culturally attachment to a group, which clarifies the common "symbols" (Gautam, 2013). However, currently, it is used for human cultures (Gautam, 2013). Political scientists use ethnicity as an autonomous variable to elaborate on "culture," in addition to the anthropology discipline; it is a dependent variable that elaborates on behavior. In other words, the Diaspora discipline proves that the creation of identity

changed to “ethnicity,” which shares the cultural commonalities among a group societies (Gautam, 2013).

In 1972, Glazer & Moynihan (as cited in Gautam, 2013), helped the Oxford Dictionary use the ethnicity term for the first time. It defined the socio-political aspects of society. At that time, it gave a sense of ethnic pride to one group, having shared membership, cooperating socio-cultural norms, values, and costumes (Gautam, 2013). However, Huntington (1993) defined ethnicity as identity and argued that people who identify their identity in terms of ethnicity and religion are more prone to view an "us" versus "them" relationship between themselves and people of other ethnicities or religions.

Gautam (2013) identified in his report that the “ethnic” term has been used by Anthropologists and Ethnologists for "ethnography", which gives the meaning of a “biological self-perpetuating group” through which it shares “culture and communication,” which provide a social bond between people of the same ethnicity. Furthermore, identity, in a diasporic way, becomes ethnicity. Such as Indian ethnicity, Afghan ethnicity, Farsi ethnicity, etc. Through this, one ethnicity can be differentiated from another. Because of ethnocentrism, the USA’s citizens commit hate crimes and prejudice (Pratama, 2019). However, another scholar wrote that race, ethnicity, and culture are all unreliable indicators of violent behavior in the mentally ill. After taking into consideration socioeconomic status and other factors, this is the case (Howitt, 2009, p. 376).

Fundamentally, competition gives a chance for ethnocentric, biased, and other kinds of psychologically negative behavior. This, as a result, shows the in-group bitterness and strength but the weakness and badness of the out-group ethnicity. This behavior leads to psychological and physical conflicts.

Ethnic divisions in Malaysia are also a result of ethnocentrism. According to some research, Malaysians prefer to converse online with members of their ethnic group rather than with people of other ethnic groups. Ethnocentrism may get greater as a result of this. According to several studies, ethnocentrism reduces the motivation to associate with individuals from different cultures. It even prevents high-sensation seekers from forging intercultural friendships. Ethnocentrism also serves as a deterrent to forming intercultural connections. It was found that ethnic disparities exist in Malaysia. These

are frequently manifested in prejudices, discrimination, tensions, and conflict, all of which obstruct the process of creating togetherness (Ridzuan et al., 2012, p. 518).

2.1.3 Ethnicity Term vs Caste Term

The term "ethnic" denotes characteristics that are distinctive of, connected to, or unique to a certain group of people. However, although being effective descriptive tools, both the adjective and the associated word "ethnicity" are scientifically imprecise and unclear (Bolaffi et al., 2003, p. 90). Many people believe that the Greek term comes from Sanskrit. Until the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, ethnicity was frequently related to the concepts of "race, people, and nation," and vestiges of this ambiguity may still be seen today. The concept of ethnicity is soundly applied in three conditions: association of a group, mutual identity, and in-group and out-group ethnicity stereotypes (Bolaffi et al., 2003).

An ethnic group, also known as ethnicity, is a collection of people who share a common culture and characteristics such as shared ancestry, language, history, society, culture, or nation. Ethnicity is often an inherited status depending on one's social environment (Bolaffi et al., 2003, pp. 94–96). Endogamy, the hereditary transfer of a lifestyle that generally includes employment, hierarchy rank, conventional social contact, and exclusion, characterizes caste as a kind of social stratification (Kadel, 2014). Caste is mostly a socially constructed group, while ethnic groups are defined based on geographic and anthropological theories.

However, some authors have noted that ethnicity is frequently defined by physical traits like skin color, although it is not based on any biologically separate "races." Ethnicity is a socially created resource based on religion, language, and nationality, similar to gender (Bendixen et al., 1999, p. 12).

2.1.4 Afghan perspectives

One of the well-known names of Afghanistan is the Heart of Asia, which connects most of the Asian countries through land. It is a "multi-ethnic state." Even though up to now there has been no digital exact census recorded, the official percentage is such as Pashtun 42%, Tajik 27%, Hazara 9%, Uzbek 9%, Aimaq 4%, Turkman 3%, Baluch 2%, and others 4% (Mazhar et al., 2012).

Afghanistan is a crossroads of the Middle East, Central Asia, East Asia, and the Indian subcontinent, located in the center of Asia. Because of its strategic location, it is home to a diverse population of ethnicities. However, this diversity has hampered peacebuilding attempts. With rising ethnic tensions and shifting ethnic lines, no single strategy, plan, or proposal can properly satisfy the needs of all ethnic groups. Politicians in Afghanistan, on the other hand, dismiss ethnicity as a major concern. In certain ways, ethnic rhetoric is taboo to discuss in public. History, on the other hand, bears witness to the contrary, as this study report will demonstrate. Since the founding of the modern state of Afghanistan, ethnic differences have played a key role in the country. This topic was raised during the United Nations' Bonn Conference in 2001, when the UN underscored the significance of maintaining the country's multi-ethnic nature. The conference emphasized the need to ensure that all ethnic groups' political representation and interests were protected. The events that led up to the Bonn Conference, on the other hand, were tangled up in a foggy and obscure ethnic past. The ethnic groups of Afghanistan are not confined to a single location, and in many cases, they overlap, creating a vibrant tapestry of languages and cultures that resembles the exquisite pattern of an Afghan rug (Ali, 2015, p. 1).

The total population of Afghanistan is 39 million (Demographics of Afghanistan Population Statistics, Vital Statistics, Development and Health Indicators, Ethnic Groups, The Free Encyclopedia, 2022). There are many ethnic groups in Afghanistan. For instance, Pashtuns, Tajiks, Uzbeks, Turkmens, Hazaras, Aimaqs, Gujars, Brahues, Qazalbash, Kyrgyz, Arabs, Pamirs, Qizilbashes, Balochs, Pashais, and Nooristanis are among Afghanistan's ethnic groups. The Pashtuns, Tajiks, Uzbeks, and Hazaras, however, make up the majority of the country's population. Due to the lack of a census, the estimated percentage of each ethnicity is highly controversial (Ali, 2015, p. 2; Siddique, 2012).

2.1.5 Ethnocentrism in Afghanistan

Ethnicity is one distinctive dimension for understanding one individual group from another. In this era, some major ethnicities have changed in a negative way of understanding. In particular, ethnicity in Afghan society has brought some unpredictable negative results. In Afghanistan, ethnicity has brought some new changes in the social and political dimensions (Mazhar et al., 2012). Siddique (2012) points out

some social conflict because of ethnicity in Afghanistan, which is currently threatening the peace inside the country. Mostly, ethnic cleansing based on politics and internal war (the 1980s–2000s) was the main cause of ethnic hegemony (Marsden, 2001). However, before the 1980s, there were no ethnocentric problems because every ruler knew that he was multi-linguistic and was working for unity (Siddique, 2012). Even though, a researcher claimed that; during the civil war in Afghanistan, ethnic members fought for hegemony and regional power until the Taliban removed them all (Ali, 2015).

Hanley (2011) cited in his war report that Afghan violence has many factors, and one of them is ethnicity, which promotes internal violence among the members of ethnic groups. Khawrin (2021) proved in his research that even ethnic hegemony and problems happen in the current high technology sphere. He statistically showed that ethnocentrism behavior significantly triggered issues among the ethnic and outside groups. In addition, he showed that ethnocentrism has a positive statistical correlation with Afghan nationals in cyberspace via cyberbullying and cyber victimization. In addition, he showed that Afghan gender and age factors did not have a significant impact on ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization. However, in another research, it was proved that there was no significant difference between the Afghan ethnicities; Pashtun, Tajik, Hazara, and other minorities; via ethnocentrism behavior. In addition, it was found that internet surfing has a positive and significant association with cyberbullying and victimization (Khawrin et al., 2021b).

2.1.6 Indian perspective

Some documentaries show that the younger Indian generation has witnessed cyberbullying behaviors in different spheres of life. For instance, in 2014, the daughter of Pooja Bedi became a cyber-victim at the age of 17 by her classmates through social media and internet surfing (Chandra, 2018). In another case, Sharanya faced psychological disorder for months just by reading her friend's WhatsApp message. Similarly, in the case of Amita, who tried to commit suicide just by seeing her naked pics on Facebook messenger (Chandra, 2018). Furthermore, some applications are working online for different purposes of destabilizing social norms, such as live "self-harming," "constructive feedback," etc. Some of these online applications are the Blue Whale Challenge and Sarahah (Chandra, 2018).

One of the epidemic behaviors is cyberbullying. Which is more popular among Generation Z. However, it can affect a person's mental and physical health. India has the fourth position in the world in cyberbullying behavior (Bhatia, 2022). Cyberbullying is a type of online communication in which a person or a group of people harasses, threatens, or anguishes a person's reputation and privacy, having a long-term traumatic effect on that individual. It refers to exceeding the legal limit and using the internet in an unauthorized manner that has an impact on a person's life and survival (Arora, 2020, p. 351).

2.1.7 Ethnocentrism in India

Das & Uddin (2022) proved in their bottom-up method that Asian states such as India, China, Myanmar, Bangladesh, Indonesia, and Thailand have many barriers to nation-building. Some of these barriers are ethnic, race, ethnicity, caste, and religious conflicts. In addition, it has a direct influence on civilian lives. For instance, these issues are triggered by power, which brings bias, prejudice, racism, and stereotypes systematically.

Indian castes have been defined through different dimensions, and it is a syntax of socio-political system. Which is defined as below.

“Caste has been a form of social stratification characterized by endogamy, hereditary transmission of a lifestyle, which often includes an occupation, ritual status in a hierarchy and customary social interaction and exclusion based on cultural notions of purity and pollution. Hierarchy, commensality, repulsion and hereditary membership and specialization are the major characteristics of caste system.” (Kadel, 2014, p. 9)

Sharma (2013) discovered in his conference paper that Indian upper castes neglected and did not give importance to Scheduled Castes (SC) and Scheduled Tribes (ST). In addition, upper-caste Indians show bias, prejudice, and crime against the lower castes. However, official district-level data of 2001-10 proved that crime has a positive and significant correlation with the expenses of lower castes; however; upper-caste was vice versa.

Basu et al. (2003) published a statistical study of 58 DNA markers (mitochondrial [mt], Y-chromosomal, and autosomal) and mtHVS1 sequencing data from a large number of ethnically varied Indian groups. The tribal and caste populations are very differentiated; the Austro-Asiatic tribal were the first settlers in India, providing support for one anthropological hypotheses while refuting another; a major wave of humans entered India from the northeast; The Tibeto-Burman tribes share significant genetic similarities with the Austro-Asiatic tribes, implying that they may have shared a common habitat in southern China, but the two groups of tribes can be distinguished by Y-chromosomal haplotypes; the Dravidian tribes were possibly widespread throughout India before the arrival of the Indo-European-speaking nomads, but retreated to southern India to avoid dominance; population formation; The upper castes have closer genetic affinities with Central Asian populations, though those in southern India are further apart than those in northern India; historical gene flow into India has contributed to a significant obliteration of contemporary populations' genetic histories, so there is no clear congruence of genetic, geographical, or socio-cultural affinities at the moment.

2.1.8 Caste system in India

The author discusses the issues surrounding the usage of the term "ethnicity" in the Indian context and refutes the notion that "ethnic conflict" in India is a threat to democracy or the Indian state's coherence (Manor, 1996, p. 459). In India, ethnicity is a difficult concept to grasp. From an Indian perspective, there are five theories for understanding this concept. First, religiously based identities. This mostly relates to Hindus (about 82%), Muslims (12%), and Sikhs (about 2%) (Manor, 1996, p. 461). Second, identities are based on language. India has at least nine main languages and a large number of minor languages. Third, Adivasis, or "scheduled tribes", have "tribal" identities. Adivasis are a tough group to classify; to put it bluntly, they tend to exist outside of Hindu society, as they do not adhere to traditional Hindu religious practices, and many do not organize themselves into Jatis (endogamous castes). Fourth, people in Himalayan or rural northeastern locations have tribal identities. Fifth, identities such as Aryan and Dravidian (Manor, 1996, p. 462).

The "caste system" divides the Hindu people into thousands of groupings known as "jatis" (castes). These groupings arose from the ancient Varna system (also known as caste), which separated society into the following classes and orders. For instance, Brahmins, Kshatriya, Vaishya, and Shudra (Sharma, 2013, p. 4).

The Indian caste system is significantly based on social, educational, and economic backwardness. The Constitution designated the untouchable Jatis and Adivasis as Scheduled Castes (SC) and Scheduled Tribes (ST) in 1950. They were given affirmative action in the form of reservations or quotas in national and state legislatures, local village councils, higher education institutions, and government positions. Since the early 1990s, reservations have been extended to the third category of people. While not subject to the stigma of untouchability, the Other Backward Classes (OBC) were socially and educationally behind, suffering from a prolonged lack of opportunity and low socio-economic outcomes (Sharma, 2013, p. 5).

However, it occurs worldwide. India, Brazil, and the United States are the top three nations where cyberbullying is most widespread (Todorov, 2022). The most prevalent cause of cyberbullying appears to be personal attractiveness (61 percent), followed by intelligence in the class (25 percent). Racism (17%) and sexual discrimination (15%) are also common forms of prejudice, as are insulting someone for their financial issues (15%) and religion (11 percent) (Djuraskovic, 2022b).

2.2 Introduction to Cyberbullying and Cyber victim

In 2018, one incident happened when one of my colleagues changed his name and gender on Facebook and sent me messages. First, he made a friendship. I was surprised at how it happened that someone unknown wanted to have a friendship and was sending me sexting text messages. I blocked that person but under a different name. The person wants to contact me. I thought that I would bring this person to the right path, but the person was making me astray and asking for some information. Then I directly told the person that I know you and you are my colleague, and if you keep texting, I and want to tease me again, then I would directly unveil all your messages in front of all academia. After the threat, that person stopped messaging me.

Every educational and academic institution gives new skills to their output through teaching and interaction of students with one another. Besides that, these students learn the misuse of these skills. For instance, the new generation of students learn digital skills, and these digital skills can be altered to be misused against their peers, teachers, or any other person whom they want. This new digital misuse is called "cyberspace misusing." This new technology has many types, and day by day, its number is increasing.

According to Hinduja & Patchin (2010), cyberbullying is a behavior that transcends all geographical boundaries. The Internet has effectively opened up the entire globe to people who access it through a variety of devices, which has been a good thing for the most part. Digital bullying is the use of computers, cell phones, and other electronic devices to inflict purposeful and repetitive harm. Furthermore, estimates of the proportion of young people who are victims of cyberbullying vary substantially (from 10% to 40% or more), depending on the age group investigated and how cyberbullying is properly defined.

2.2.1 Bullying

Donegan (2012) defined that, directly or indirectly, one person bullying another through physical or non-physical power to show dominance is called bullying. All species have a survival instinct; therefore, they do those activities that can protect them and take action against others. Similarly, humans also do these actions. Which can be seen at different organizational and societal levels. Moreover, this hierarchical chain can be seen in different cultural systems, such as the "ethnic system, tradition" and the ruling power of states (Donegan, 2012). This behavior leads to a negative influence on all areas of life. Because of technological changes, they introduce a new space for communication even though this place also has some issues that can harm humans.

Tiffany (2018) argued that countries give priority to different angles for defining cyberbullying. In general, they are deliberate action with harm, imbalance of power among the parties, aggressiveness, repetition in action, using electronic devices, the relationship among the parties to the action, and anonymously taking action.

Afghanistan and India have codified cyber laws from different dimensions to ensure their civilian rights and lives. For instance, to protect from any harm, ensure

harmony, and soften personalities at national and international levels. However, all human societies have some issues in their era. So in this new Artificial Intelligence (AI) era, the cyberspace area needs to impose the laws of the land and globe. Every state is codifying laws and regulations for the safety and sovereignty of its citizens. Afghanistan's criminal code was enforced in 2017, which has one chapter for cybersecurity and criminal activities and its offenders' punishment (Criminal Code of Afghanistan, 2017). On the other hand, India also has many provisions and codes to tackle cyber-criminal activities The Information Technology Act of India 2000, and The Indian Penal Code of 2018 (The Indian Penal Code, 2018; The Information Technology Act of India, 2000).

In the digital space, it has been witnessed that gender has significant differences in soft harm such as teasing and harassment. Moreover, the faulty justice systems for cyberspace in the USA, UK, and India cause more harm to the victims (Halder & Jaishankar, 2011). Similarly, Felt (2001) discovered that many teenagers' deaths happened because of cyberbullying in Canada. In 2001, the Canadian legislature was not able to name these kinds of soft-harming behaviors in cyberspace. In academic documentation, bullying is first recorded in 1802 as a social problem among classmates in Norway. Because of this behavior, three boys committed suicide. Therefore, many States in Europe start taking care of teenagers in the school area (Felt, 2001). Latterly, online gossiping is also included as a form of cyberbullying behavior (Marcum et al., 2012). Nycyk (2015) elaborates that intentional harmful activities on electronic devices are called cyberbullying behavior. It took place in different formats, such as texting, photos, memes, emoji, audio, and video, creating fake profiles, deceiving others of different genders, and sharing personal information. Furthermore, threatening or making fun of someone's color, race, ethnicity, culture, or any other identity is illegal.

2.2.2 A technological development

The development of electronic virtual communication has two faces; those are the good face and the bad face. Similarly, most phenomena have good and bad aspects. One of the most misused forms of technology is cyberbullying. Most of this digital bullying behavior takes place on cell-communicative technologies and social media (Donegan, 2012).

2.2.3 Cyber environment

Cyberbullying and cyber victimization can occur in a variety of ways. Everything may be divided into two pieces. First, electronic devices are used without an internet connection. Secondly, those that occurred with technological devices that have an internet connection. For instance, cell phones, telephones, and text messaging (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016). This cyberbullying and cyber victimization behavior happen in different forms such as text, audio, video, and multimedia, gaming devices, and social networking sites, and the author cited instant messages and chat rooms (Bauman, 2007).

2.2.4 World internet users

In January 2022, 4.95 billion individuals utilized the internet worldwide, accounting for 62.5 percent of the global population. More than nine out of ten internet users (93.4%) use social media at least once a month, and seven social media networks today claim to have over one billion monthly active users. Meanwhile, smartphones account for about 4 in 5 of all mobile telephones in use today, with more than two-thirds of the world's population owning one (*Digital Around the World — DataReportal – Global Digital Insights, 2022*).

Internet users have different prevalence with different effects. Some of the examples are discussed. According to the Pew Internet and American Life Project (PEW), 68 percent of Internet users are anxious about thieves gaining access to their credit card information, while 84 percent are concerned about their personal information being compromised (Jean Camp & Eric Johnson, 2012). According to Ybarra and Mitchell (as cited by Campfield, 2008), 12 percent of regular Internet users who were reportedly involved in online aggression in the previous year reported being aggressors, 4 percent reported being targets of online aggression, and 3 percent identified themselves as aggressors and targets. Only approximately 30% of the targets reported knowing the harasser, but a high majority of the aggressors (84%) knew their victims.

In the United Kingdom, it is believed that 99 percent of 12-to 24-year-olds access the internet, with young people spending growing amounts of time on technology (Betts & Spenser, 2017). Moreover, in the United Kingdom, 12 percent of

internet users aged 11 to 16 had received sexual communications, with 4% sending sexts. A study conducted in five EU nations, including the UK, indicated a rise in the number of young people reporting seeing sexually explicit images, particularly among adolescent girls, between 2010 and 2013 (P. K. Smith et al., 2014).

According to Pratomo (as cited by Akrim & Sulasmi, 2020), the results of an Indonesian polling study conducted in collaboration with the Association of Indonesian Internet Service Providers (APJII) revealed that approximately 49 percent of internet users had been victims of cyberbullying on social media. Furthermore, according to Retno Listyarti, the Indonesian Child Protection Commission (KPAI) has received hundreds of allegations of cyberbullying that suppressed the internet.

In 2000, two board surveys were taken into account by Beatbullying and #DeleteCyberbullying. It showed that European youngsters and children think similarly. Thirty-four percent of participants perceived cyberbullying and bullying as normal activities, but the abnormal activity was distinguished by children displaying sexual images (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016).

During the COVID-19 epidemic, the rate of cybercrime soared by 600 percent. In 2020, the financial industry incurred the most financial losses. In 2021, the overall cost of all cybercrime losses is anticipated to reach around \$6 trillion globally (Pitchkites, 2022).

2.2.5 Internet users in India

In January 2022, India had 658.0 million internet users. At the start of 2022, India's internet penetration rate was 47.0 percent of the total population. India has 467.0 million social media users. India's social media users accounted for 33.4 percent of the entire population, but it's vital to remember that social media users don't always represent distinct individuals (KEMP, 2022b). So far, in 2018, India has had the highest percentage of youngsters being victims of cyberbullying. Over 37% of Indian parents say their children have been victims of cyberbullying at least once, up 5% from 2016 (Djuraskovic, 2022a).

The necessity for critical research that investigates the contextual and cultural lenses through which cyberbullying might be seen is highlighted. The definitional

challenges of cyberbullying involve these three components of intentionality, repetition, and power imbalance (Giumetti & Kowalski, 2019, pp. 3–4).

Figure 3 Effects of cyber space for different age groups, gender and population

Note: Types of and infected personality of Cyberbullying behavior (*Isometric Cyberbullying-Infographics with Online Threats Aggressive Comments Vector Illustration*, n.d.).

The use of social media is fast and drastically expanding at all levels of society, as well as in more nations throughout the world. A social networking site is an online venue where a user may establish a profile and a personal network to communicate with other users. There were 54 percent of male users and 46 percent of female users, according to the data. Malaysians also spend the most time on such sites every week. Malaysians spend an average of nine hours each week on social media platforms. People are now spending more time on social networking sites than on email, according to the report (Ridzuan et al., 2012, pp. 518–519).

2.2.6 Internet users in Afghanistan

In January 2022, Afghanistan had 9.23 million internet users. At the start of 2022, Afghanistan's internet penetration rate was 22.9 percent of the overall population. In Afghanistan, there were 4.15 million social media users (KEMP, 2022a).

The usage of online applications for modern communication is nearly universal, which may foster negative or cyberbullying behaviors. Six hundred and twenty-nine Afghan university students were asked to participate in the study. The findings demonstrated that cyberbullying was prevalent among Afghan students, both perpetrators, and victims. Facebook was also determined to play the most important influence in the promotion and prevalence of cyberbullying. The cyber perpetrator was revealed to have gender disparities. Female students were more vulnerable to victimization than male students. There were statistically significant differences in the prevalence of cyber victimization by age group and internet frequency. However, this was in contrast to cyberbullying among Afghan students. Cyberbullying and cyber victimization were found to have a substantial positive association (Hashemi, 2021).

2.3 Concept of Cyberbullying and Cyber victimization

In the face of new kinds of delinquency linked to the growth of internet users, criminal psychology should actively pursue the research of criminogenic elements that encourage deviant behavior. An environment of anonymity is created by digital infrastructures that shield, encourage, and foster new means of assault against people. Furthermore, because of the nature of the internet and the intercommunication capabilities provided by information and communication technology (ICT), criminal behavior has a damaging potential that amplifies the possibility of third-party harm. In this view, it is vital to identify and enhance the current linkages between the virtual space's limitations and regulations, and the attraction or development of delinquency that results. However, situational prevention measures infringe on internet users' rights to privacy, speech, and navigation (Agustina, 2015, p. 36). The terms "cyberbullying" and "cyber victimization" are a combination of "cyber" and "bullying," as well as "victimization." We must first comprehend the meaning of these phrases before proceeding.

2.3.1 Cyberbullying

Cyberbullying is an epidemic of cyber-psychological behavior. Most of the time, intentional cyber activity happen against someone who cannot defend himself/herself. Even though the benefit of these services is to facilitate

communication, transactions, and sharing of soft data among the homo-sapiens, the technologies are now also involved in forming and influencing human behavior.

Prominent researchers Smith et al. (2008) defined cyberbullying as “an aggressive, intentional act carried out by a group or individual, using electronic forms of contact, repeatedly and overtime against a victim who cannot easily defend him or herself” (p.376). From this definition, it can be seen that there are eight characteristics of cyberbullying, such as determination of harm, cyberbullying, the reputation of action, use of a digital machine, communication through cyberspace, feeling of harm which affects psychological changes, a person who becomes a victim or victims, and powerless to defend. Furthermore, this definition distinguishes cyberbullying behavior from other forms of cybercrime.

The medium of cyberbullying is a soft format of the text, video, audio, pictures, memes, emoji, and other emoji through social media and networking sites, such as Facebook, YouTube, and blogs, which connect one person to another. This soft data, which degrades the victim's reputation, is called cyberbullying behavior (Li et al., 2012).

Jenaro, Flores, & Frías (2018) has cited about the adolescent from various authors (Garaigordobil, 2011; Selkie, Fales, & Moreno, 2016) and found that the prevalence of cybercrime ranged from 1%–4% perpetrators and 3%–72% cyber victimization, while cyber perpetration and victimization are 2.3%–16.7%. Females argue that they have been sexually clobbering victimized because of their gender, and males argue that they are cyber victimized because of their ethnicity (Faucher et al., 2014, p. 5). Moreover, another author statistically proved that males are more cyberbullied in these digital actions (Aboujaoude et al., 2015).

Interpersonal relationships such as parent-adolescent relationships, student-teacher relationships, and peer supporter relationships are important variables for controlling and intervening in cyberbullying and cyber victimization. Moreover, it can be assumed that adults' protective measures are also the same (Jenaro et al., 2018).

Zych, Izabela Ortega-Ruiz, Rosario Del Rey, and Rosario (2015) conducted a systematic review of theoretical studies on bullying and cyberbullying. They revealed that Nakamoto and Schwartz (2009) discovered a weak negative and significant relationship between peer victimization and academic achievement ($r = -.12$; 95% CI:

-.15 to -.09) respectively. However, the gender difference was not proven. Moreover, the results showed that cyberbullying victimization has weak academic achievement, psychological, and affective problems.

The cyberbullying field is open to both adults and school-age students (Jenaro et al., 2018). In one middle school survey (1105), participants' active, passive, and reactive responses have been revealed. It has been revealed that bystanders play an important role in controlling and reducing cyberbullying actions. Moreover, they can save a cyber victim (Holfeld, 2014).

In this digital era, cyberbullying is a global issue that shows the starting point of hostile behavior (Jenaro et al., 2018). Cyberbullying is the same as bullying, which occurs in digital space but creates different problems (Englander, 2020; Nycyk, 2015). Even though the younger generation with artificial intelligence has many facilities, they also have many problems. For instance, using technology brought aggressive behavior, cyberstalking, hacking, phishing, cyberbullying, and many others. Cyberbullying is "willful and repeated harm inflicted through the use of computers, cell phones, and other electronic devices" among different genders and ages of internet users (Chandra, 2018). In addition, Parks (2013) argued regarding cyberbullying as below: "with cyberbullying, bullies no longer need to confront their victims face-to-face. Instead, young cyberbullies use communications technology to annoy, embarrass, humiliate, abuse, threaten, stalk, or harass other children or teenagers" (p. 8).

Cyberbullying is a kind of hostility that involves the use of information and communication technology to cause harm to others (Chu et al., 2021). Olweus (as cited by Zsila, 2018) Persistent, hostile behavior marked by a power imbalance, intentionality, and negative psychological repercussions for both the perpetrator and the victim is classified as bullying. On the understanding that this behavior takes place in digital space or cyberspace, it is called cyberbullying.

It is inferred that digital bullies and bystanders engage in a kind of soft harming of oneself or others based on digital identity. On the other hand, ethnicity is an amalgamation of biological and sociological aspects. Therefore, ethnicity is the biosocial identity of a person, group, or people. For this reason, if the plaudit behavior happens for one's own biosocial identity, it is called ethnocentrism. So, ethnocentrism itself does not have any problems, but when compared with other biosocial identities, which show others as inferior, this creates problems. Furthermore, the digital

aggression that appears as a soft harming of people's biosocial identities is called "cyber ethnocentrism."

Every country and academician has defined cyberbullying differently. Because information and communication technologies (ICTs) are in continuous progress, it is very difficult to deliver one accepted definition, which can conclude all its space. For this reason, every country defines cyberbullying according to its source. The growth of information and communication technologies (ICTs) gives the cyberbully the ability to access its prey at any place and any cost. He/she cannot secure him/herself. More importantly, the technology enables the predator to hide its identity (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016).

A published report cited the cyberbullying definition according to different countries' perspectives. As the Czech Republic defines cyberbullying as the intentional misuse of ICTs through digital devices, which emerges in a psychological form, is called cyberbullying. France defines cyberbullying as a hostile, deliberately repeated action against someone who cannot protect himself (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016).

Dinh et al. (2016) cited that 91.7% of cyberbullying and cyber victims consisted of hate speech and sexual content at the top of the activities. Moreover, cyberbullying is known as a kind of deliberate cyber-aggressive behavior that takes place in a repetitive way against a person who cannot be rescued (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016). Cyberbullying is the repeated use of digital devices with the intention of harming someone. It has some components, such as willful, repeated, and aggressive behavior through the use of artificial intelligence (Jenaro et al., 2018).

According to the research of Kowalski et al. (as cited by Giumetti & Kowalski, 2019) internet surfing is regularly linked to cyberbullying participation. Cyberbullying correlates with different demographic factors, for instance, age, race, ethnicity, gender, and some other variables. Of these factors, cyberbullying was predicted to some extent (Giumetti & Kowalski, 2019). The study statistically proved that online harassment differed by ethnicity among adults, with 59 percent of Black/African Americans, 41 percent of White Americans, and 48 percent of Hispanics reporting being harassed online due to their ethnicity. A quarter of Black and African American Americans said they have been harassed online because of their race or ethnicity, compared to 3% of whites and 10% of Hispanics (Giumetti & Kowalski, 2019, p. 26).

Along this lifespan continuum, we find cyberbullying targeting academic members and other teaching employees in institutions. Cyberbullying at universities is unique in that it serves as a link between bullying in schools and workplace bullying. The permanence of roles, such as victim, bully, and bully-victim, as well as the comparable repercussions described at both the school, university, and workplace levels have been underlined (Navarro et al., 2015).

2.3.1.1 Forms of cyberbullying

There are many forms of cyberbullying and victimization. In addition, with the changes in technology, the forms of these negative behaviors are also changing. Some of these forms are written as below. Through technology, bullied; posting mean comments, hurtful comments, mean or hurtful pictures, mean or hurtful videos, mean or hurtful web pages, online rumors, showing different genders, pretending as different people, and misusing others' privacy and identification (Patchin & Hinduja, 2012).

The misery of cyberbullying does not end when the bell sounds. On the Internet, bullies may now taunt, threaten, harass, humiliate, and sham their peers at all hours of the day and night. Bullies may now administer daily doses of humiliation by simply publishing a message on their personal web page or sending an e-mail about the victim to everyone in the class, whereas before rumors and hate were disseminated by passing notes or making "slam" books (Parks, 2013, p. 12). According to some studies, the most common kinds of cyberbullying activities include spreading rumors, humiliating, demeaning, and threatening (Duman & Bridge, 2020). Cyberbullies use a variety of strategies to damage their victims. Educators must understand how technology can be used to bully others (Bauman, 2007).

Forms of cyberbullying and cyber victims are as below:

1. Flaming: Online fights include furious and profane electronic messages (Bauman, 2007; Chandra, 2018).
2. Harassment: sending unpleasant, nasty, and insulting messages regularly (Bauman, 2007; Chandra, 2018).
3. Denigration: Online dissing is when someone sends or publishes vicious rumors or slander about someone to harm their reputation or friendships

(Chandra, 2018). It is the act of making insulting words about a target and then propagating them on the internet. The statements are frequently fabrications intended to harm the target. The purpose is to smear the target's name or friendships (Bauman, 2007).

4. Impersonation: Getting into someone's account, impersonating that person, and sending messages to harm that person's reputation or friendships (Chandra, 2018).
5. Outing and Trickery: Online sharing of a person's secrets, humiliating information, or photographs (Chandra, 2018). Getting someone to give personal information or secrets, is subsequently posted online (Chandra, 2018).
6. Social Exclusion: exclude someone from an online community, such as a friend list (Bauman, 2007; Chandra, 2018).
7. Cyber threats and cyberstalking: sending texts that contain threats of violence or are very threatening regularly in other words participating in other online behaviors that make a person feel unsafe. (Chandra, 2018). These are the most terrifying types of cyberbullying. The latter entails sending repeated communications containing threats of future harm, whereas the former can include threats to others, threats to harm a third party or parties, or threats to hurt oneself. These kinds of communication are frequently linked to mental suffering (Bauman, 2007).
8. Masquerading: It necessitates advanced technological abilities. Pretending to be the target, the bully sends abusive communications that look like they emanate from the target (Bauman, 2007).

2.3.1.2 History of Cyber Bullying

Since the 1530s, the term "bully" has been used. Bullying requires two people at its most basic level: a bully or intimidator and a victim. The bully attacks the victim physically, verbally, or in other ways to achieve a sense of authority and control. Direct or indirect behavior is possible. Bullying has become more common as technology has advanced. Chat rooms quickly followed the introduction of the Internet. For youngsters to assault one another, online forums provide a collective breeding ground (Donegan, 2012).

Although cyberbullying-like conduct predates the introduction of precise terminology, the phrase appears to have been created in 2000 in Canada by the proprietor of a Web site aimed at combating conventional (face-to-face) bullying. One of the oldest incidents dates back to 1998, when a 14-year-old kid was expelled from school for posting threatening comments about classmates on the internet. A four-year legal fight ensued, culminating in the expulsion being upheld by the Pennsylvania Supreme Court. After multiple suicides were related to cyberbullying, media attention to such incidents steadily grew, becoming more acute in recent years (Aboujaoude et al., 2015).

2.3.1.3 Digital ragging or cyberbullying

It is human instinct to hide from responsibility, especially the offense. In other words, the perpetrator often reports himself as having become an offender. The data regarding the perpetrators of cyberbullying is different according to society. For instance, in the USA and Germany, studies proved that perpetrators of cyberbullying exist with the increase in age and that it continues to adulthood. Furthermore, data from Romania, Portugal, Poland, and Spain showed that cyberbullying increased up to the age of fourteen and continued up to adulthood. But in the United Kingdom, it decreases at the age of 12 to 15 (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016).

In an Indian context, the physical bullying of a student is called ragging. The younger generation is using digital media, so ragging on digital media, such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Viber, and other platforms, is called cyberbullying, which can take place anywhere and anytime (Chandra, 2018, p. 150; Sivakumar, 2013).

2.3.1.4 Cyberbullying and cyber victimization's equivalent terminology

The German term "cyber mobbing" was used for the first time to indicate cyberbullying and victimization. Italian uses the term "virtual" bullying and victim, and Spanish uses the terms "harassment via mobile and internet" (Campbell, 2010, p. 129). Finland uses the terms "web-bullying" to identify these behaviors. Furthermore, there are many terms, such as e-bullying and online bullying, that have also been used by some legal and administrative systems (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016, p. 25).

Many countries have different legal and administrative terminology with different meanings. Therefore, it is very important to know those terms that are used in different places with almost the same meaning. Indians use the term "ragging" for bullying and victimization of peers in classes (Sivakumar, 2013). However, technology is boosting, so the new terms are used, such as cyber-ragging for cyberbullying and cyber-victim for cyberbullying.

2.3.1.5 Kinds of cyberbullying and cyber victims

There are many kinds of cyberbullying and cyber victims, such as mockery, insults, threats, rumors, gossip, disagreeable comments, and slander (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016). Moreover, some authors include these forms also, such as receiving nasty, mean, rude, vulgar, hurtful, or harassing e-mail or text messages; having terrible, derogatory, sexist, racist, or homophobic online postings; posting an embarrassing photo or video; being excluded from an online group chat (Navarro et al., 2015, p. 85).

2.3.1.6 UN definitions of cyberbullying behavior

In its 2016 Annual Report, the UN Special Representative of the Secretary-General on Violence against Children described cyberbullying as “an aggressive, intentional act carried out by a group or individual, using electronic forms of contact, against a victim who cannot easily defend himself or herself” (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016). This definition has four main parts. First, cyberbully, in other words, cyberbullying perpetrators with the intention of harming someone. Second, a cyber-victim is, in simple words, a person who has been harmed by others. Third, using digital technology. And lastly, the victim cannot defend him/herself. In addition, it has been found that there are four main types of people involved in cyberbullying behavior. 1. Pure cyberbullies, 2. Pure cyber victims, 3. Cyberbully and victims, and 4. Those who have neither cyberbullied nor been cyber victimized.

2.3.1.7 Definitions of cyberbullying by academicians

Almost all academicians define cyberbullying as hostile and hateful behavior through electrical devices in a repeated way, and the victim cannot defend himself/herself (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016). The characteristics of cyberbullying by academia are listed below.

- Aggression: Against a person or group;
- Cyber Victim: not able to defend;
- Anonymity of cyberbully;
- Electric device usage;
- Repeated activity;
- Intentionally harm to the victim;
- An imbalance of power, which benefits the perpetrator;
- Harmful content can be posted, reposted, shared, liked, tagged;
- A victim's definite and the form of the content may include text, voice, emoji, pics, videos, and memes (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016; Jenaro et al., 2018).

2.3.1.8 Impacts of digitalization and cyberbullying

Reduce job performance, study /academic procrastination, depression, sleep disorders, stress, Absenteeism, low productivity at work, Lowered self-esteem, depression, Anxiety, Digestive upsets, High blood pressure, Insomnia, Trouble with relationships due to stress over work, Posttraumatic stress disorder There is minimal research available specifically related to adult cyberbullying (Abu Bakar et al., 2013; Minor et al., 2014). Abu Bakar et al. (2013) discussed the kinds of cyberbullying and victims such as “flaming and trolling, online harassment, cyberstalking, denigration, identity theft, outing, ostracism, photo shopping, happy slapping, and sexting” (p. 105).

Furthermore, Hinduja & Patchin (2007) also added that interpersonal violence, both directly and indirectly tied to the Internet, is becoming increasingly common as a growing number of teenagers adopt computer-mediated communication to satisfy scholastic and social demands. Due to the emotional, psychological, and even bodily harm that victims can suffer from cyberbullying, it has risen to the top of agendas in schools and communities. The current study aims to use general strain theory to discover the emotional and behavioral repercussions of being a victim of cyberbullying.

2.3.1.9 Positive impact digitalization

Different services are available because of digitalization. For example, free services; freedom of expression; public opinion; knowledge sharing; well-being;

entertainment; social capital formation through establishing connections with good contacts; finding study materials in both video and textual forms; digital electronic and print media; enhancing public participation and enabling public dealing skills; low self-esteem could increase; and confidence and self-esteem through activities (Tupat & Panda, 2021, pp. 807–808).

2.3.1.10 Negative impact digitalization

Cyberbullying has many negative impacts on individuals and society as well. For instance, being shameful; wasting time on the internet; crazy; hurt; not concentrating on jobs and studies; sad; receiving inaccurate information; unaffected; depressed; propaganda; anxious; angry; more advertisements; distracted; shocked; revengeful; restless; lowering well-being; fearful; hopeless; tired; reducing physical interaction with coworkers; helpless; guilty; cyberbullying; cyber victimization; lonely; suicidal; and malware to technologies are all factors that contribute to a decrease in well-being (Bhatia, 2022; Kowalski et al., 2014; Tennant et al., 2015; Tupat & Panda, 2021, p. 808).

2.3.1.11 Reasons of Cyberbullying Behavior

Every activity was carried out for a variety of reasons. Cyberbullying is also perpetrated for a variety of reasons. It's worded like this: envy, prejudice, and intolerance for disability, religion, gender, humiliation, pride, guilt, rage, anonymity, approbation, boredom makes you feel better, incites jealousy, no repercussions, projection of sentiments, protection, reinvention of self, and retribution (Chandra, 2018).

2.3.1.12 Definitions of cyberbullying and victimization from Indian national level

Bullying is a component of several Indian civilizations. Even though ragging is commonly used to describe school or college bullying. Misuse and abuse of technology, such as the internet and mobile phones, has been documented, and several incidences of cyberbullying have been reported among Indian college students. The study discovered a link between cyber victimization (70 percent) and perpetration (30

percent) and various characteristics. Furthermore, almost 57% of respondents became cyber bystanders in the last six months (Sivakumar, 2013).

Besides that, Khawrin et al. (2022b) conducted a study on the age and internet surfing of the participants as predictors of cyberbullying among the students in Ahmedabad City. He found that internet surfing had a significant predictive value for cyberbullying and cyber victimization. However, age did not show any statistically significant association with the above variables.

The Indian Information Technology Act 2000 act outlines the types of cybercrimes and the penalties for each. Cyberbullying is one such offense that has a life-long devastating impact on the victim that they are unable to overcome. In some cases, the victim may even commit suicide. It's hard to imagine that there isn't particular legislation in India to deal with cyberbullying, but it's real, and with cyberbullying on the rise in India, it's a startling fact (Arora, 2020, p. 351). Some articles which define cyberbullying and victimization up to some extent and predict the punishment are as below.

- Section 66 (A) – This section addresses the penalties for transmitting offensive, disparaging, abusive, or cruel remarks or information via the internet, whether through social media or any other digital chat room or platform (The Information Technology Act of India, 2000 article 66 (A)).

- Section 66 (D)-If someone deceives or cheats someone on the internet, whether, through social media or any other online platform, that person should face up to three years in prison and a fine of up to one lakh rupees (The Information Technology Act of India, 2000 article 66 (D)).

Section 66 (E): This section deals with the punishment for violation of privacy. In case a person infringes on someone's privacy digitally, such as by utilizing their photos or disclosing information, he is guilty of cyberbullying and can be fined up to 3 lakh rupees or imprisoned for up to 3 years (The Information Technology Act of India, 2000 article 66 (E)).

- Section 67-This provision of the legislation stipulates that posting, transmitting or spreading offensive, vulgar, or indecent content over the

internet/cyberspace is punishable by a fine of up to ten lakh rupees or a sentence of up to five years in jail (The Information Technology Act of India, 2000 article 67).

2.3.1.13 Prevalence of cyberbullying and Victimization in India

So far, in 2018, India has had the highest percentage of youngsters being victims of cyberbullying. Over 37% of Indian parents say their children have been victims of cyberbullying at least once, which is 5% more than in 2016 (Djuraskovic, 2022b).

Online bullying is a fairly common phenomenon in India. In a 2012 study of 25 nations, Microsoft Corporation rated India third in the number of reported incidences of online bullying. According to research conducted in 2014 by the Internet security firm McAfee, "Half of the youngsters in India have had some experience with cyberbullying" (Chandra, 2018, pp. 149–150). According to the 2016 Norton Cyber Security Insights Report, 51% of parents throughout the world believe that online bullying is more likely than bullying at school or work (49 percent). Such findings demonstrate the magnitude of the problem produced by cyberbullying, and it is apparent that combating cyberbullying in India is now a major concern (Chandra, 2018, p. 150).

2.3.1.14 Definitions of cyberbullying and victimization from Afghan national level

President Mohammad Ashraf Ghani of Afghanistan signed the Cyber Crime Code into law on June 20, 2017, as part of the country's new Penal Code. The Ministry of Justice's Law Enforcement and Academic-Legal Research Institute are working on the Penal Code. The author got a copy of the Institute's formal letter to the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology (MCIT) from MCIT spokesperson Najeeb Nangial. The Penal Code will consolidate 11 existing criminal statutes and 63 different criminal provisions. "The new Penal Code of Afghanistan answers the demands of today's social and economic context in Afghanistan, and makes the sentence proportionate to the offense," says Mohammad Ashraf Rasoli, a Ministry of Justice expert (Ekhtyar, 2017).

Cybercrime and cyberspace define cybercrime and cyberspace. However, the laws do not have other types or varieties, such as cyberbullying and cyber business and

their offenders. Furthermore, they do not define cyberspace for children, adolescents, and their protection.

The definition of cybercrime and cyberspace given by the Afghan Criminal Code is as below. Article 851:

(1) Cybercrime is a crime committed by modern information technology and electronic or Internet communications in cyberspace.

(2) Cyberspace is a virtual or intangible space created based on the connections of computers or Internet networks (Criminal Code of Afghanistan, 2017 Article 851 (1,2)).

Moreover, the Afghan Criminal Code specifies unauthorized access to cyberspace and its punishment in the below articles.

Article 852:

(1) A person who has unauthorized access to another system, program, or computer information shall be sentenced to a short imprisonment.

(2) A person who, as a result of committing an offense referred to in paragraph (1) of this article, inflicts physical, financial, or moral damage to a person or persons; in addition to the punishment mentioned in paragraph (1) of this article; is also sentenced to the crime of the perpetrator (Criminal Code of Afghanistan, 2017 Article 852 (1,2)).

2.3.1.15 Prevalence of cyberbullying and Victimization in Afghanistan

Cyberbullying was prevalent among Afghan university students, both perpetrators, and victims. Facebook was also determined to play the most important influence in the promotion and prevalence of cyberbullying. The cyberbullying culprit shows gender disparities. Female students were more vulnerable to victimization than male adult students were. There were statistically significant variations in the incidence of cyberbullying victims across age groups and internet frequency, but not in the prevalence of cyberbullying perpetrators among Afghan students. Cyberbullying perpetrators and victims were shown to have a substantial positive association. The authorities and other parties concerned were provided with some practical considerations (Hashemi, 2021).

2.3.1.16 Involved types of cyberbullying behavior

According to the involvement of cyberbullying behavior, there are five types of cyberbullying parties, which are listed below.

1. Cyberbully or cyberbullying perpetrator: A person who just and only engages in bullying behavior through digital space is called a cyberbully or cyberbullying perpetrator.
2. Cyber victim: A person who becomes a digital victim of cyberbullying behavior only becomes a cyber-victim because the cyberbullying action happened against him/her.
3. Cyberbullying perpetrator and victim: A person who simultaneously engages in cyberbullying behavior as a perpetrator and he also becomes a victim of digital behavior.
4. Cyber bystander or witness of cyberbullying: A person who has watched or heard digital behavior but was not involved in cyberbullying behavior and did not become a victim is called a "cyber bystander." In other words, a witness of cyberbullying behavior (Tiffany, 2018).
5. Neither cyberbullying nor victim: A person who has not become a cyber-victim or cyberbullied by another and does not see digital behavior is called an innocent and normal person.

2.3.1.17 Ethnicity with cyberbullying behavior

J. A. Smith & Yoon (2013) clarified in their study of 276 voluntary participants with mixed methods data of qualitative and quantitative data that half (51.8%) of the participants of the university students had experienced or seen cyberbullying behavior over electronic devices. Fortunately, these students were not severely affected. For different reasons, students become cyberbullied and cyber victimized, such as ethnicity (14.3%), age (3.4%), sex of the participants (13.7%), marital status (1.1%), and many other reasons.

Jenaro et al. (2018, p. 3) conducted a systematic assessment of several papers and concluded that females, sexual minorities, and other ethnic minorities appear to be at increased risk. Male perpetrators are more likely, but gender variations across research are inconsistent. A hostile school climate and dangerous Internet practices are also contributing factors.

Heiman & Olenik-Shemesh (2016) conducted a study on 114 samples who were Israeli Arab teenagers. They used the internet for a variety of things, including video games, music, and social networking. There is no major variation in gender. With cyberbullying and victim behavior. There were different forms of bullying, such as sending nasty words, sending humiliating pictures, spreading rumors, and laughing at appearances.

2.3.1.18 Ethnicity difference in regard of cyberbullying and cyber victim behaviors

In an online poll, Patchin & Hinduja (2008) discovered that data from 1,378 teenage Internet users was studied to identify characteristics of typical cyberbullying victims and perpetrators. Although gender and ethnicity did not substantially vary the responses to victimization or offending, computer skills and time spent on the internet were shown to be positively connected to both victimization and offending from cyberbullying. Other researchers also proved that, as Khawrin et al. (Khawrin et al., 2021b) based on the sample's digital bullying and digital victimization, the study found no significant differences across Afghan ethnicities such as Pashtun, Tajik, Hazara, and other minorities. The data for this study came from Kabul's public and private institutions. A total of seven hundred and fifty people freely participated in the study using a random sampling approach. In addition, the sample includes four ethnic groups: Pashtun, Tajik, Hazara, and other minorities (224, 267, 221, and 38, respectively). The results revealed that the relationships between internet browsing, digital bullying, and digital victimization were positively significant. The variances amongst Afghan ethnicities, on the other hand, were not considerably different.

The work by P. Sengupta et al. (2022) revealed the code as a heterogeneous language. In computer models of sociopolitical issues like segregation and ethnocentrism, they looked at the link between language and symbolic violence. They also provided a critical phenomenological description of how computational models of ethnocentrism's transparency and ambiguity embody and execute symbolic power and violence through assumptions of docility and exclusions of oppressed voices and experiences. They provided an empirical vignette as well as theoretical arguments that demonstrate feelings of pain, injustice, and erasure that underpin migration and urban segregation, focusing on the perspectives of immigrants of color and Dalit scholars

from the Global South. Their research shows that learning dignity is not reliant on how dignity is represented digitally, and they propose a fundamental axiological reorientation of computer ontologies toward Southern viewpoints.

2.3.1.19 Race relations with cyber bullying behavior

Black (2014) conducted studies on girls' (59.7%) and boys' (40.3%) students at Southeastern Tennessee City Middle and High Schools with 77 participants. Which includes the Caucasian (67.5%) and Hispanic (19.5%) races. The researcher proved that there was very little evidence (3.9%) that participants were bullied because of their race.

Patchin & Hinduja (2008) conducted an online survey of 1,378 teenagers who use the Internet. which showed that race had no significant difference in victimization or offending. Computer skills and time spent online were positively connected to both victimization and offenders in cyberbullying.

2.3.2 Cyber victimization

It is important to mention the victims of cyberbullying for many reasons. Such as victim reaction, harm, the intensity of cyberbullying, and many other reasons. These reasons provide an initial stage for taking action against cyberbullies and cyberbullying at an individual, group, community, organizational, and national level. Which can bring social harmony to society and individuals also.

A person who is affected physically, socially, or psychologically by a cyber offender or perpetrator is called a cyber victim, and this behavior is called cyber victimization behavior. Hinduja & Patchin (2008) defined cyber victimization as “willful and repeated harm inflicted through the medium of the electronic text” (p. 129). Furthermore, these two authors clearly define and specify the side effects of cyber victimization behavior. Cyberbullying action's victims frequently claim that they were too scared or humiliated to attend school. Furthermore, studies have found a relationship between cyberbullying and low self-esteem, family issues, academic issues, school violence, and deviant conduct (Hinduja & Patchin, 2007, 2011; Patchin & Hinduja, 2010).

Mason (as cited in Dalla Pozza et al., 2016) also defined the cyber victim as a deliberate action against at least one person through technology, in repeated ways that harm or threaten, which is called cyber victimization. Moreover, action against whom is taken is called the cyber victim, and the process of this action is called cyber victimization.

Smith & Brain (as cited by Patchin & Hinduja, 2015) it has taken several generations, as well as several heartbreaking instances of teenagers suffering from emotional, psychological, behavioral, and physical effects, for society to recognize that bullying is an issue worthy of our time, attention, and response. Even if arguments like these were common in the not-too-distant past, it is today extremely unusual to hear someone state that bullying is a "rite of passage," resilience training for the "hard knocks of life," or an otherwise acceptable element of teenage growth. Even though we have made significant progress in highlighting the possible effects of bullying (Patchin & Hinduja, 2015, p. 69).

According to Tiffany (2018), who studied secondary data collected over the previous four years through narrative research, tenth graders and females were considerably impacted by cyberbullying conduct. Previous cyberbullying, excessive internet use, lack of empathy, rage, narcissism, and authoritarian/permissive parenting are all risk factors/predictors of cyberbullying.

Furthermore, Durán & Martínez-Pecino (2015) mentioned that cyberbullying is an issue that has been extensively studied among teenagers. However, there have been few studies on young adults and their love relationships in the internet setting in Spain. A quantitative technique was used on a sample of 336 pupils. According to the findings, 57.2% of the sample admitted to being victimized by their spouse via cell phone and 27.4% over the Internet. Males were more likely than females to have been victims. 47.6% said they had bullied their partner over the phone, and 14% said it was over the Internet. Males were more likely than females to engage in this behavior. The results of this interaction show that young adult males who have been victimized through the use of mobile phones or the Internet are more likely than females to be perpetrators of this phenomenon.

2.3.2.1 Relations of age with Cyberbullying and Cyber victim

Cyberbullying can take place in every part of life. Cyberbullying took place at any human gathering through digital media. A study was conducted in lower and higher educational institutions, which revealed that digital bullying and victimization could take place at any level of education. Moreover, there is no age limit because you can either be cyberbullied or cyber victim at any stage of life (Minor et al., 2014).

Khawrin et al. (2021a) found that these digital habits have a beneficial and harmful impact on Afghan adult students. The research was carried out at private and governmental universities in Kabul. Furthermore, participation was entirely voluntary, and a random sampling design was employed. Aside from that, the sample consisted of seven hundred and fifty people, 50 of whom were removed due to exclusion conditions. It has 464 males and 236 females, ranging in age from 17 to 35. The findings reveal that the age of the participants had no bearing on cyberbullying or cyber victimization conduct. In addition, cyberbullying and cyber victimization have a significant influence on Afghan adult students' gender. Between digital bullying and cyber victims, there is a considerable difference between males and females. In other words, men are more likely to be both offenders and victims of cybercrime. Furthermore, cyberbullying and cyber victimization conduct have a high positive association, according to statistics. In a few words, Afghan adult students' age did not show a significant difference in cyberbullying behavior and cyber victim behavior among the participants. It meant that all age participants were almost equal in cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior.

Similarly, Safaria (2016) discovered a result regarding the age of the participants that in recent years, cyberbullying has been common among junior high school students in Yogyakarta, Indonesia, resulting in a large number of teenagers who have been victims of cyberbullying. Cyber victimization has been linked to poor mental health results. The research included 102 seventh-grade teenagers, with 72 (70.6%) boys and 30 (29.4%) girls participating. The majority of the students in this research (80 percent) said they had been victims of cybercrime every day. The findings reveal a link between cyber victimization and the amount of psychological distress among pupils.

On the other hand, Rafi (2019) discovered that an open-ended questionnaire and cyberbullying confession sheets were used to collect data from 329 male and female students of various age groups for this study on cyberbullying. According to the

findings, the chance of being a victim of cyberbullying decreases as one gets older. There was no relationship between gender and cyberbullying, however. The participants praised their parents and friends' support and expressed confidence in educational institutions and Pakistan's Federal Investigation Agency anti-cyberbullying efforts. That is to say, an increase in the age of the participants has a negative relationship with cyberbullying and cyber victimization. It means that when age is increasing, digital bullying and victim behavior are decreasing.

According to Sakellariou et al. (2012), the incidence and character of electronic forms of bullying were researched among 1,530 primary and secondary school-aged male students (6 to 12; 9-18 years, chronologically) in Sydney and Brisbane, Australia. Cyberbullying through the Internet was found to be the most frequent type of cyberbullying, with 11.5 percent of students reporting at least one incident during the school year. There was a substantial main impact, with junior high school adolescents (8 to 10 years old) being the most likely to be victimized. When it came to other students' cyberbullying, the Internet was once again the most popular tool, with 8.5 percent of students reporting surfing the internet. For all four types of cyberbullying studied, there was a major influence between year grade levels. The transmission of electronic photographs was the least commonly reported type of cyberbullying (4.8 percent) and the least frequently perpetrated form of cyberbullying (3.7 percent), both of which were lower than the only other research that collected similar data. These findings are examined in light of the small amount of cyberbullying research that has been conducted so far.

Furthermore, Espinoza (2015) revealed that daily cyber victimization experiences among Latino high school students (N = 118) are linked to their mental and physical well-being as well as school adjustment. The results of hierarchical linear modeling showed that daily cyber victimization experiences were linked to higher levels of anguish, anger, embarrassment, and somatic symptoms. The daily level relationships with sadness and anger were significant for Latinas but not for Latino adolescents, according to moderation analyses. Cyber victimization daily was also linked to increasing school attendance issues, such as coming late or skipping a class. Daily sentiments of distress, according to mediation models, account for the link between single events of cyber victimization and attendance issues. The findings

demonstrated that cyber victimization rises with teenage age and has an impact on class attendance and skipping.

However, Sengupta & Chaudhuri (2011) highlighted media reports in their research indicating that online misuse, particularly among teens, is increasing at an alarming rate, generating anxiety among parents of teenagers and spurring laws targeted at restricting internet use among minors. Strangers have been accused of using social networking platforms as a fertile ground for cyberbullying and abuse. Using the 2006 cycle of the Pew Internet™ American Life Survey, researchers identified important characteristics related to cyberbullying and online harassment among teens in the United States. The study found no link between cyberbullying and cyber victimization and social networking platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, and others. They did, however, show that cyberbullying and cyber victimization varied significantly depending on the gender of the subjects.

Similarly, Khawrin et al. (2022b) discovered that students of various age groups who use new virtual communication excessively and their peers lead to frequent and long-lasting physical, social, or psychological harm. The association and variance variations between age and education level with cyberbullying and cyber victimization are examined in this study. On the other hand, it investigates the relationship between internet browsing and cyberbullying and cyber victimization among Ahmedabad students. On a 0.001 level, the data demonstrated that every hour of internet browsing had a substantial impact on cyberbullying and cyber victimization (0.272, 0.328). However, there was no significant relationship or difference between age and education level and cyberbullying and cyber victimization among Ahmedabad city students in Gujarat.

On the other hand, Didden et al. (2009), on the other hand, discovered that adolescents with intellectual and developmental disabilities aged 12–19 years old completed a questionnaire comprising questions on bullying and victimisation via the internet and cellphones. Other questions focused on sociodemographic factors such as intelligence, age, gender, and diagnosis, as well as self-esteem and melancholy moods. At least once a week, 4–9% of kids reported bullying or being a victim of bullying. Cyberbullying was shown to have significant links to IQ, Internet usage frequency, self-

esteem, and melancholy moods. There were no correlations between cyberbullying and age or gender.

Anderson and Smith (as cited by Donegan, 2012) statistically proved with evidence from national vital statistics that people aged 15–24 years have the third-largest suicide rate because of cyberbullying. Moreover, High (as cited by Donegan, 2012) proved that perpetrators and victims of cyberbullying have been more likely to commit suicide or bully-cide because of cyberbullying behavior than those not affected by cyberbullying.

Shaban Rafi (2019) took data from students (N=329) of both genders in the age range of 13 to 20 years. The data was collected using an open-ended structured questionnaire. The research proved that by increasing the average age, cyberbullying, and victim behavior decrease. It means these two variables have a negative significant association. Furthermore, he testified that the gender of the participants does not show any significant difference in the role of cyberbullying and victim behavior.

Raskauskas & Stoltz (2007) collected data from 84 adolescents of both genders, comparing traditional bullying behavior with cyberbullying behavior. They found digital technology bullying and traditional bullying have the same and significant effect on participants' emotional and social behavior.

Sevcikova & Šmahel (2009) collected data from both sexes with an age range of 12–88 years, and the total sample size was 2215 respondents in the Czech Republic. They scientifically proved that adolescents and young adults aged 12–19 and 20–26 years have significantly more cyberbullying and victim behavior compared to other age groups. Moreover, they found that cyberbullying aggression decreased significantly with the increase in participants' age. It means age and cyberbullying have a significant negative correlation with old age ranging from 27 to 88 years.

Khawrin et al. (2022b) found that every hour of internet browsing had a significant impact on cyberbullying and cyber victimization at a $p = 0.001$ level (0.272, 0.328) among Ahmedabad city students. However, there was no significant association and difference between age and academic level and cyberbullying and cyber victimization levels of the participants.

Dalla Pozza et al. (2016) cited that traditional bullying has a negative correlation with age, but the relationship between cyberbullying and cyber victimization is different in societies. Moreover, age played a different role according to the status of a person being a cyber-bully or cyber-bullied. In other words, the adulthood of a person has a relationship with cyberbullying and cyber victimization, even if it continues in the workplace also.

A qualitative study in Pakistan included 329 participants, male (171) and female (158), ranging in age from 13 to 20 years. Language has significance and influences a person, causing him or her to become a victim of cyberbullying. He went on to say that becoming older has a detrimental impact on cyberbullying and cyber victimization. Furthermore, there was no significant difference in cyberbullying and cyber victimization based on the gender of the individuals (Shaban Rafi, 2019). However, Dalla Pozza et al. (2016) noted that different ages of people could become victims, but teenagers are significantly more vulnerable to cyberbullying. Moreover, it has been seen that the victims of cyberbullying are younger than the perpetrators of cyberbullying actions.

Furthermore, they discovered that there is very little evidence that proves that cyberbullying and cyber victimization have a relationship with the gender and ethnicity of the participants (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016). Sivakumar (2013) did a study on cyberbullying and cyber victimization with 600 participants ranging in age from 18 to 35. He discovered that students between the age group of 18–25 are more likely to engage in cyberbullying than students of other ages.

2.3.2.2 Gender Differences on cyberbullying and cyber victim behaviors

There is not a single view regarding gender relations and cyberbullying and cyber victimization. The first view is that females are more victimized in cyber activities than males (Chandra, 2018). The second view is that some authors discovered that males are more cyber-victimized and more cyberbullied than females (Huang & Chou, 2010; Topcu & Erdur-Baker, 2010). The third view is cited by Raskauskas & Stoltz (2007) and Wright & Li (2013), who have found that the sex of the participants does not have any relation to cyberbullying behavior. The fourth view argues that males significantly engage more in cyberbullying behavior than females (Topcu & Erdur-

Baker, 2012). As it is mentioned that there is no unanimity regarding gender and cyberbullying behavior. Dalla Pozza et al. (2016) discussed different views of researchers. They argued that females are significantly different in cyberbullying and victims in most of the European Union member states, but in Poland, there was no significant difference. There are various scientifically proven results, as Tokunaga (2010) argued that “research on gender differences in cyberbullying victimization is fraught with inconsistent findings” (p. 280). Heirman & Walrave (2012) discovered a clear link between teenagers' attitudes towards cyberbullying and their behavioral intention to perpetrate it (p. 614). When Karabacak et al. (2015) statistically compared the male and female cyberbullying and victim scores, it was discovered that the boys were more cyberbullies and more cyber victims compared to girls (p. 846).

Qualitative study findings of Nilan et al. (2015, p. 1) imply that young people engage in cyberbullying to gain social advantages over peers and to cope with social pressures and distress, but cultural norms in gender performance lead to females engaging in cyberbullying more than males. On the contrary, Didden et al. (2009) found that the age of the participants did not have any significant association with digital bullying and victimization.

In another qualitative research, Marr & Duell (2020) examine the impact of gender on college students' perceptions of the cyber victim. The findings demonstrated considerable disparities in judgments depending on gender, with males being completely different in their conduct as cyber bullies, cyber victims, and participants (p. 1).

However, P. K. Smith et al. (2019) statistically proved that females are more likely to be victims of cyberbullying activities than males. Barlett & Coyne (2014, p. 474) revealed that males were marginally more likely to cyberbully than females. Additionally, age mitigated the overall impact. Females were more likely than boys to report cyberbullying throughout early to mid-adolescence, but males reported greater levels of cyberbullying during later adolescence. There are significant gender inequalities in cyberbullying and cyber harassment, and pornography mostly targets women (P. K. Smith et al., 2014, p. 1). According to research conducted between 2007 and 2010, females are more likely to be victims of cyberbullying (Chandra, 2018).

However, male students, according to Erdur-Baker, were more likely to be bullies and victims in both physical and online contexts than female students (Chandra, 2018).

Khawrin et al. (2021a) found that Afghan students' gender showed a significant difference in cyberbullying behavior and cyber victim behavior among the participants. In addition, they added that male participants became more cyberbully and cyber victimized compared to female participants. However, a study in the United States with a sample of 267 students at a university found that adult gender did not have a significant difference in the prevalence of digital bullying and digital victimization among the participants (Tennant et al., 2015). Safaria (2016) discovered that gender did not have any significant effect on cyber victimization. It means that males and females are almost equal in cyber victim behavior. However, gender had a significant effect on cyberbullying behavior. It meant that males engaged in more cyberbullying behavior compared to females. Similarly, Kim et al. (2019) discovered that female adolescents significantly became more cyber victims compared to male participants. In addition, the males engaged in more cyberbullying behavior than the female participants did. According to the findings of Marcum et al. (2014, p. 538), both males and females with low self-control were more likely to engage in cyberbullying by posting unpleasant remarks or photographs on Facebook. Second, if they had been cyberbullied, both sexes were more likely to engage in cyberbullying via Facebook. Another study showed that male and female participants participated in cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior, and they used Facebook for these activities (Marcum et al., 2014).

Sorrentino et al. (2019) showed academic evidence that Bulgaria, Hungary, and Spain's males had more significant digital bullying behavior compared to females. However, gender was not significant depending on the digital victimization of the participants. Even so, girls were more digitally victimized. Campfield (2008) statistically proved in his thesis that 69 percent of all participants, including males and females, supported cyberbullying and/or victimization, with females accounting for a significantly larger number.

Some authors found differently, such as Felix & McMahon (as cited by Sivakumar, 2013, p. 34), that both sexes have the same ability to engage in bullying behavior. Male bullies are more likely to target both male and female targets, but female bullies are more likely to target solely other females. Furthermore, Guan et al. (2016)

discovered a few different results and argued that both sexes have the same level of digital ragging behavior; bullies and victims. In addition, the older age group participants were more prone to cyberbullying and victim behavior.

Yiğit et al. (2018) identified cyberbullying behavior among middle school kids (n = 223) who are at high risk of being involved in cyberbullying. According to the findings, perceived family support diminishes as kids' grades and frequency of Internet use rise, whereas cyberbullying activities rise, independent of gender. Students' cyberbullying levels and their reported levels of family support have also been found to have a modest and unfavorable association.

Donegan (2012) cited research conducted by the Cyberbullying Research Center, which consisted of 468 student participants, showing that there is a significant emotional difference among the genders of cyberbullying. Furthermore, they testify that females are more emotionally frustrated (39.6%), angry (36%), and sad (25.2%) than males are (27.5%, 24.3%, and 17.9%), respectively.

Muhammad Shaban Rafi (2019) revealed that age and cyberbullying have a negative relationship. In other words, as you increase your age, cyberbullying decreases, but cyberbullying and gender do not have any relationship. Black (2014) conducted a study of 77 participants of both sexes; participants were significantly involved in cyberbullying behavior. In addition, women were significantly more vulnerable to cybercrime. According to Arcaç et al. (as suggested by Duman & Bridge, 2020, p. 468), who studied 269 Turkish middle and high school adolescents aged 12 to 19, 13.4% of boys and 10.4% of girls are victims of cyberbullying behavior. Dalla Pozza et al. (2016) reported that girls were significantly more cyber victims than boys in most of the European Union member states, such as Belgium, Cyprus, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, and Luxembourg, but from the Czech Republic reported vice versa.

Qualitative research conducted in Pakistan had 329 participants, male (171), and female (158), with an age range of 13–20 years. The language gives meaning and influences the person, through which s/he becomes a victim of cyberbullying behavior. He included that increasing age has a negative association with cyberbullying and cyber victimization. In addition, the gender of the participants did not have any significant difference between cyber bullying and cyber victimization (Shaban Rafi, 2019). Patchin

& Hinduja (2008) conducted an online survey of 1,378 teenagers who use the Internet. Which showed that gender were not related to victimization or offending. Computer skills and time spent online were positively connected to both victimization and offender-ship in cyberbullying.

A study of 122 participants found that males were marginally more likely than females to cyberbully, with age moderating. Females, on the other hand, were more likely than males to report cyberbullying during early to mid-adolescence, whereas males reported higher levels of cyberbullying throughout later adolescence. In addition, female individuals engaged in more indirect cyberbullying acts (C. Barlett & Coyne, 2014).

Tiffany (2018) cited a study of Italian participants that showed the most popular social networking sites are Facebook, YouTube, and Google. Different psychological problems, for example, anti-social behavior, suicidal ideation, lack of empathy, anger, narcissistic behavior, authoritarian parenting, educational problems, internet addiction, and emotional imbalance could take place due to digital bullying and victim behavior. Furthermore, the researcher added that the prevalence of cyberbullying happens at different times, such as among school-age, college-age, and university-age students who face these problems. On the other hand, gender also differs. In which girls are victimized more than boys (Tiffany, 2018). Another scholar, Tiffany's (2018) research on Spanish schoolchildren (N = 1278), statistically proved that males have been the bullies and females have been the victims.

Wright et al. (2015) found that India is the 3rd country around the globe for surfing the internet. Furthermore, the cyberbullying and victim behavior of adolescents in India is still lower than in China and Japan. Similarly, cyberbullying behavior is ambiguous in Indian individualistic and collectivistic cultures and needs more attention for academic contribution.

2.3.2.3 Cyberbullying and Cyber victimization in India

Examining diversity based on gender, caste, occupation, etc. may be done in many different ways using the lens of cultural conflict. The right system, one that advances humankind's ability to flourish and prosper, must be identified. Males and females were equally present (42.8 percent and 57.2 percent, respectively).

Additionally, information was acquired between 2019 and 2021 using a sample and a random sampling approach. There were variety of castes, including Open/General (53.9%), Scheduled Tribe (9.5%), Scheduled Extremely Backward Caste (20.7%), Scheduled Caste (8.5%), Other Backward Caste (5.6%), and Economically Weaker Section (1.9%). In addition to evaluating the mean score difference between genders, this study also analyzed the variation across castes. Their study demonstrated that there was no discernible difference between caste groupings, just as there was no discernible difference between the genders of Ahmedabad city students (Khawrin et al., 2022a).

2.3.2.4 Cyberbullying and Cyber victimization in Afghanistan

Khawrin et al. (2021a) discovered that cyberbullying and cyber victimization had a significant difference with respect to the gender of the Afghan participants. However, it did not show any significant relationship with the age of the participants.

2.3.2.5 Relationship between cyberbullying and cyber victimization

Cyberbullying and cyber victimization have a significant positive indirect relationship. Furthermore, these have a significant direct relationship with anger (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016). Cyberbullying and cyber victimization are widespread across different demographics such as age, gender, ethnicity, and caste. Different authors test the relationship between the cyberbullies and the cyber victim; however, they do not have one view. As their actions show that they knew each other before, it is argued that this is peer cyberbullying behavior.

Barón et al. (2018) discovered that cyberbullying is becoming a more common problem among teenagers, and it is causing widespread societal concern. The major goal of this study, which used a cross-sectional and quantitative technique, was to look at the disparities between adolescent who perpetrated and were victimized by cyberbullying, as well as their parental communication and emotions of connection with peers. A total of 849 adolescents aged 12 to 18 years old ($M = 14.5$; $SD = 1.62$) were included in the study (51.7 percent males and 48.3 percent girls). According to the findings of the analysis of variance, teenagers who are offenders or victims of cyberbullying have less open and avoidant contact with their parents than adolescents who are not participating in cyberbullying. Furthermore, victims of cyberbullying had

a weaker sense of connection with their classmates, but cyberbullies had no difference in this regard. These new findings shed light on the critical role of family and peers in the prevention and eradication of cyberbullying, which is on the rise. They also found that cyberbullying perpetration was associated with cyberbullying victimization and avoidant communication with the mother, with a $p < 0.01$ correlation. There was also a strong positive association between cyberbullying and avoidant communication with the father ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, cyberbullying was shown to be inversely connected with open communication with both the mother and father at a $p < 0.01$ level.

C. P. Barlett et al. (2019) studied the Barlett Gentile Cyberbullying Model (BGCM), which was improved by including participant age, time spent online, and views of national technology availability. One hundred and sixty-four people in the United States answered surveys about cyberbullying practices, attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions. The postulates of the BGCM's initial derivation were supported by path modeling findings. Additional data revealed that cyberbullying attitudes and perpetration were both negatively connected with views of country's technology availability and favorably correlated with time online, potentially expanding the model. Similarly, Erdur-Baker (2010) discovered that cyber-victimization and cyberbullying were substantially associated, according to correlation coefficients.

Ozgur (2015) examined the levels of cyberbullying, cyber victimization, and cyberbullying sensitivity among distance education students concerning a number of factors. During the autumn semester of the 2012-2013 academic year, 297 distance education students studying at a university in the Marmara area formed the study group. Distance education students scored low on cyberbullying and mid-level on cyber victimization, indicating that they have a strong sensitivity to cyberbullying and that there is a statistically significant divergence between cyberbullying and cyber victimization. It has also been discovered that when Internet usage rises, cyberbullying and cyber victimization rise in tandem, and that there is a link between cyberbullying and cyber victimization. Furthermore, it has been discovered that, in comparison to female students, male students engage in greater levels of cyberbullying and are more frequently cyber victimized.

Beran et al. (2015) reported cross-sectional data from a nationwide household panel of families from all provinces in Canada. A total of 1,001 youngsters between the ages of 10 and 17 were enrolled in the study. In all, 13.99 percent of youngsters said they had been cyberbullied at least once in the previous month, with gender differences.

Cyberbullied children were more likely to have bad results in all eight categories studied. The great majority of those who were cyberbullied (94.28 percent) were also victims of other forms of bullying, and more than a third (33.57 percent) perpetrated other forms of bullying. One in every seven Canadian children aged 10 to 17 is a cyber-victim, and one in every thirteen children is a cyber-perpetrator.

2.3.2.6 International level cyberbullying behavior

Article 19 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) applies to those who are under 18 years of age and mentions that children have to be safe from all forms of violence, physical or mental (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016). This violence could be in digital space, a virtual world, or the physical world. It is the right of the child to be protected. Similarly, on April 22, 2014, the United Nations General Assembly issued a resolution to protect the children of all member states. Moreover, available data from European Union member states showed that cyberbullying significantly affects adult life as well. On the other hand, in Sweden, it is significantly proven that higher usage of the internet leads to a higher risk of cyberbullying behavior (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016).

2.3.2.7 Bystanders of cyberbullying behavior

Bystanders are the third-party victims of cyberbullying. In other words, they are observers or witnesses of cyberbullying behaviors. Through empathy (Tiffany, 2018), bystanders could reduce cyberbullying behavior. Bystanders, according to Holfeld (2014), have a significant role in the maintenance or reduction of bullying behavior. Because of the internet world's theoretically infinite audience, bystanders may play a particularly critical role in cyberbullying. 1105 middle school kids were randomly assigned to one of three experimental situations that varied the victim's reaction (passive, active, reactive). In every case, the consequence was bad. Passive answers, in particular for male spectators, generated larger feelings of control, attributions of responsibility, and blame than active or reactive ones. Bystanders may be less willing to help victims of cyberbullying who respond passively to their situation. The findings have significance for determining what characteristics might boost or reduce bystander support in real-world cyberbullying scenarios.

Furthermore, Li (2006) polled 264 high school pupils. The researcher claimed that cyberbullying is the abuse of electronic communication technologies. Almost half of adolescents have been bullied, and a quarter have been cyberbullied. The majority

of bullied, victimized, or bystander students did not report it. Furthermore, males were more likely than females to be bullies and cyberbullies. A bystander of cyberbullying behavior is a person who does not have a direct relationship with cyber activity. In other words, a bystander is a third party who has a passive role in cyberbullying behavior. Such as seeing, listening, and having an influence on cyberbullying behavior. Most of the European Union member states do not have a significant difference between bystander behavior and cyberbullying behavior (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016).

Based on the above arguments, it is inferred that these all-social phenomena have links with one another, especially in this study, which depicts the link between ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victim behavior. The below-given diagram shows the relationship between ethnocentrism, cyberbullying behavior, and cyber victim behavior.

Figure 4 Correlational Model: The relationship of Ethnocentrism with cyberbullying and victim behavior

Correlational Model

The relation of Ethnocentrism with cyberbullying and victim behavior

Note: The above model illustrate that there is correlations among ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization behavior.

2.4 Contesting of Social Dominance and Realistic Group conflict theories

An alternative way of understanding the model is in (Figure 4) which illustrates the correlation among the variables. This is supported by different theories via Social dominance theory and the Realistic group theory, and the association of other variables. The natural attributes such as age, gender, and classification of the society via different attributes and factors such as race, tribe, class, religious group, caste, nationality, clan, lineage, are the potential spot for benefiting and harming (Pratto & Stewart, 2011; Tanner & Jackson, 2011). On the other hand, groups engage in' negative behaviors via racism, social dominance, bias, prejudice, political and religious groups, castes and ethnicities, discrimination, in-group favoritism, intra-group conflicts, and many other traits that lead to negative behavior (Gould, 1999; Münster, 2005). These theories simultaneously associate ethnocentrism behavior with cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior in one intersection. Through this contesting point increase, any one variable could increase other variables also. Even though, decreasing any one variable decreases other variables also.

Chapter III

Research Methodology

3

3.0 Introduction

3.1 Statement of the Problem

3.2 Objectives of the Study

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3.0 Introduction

The contextual framework was done according to the well-defined method. In addition, rules of the research methodology were applied. This chapter included the below topics. For instance, objectives of the study, Hypotheses of the research, population, samples, procedure, participants, research type, research tools, and variables.

3.1 Statement of the Problem

The concept of ethnocentrism means prioritizing one's own culture over others, which shows bias against the minor cultural group. Moreover, the virtual social disharmony, in other words, social media, which can lead to hate and prejudice against the out-group, is going to be discussed in this cross-cultural research.

Secondly, diagnosing disharmony behavior, specifically cyberbullying and its victimization against out-groups, is also important. which can cause hate crimes and biases regarding any minority, culture, ethnicity, caste, or any other similar issue. Furthermore, it is one of the responsibilities of academicians to eradicate the blind spot, which is the root of social problems. Every day in Afghanistan and India, social disharmony on virtual bases is increasing. One of the root causes of this issue is ethnocentrism. It is used for different purposes of in-group and out-group comparison on a different basis. Despite the fact that cyberbullying tends to affect important percentage of teenage Internet users, it has been linked to detrimental consequences such as despair and suicidal ideation (Ševčíkova et al., 2012).

Thirdly, public policymakers need this kind of widespread research in which the diagnosis of social disharmony is articulated. It would be easy for them to make long-lasting problem-solving rules and regulations for society: peace, fraternity, freedom; and this would bring peace and prosperity to society and could lead society to social justice.

Fourthly, Indians and Europeans witness discrimination because of ethnocentrism. For instance, when there is a competition between the host culture and the guest culture, it breaks the social norms of cooperation. It has been seen in times of

economic crisis. In these conditions, the host culture shows discrimination toward the outgroup (Gautam, 2013). In addition, Afghan society also has ethnocentrism and cultural favoritism. Additionally, this new era of virtual connectivity and enhanced technology shows cyberbullying against one another. Many factors have an inflectional relationship, such as gender, age, ethnicity, education, and internet surfing time. For instance, Allen & Barter (2016) also conducted ethnocentrism and religious involvement studies in Indonesia. It also proved that ethnocentrism could be the starting point of social problems. They observed that a respondent's self-reported degree of religious participation had a high relationship with their desire for co-ethnic leadership. Indonesia's growing Islamic practice might signal an increase in ethnocentrism, jeopardizing the country's reputation for tolerance.

Lastly, it appears there is no vivid research on the mediating role of ethnocentric behavior toward cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior. This study mainly diagnoses these issues and finds the intensity of cyberbullying and victim behaviors in both regions (Kabul and Ahmedabad). Over and above that, it is going to compare Afghan and Indian cultures also. Discussing the Afghan and Indian social disharmony, which is rooted in ethnocentrism. This ethnocentrism influences cyberbullying and cyber victimization. Furthermore, there is very little investigation in this field.

Similarly, in Malaysia, which is likewise a multicultural country with three primary ethnic groups: Malay, Chinese, and Indians, a study on Social Media Contribution to Ethnocentrism were undertaken. Social media is identified as playing a role in the promotion of ethnocentrism. As a result, the purpose of this research was to determine the degree of public exposure to social media, as well as the level of ethnocentrism in Indian and Afghan cultures, as well as the link between public exposure to social media and ethnocentrism (Ridzuan et al., 2012, p. 517). Hence, scrutinizing and comparing Indian and Afghan ethnocentric behavior via digital behavior is the current dilemma for academicians, researchers, and decision-making authorities. Studying this topic as a scholar is an important issue for both regions and cultures.

3.2 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the present study were as follows-

1. To assess the level of ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization among adults.
2. To compare the adults of countries (India and Afghanistan) on their measure of-
 - ✓ Ethnocentrism
 - ✓ Cyberbullying
 - ✓ Cyber Victimization
3. To study the gender difference in their measures of-
 - ✓ Ethnocentrism
 - ✓ Cyberbullying
 - ✓ Cyber Victimization
4. To compare the adults of countries (India and Afghanistan) concerning their gender in their measure of-
 - ✓ Ethnocentrism
 - ✓ Cyberbullying
 - ✓ Cyber Victimization
5. To analyze the predictive role of ethnocentrism in cyberbullying and cyber victimization of Indian adults.
6. To analyze the predictive role of ethnocentrism in cyberbullying and cyber victimization of Afghan adults.

3.3 Hypotheses of the Study

Hypotheses framed for the present study are-

1. There will be a significant difference in the level of Ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying, and Cyber victimization among adults.

2. Adults belonging to India and Afghanistan will be significantly different in their measure of-
 - ✓ Ethnocentrism
 - ✓ Cyberbullying
 - ✓ Cyber victimization

3. Gender will be significantly different in its measures of-
 - ✓ Ethnocentrism
 - ✓ Cyberbullying
 - ✓ Cyber victimization

4. There will be a significant differences between the adults belonging to India and Afghanistan concerning their gender in their measures of
 - ✓ Ethnocentrism
 - ✓ Cyberbullying
 - ✓ Cyber victimization

5. There will be a significant predictive role of ethnocentrism in cyberbullying and cyber victimization of Indian adults.

6. There will be a significant predictive role of ethnocentrism in cyberbullying and cyber victimization of Afghan adults.

3.4 Methodology

In general, the term methodology refers to how a researcher does research (Jonker & Pennink, 2010). A systematic approach to solving an issue is known as a research methodology. It is a science that studies how research should be conducted. Research techniques are essentially the process by which researchers go about their business of describing, understanding, and predicting occurrences. It can also be described as the study of strategies for gaining information. Its goal is to provide a research work plan (Valunaite Oleskeviciene & Sliogeriene, 2020).

Techniques, strategies, and algorithms utilized in research are known as research methods. The word "research techniques" refers to all of the procedures utilized by a researcher throughout a research investigation. They are mostly planned, scientific, and value-agnostic. Theoretical techniques, experimental research, numerical systems, statistical methodologies, and so on are among them. We may use research techniques to collect samples and data, and come up with a solution to an issue. Scientific research procedures, in particular, need explanations based on gathered data, measurements, and observations, rather than only on reasoning. They only accept explanations that can be validated by experimentation (Valunaite Oleskeviciene & Sliogeriene, 2020).

The method of this study was an inductive approach for making a new theory. Whether ethnocentrism has any kind of relationship with cyberbullying and cyberbullied behavior. In other words, taking the result from a specific sample and making it toward the generalization of the result which gives us the new theory is called the inductive method (Kothari, 2004). Therefore, for conducting this study the below topic was covered instance Methodology, procedure, research type, research design, scales and tests, statistical analysis, variables, and population. Every topic has been elaborated on below.

3.4.1 Population, Sampling method and Sample size

The research population is the defined universe from which data is going to be collected. The study population means the group from which data and information is going to be collected which is needed for research to answer research questions or objectives (Kumar, 2011). A sample is the exact population from which data or information is collected. In quantitative research, a sample is chosen that is impartial and representative of the population. A number of issues may impact the selection of a sample in qualitative research (Kumar, 2011).

Then a total sample taken comprised of one thousand and five hundred adults. Random sampling technique was used to conduct the data. The sample was constituted of equal participants from two different countries, which were Afghanistan and India. Both groups of the sample were comprised of an equal number of male and female participants. The age factor was considered in the range of 17 to 30 years for the sample.

The sample distribution was depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample Distribution of the Study

The population of the subjects was infinite; therefore, a sample of one thousand five hundred and fifty 1550 samples were decided, and 50 samples of data were discarded. Therefore, the remaining sample was one thousand five hundred students. Data was conducted with a random sample method. It is worth mentioning that those who were using the internet participated in this study. Especially the students of Ahmedabad city, Gujarat state. In addition, Kabul City, Kabul Province students participated in this study. After the inclusion criteria were applied, the remaining sample consisted of 1416 participants from both regions; for more details, see table 2.

3.4.2 Variables

Variables for the present investigation are described as follows.

3.4.2.1 Independent Variables

1. Gender

1.1 Male

1.2 Female

2. Country

2.1 Afghanistan (Kabul Province, Kabul city)

2.2 India (Gujarat State, Ahmedabad)

3. Ethnocentrism
4. Internet surfing time
5. Ethnicity / Caste
 - 5.1 Indian caste type
 - 5.2 Afghan ethnicity type
6. Social media names that are used by the participants
7. Age
8. Education level

3. 4.2.2 Dependent Variables

1. Ethnocentrism
2. Cyberbullying
3. Cyber victimization

3. 4.2.3 Control Variables

1. Ages from seventeen up to thirty years were included and others were excluded.
2. Citizens of India (Ahmedabad, Gujarat) and Afghanistan (province of Kabul, Kabul city) were included, and vice versa in other locations.
3. Self-retrieving the question was taken into account, and another person's view was not allowed to count.
4. Facilitating if someone does not understand the meaning of a statement.
5. Open environment and no compulsion.
6. Voluntarily participated, and at any time, participants could leave the questionnaire.

3. 4.2.4 Inclusion Criteria of sample

1. Those participants whose ages ranged from 17 to 30 years have been included.
2. Males and females who were living in Kabul, Afghanistan and Ahmedabad, India participated.
3. Participation was voluntary in an open area. Therefore, after applying the conditions, there were 1416 participants sample was included.

3.4.2.5 Exclusion Criteria of sample

1. Participants, whose age was less than 17 years, or more than 30 years, were excluded.
2. Those who were not living in Ahmedabad and Kabul city were also excluded.
3. Those who were not using the internet were also excluded. Therefore, 84 samples were excluded because of the exclusion criteria conditions.

3.4.3 Research type

Cross-culture research is scientific research and this was carried out to compare and show systematically the differences and similarities between at least two cultures around the globe at a same time (Olatundun, 2009). Moreover, cross-culture research gives an overall generalization overview of multiple societies' cultures (Ember & Ember, 1998). Besides that, Bizumic & Sheppard (2021) noted that specific culture with bounded time is a cross-culture research. Hence, cross-cultural research was applied, and it revealed the current scenario's generalizable result. Which is described in the results chapter.

3.4.4 Research Design

The research design was descriptive and the subtype of it was cross-sectional design because the data was taken simultaneously as a snapshot at a particular time and date which elaborates the problems in a population. Cross-sectional studies was applied because it was appropriate and suitable for the current study. Cross-sectional study means one-time or status studies are often known as cross-sectional studies. This approach is best suited to studies that use a cross-section of the population to determine the prevalence of a phenomenon, situation, problem, attitude, or issue. They help get a general 'picture' of the situation during the time of the research. They are made to investigate a phenomenon by taking a cross-section of it all at once. In terms of both the research population and the period under consideration, such studies are cross-sectional (Kumar, 2011).

To attain all the objectives, the present study dealt with the following design-

- ✓ 2×2 Factorial Design: To study the main effects of country and gender as well as the effect of interaction among them on ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization, 2×2 factorial design was used.

- ✓ Within-group Design: To analyze the ethnicity and age as predictors of cyberbullying and cyber victimization for both countries in terms of their gender within-group design, was used which is depicted below.

Data has been analyzed under descriptive and inferential analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24. First, the Pearson correlation test was conducted to evaluate the relationship between variables, and secondly, an Independent Sample t-test was conducted to understand gender differences. Thirdly, a two-way ANOVA was conducted to scrutinize the gender and country differences via different variables. Fourthly, a linear regression test was applied to predict ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization behavior.

3.5 Research Tools

The primary data for the research was collected through the use of three methods: a demographic sheet, an informed consent form, and standardized questionnaires. A demographic sheet is a form that asks for information about the demographics of the participants in the study, such as their age, gender, education level, and other characteristics. An informed consent form is a document that explains the purpose of the study and the procedures that will be used, and it asks the participants to give their permission to participate.

Standardized questionnaires are sets of questions that are structured in a specific way and are used to gather data from a large number of people. The questions are typically multiple choice and short answer and are designed to be easy to understand and answer. Standardized questionnaires is one of the most extensively used data-gathering methods in assessment research. The questions used to obtain the final data were closed-ended questionnaires. Questionnaires aided in the collection of data on attitudes, views, actions, facts, and other data (Chowdhury, 2014). The reliability of the questionnaire was tested by utilizing a pilot test and in the final phase as well. Random mistakes in measuring are referred to as reliability. The accuracy or precision of the measurement device is referred to as reliability (Chowdhury, 2014). The standardized scales that were used in this research are as below.

3.5.1 Ethnocentrism scale

An adapted valid tool Generalized Ethnocentrism Scale developed by Neuliep, J. W., and McCroskey (2013) was used to tap cultural differences. The tool consisted 22 items which were administered to the respondents. However on scoring, 9 items were eliminated for balancing the positive and negative items and for increasing reliability. In more specific, items three, six, twelve, fifteen, sixteen, seventeen, and nineteen were dropped for balancing purposes; and items seven and four were dropped for the purpose of increasing reliability. Items nine had reversed score for more details (Appendix A) could be visited. Therefore, a total of 13 items were retained for the scoring purposes with a five-point Likert scale. The remaining items were 13 and their reliability was 0.769. It is interpreted that the 13-item score ranged from 13 to 65. It means a maximum of 65 scores showed the most ethnocentric behavior, and 13 scores showed almost zero ethnocentric behavior. Furthermore, a 39 score means participants are neutral on ethnocentric behavior. Additionally, the norms and validation of the scale were reviewed. It had content validity and its convergent validity was 0.522 and reliability was 0.77, the skewness and kurtosis values were close to 0, then the distribution is approximately normal. So if the skewness is significantly positive or negative and/or the kurtosis is significantly different from 3, then the distribution is not normal, and the data of this study was normally distributed, it means that it follows a specific pattern when it is plotted on a graph. The graph had a bell-shaped curve, with most of the data points falling in the middle and fewer data points on either end, which allowed the researcher to apply the parametric statistics.

3.5.2 Revised Cyberbullying inventory (RCBI)

An adopted valid tool consisted of 28 items with a four-point Likert scale that was developed by Topcu & Erdur-Baker (2010). This inventory had two sub scales. The tool had 14 items for measuring cyberbullying that is called “Bully scale”, and 14 items for measuring the cyber victimization behavior of the participants that is called “Victim scale”.

Furthermore, the respondents are asked to recall their last twelve months of cyberbullying and victim behaviors. These behaviors include aggressive email, mobile

phone calls, social networking, and general computer usage. On this scale, the participant is asked about a specific type of cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior. For instance, “stealing of personal information from the computer (like files, email, addresses, pictures, IM messages, or Facebook info)”.

The score range of this inventory form is zero to 42 for each column. A high score of 42 indicated the highest level of cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior. A zero score indicated the least level of cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior. In other words, the higher scores predict more frequent cyberbullying and similarly for cyber victimization scale for extra information visit (Appendix C). On the other hand, the reliability with Cronbach coefficients of this scale is 0.92, for the bullying scale and 0.80 for the victim scale. The constructed validity of this scale shows fourteen specific instances of cyber-criminal behavior (Topcu & Erdur-Baker, 2010).

The Cronbach Alpha was computed for the study. Overall, the reliability of the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory (RCBI) was 0.937. Additionally, the norms and validation of the scale were reviewed. Reliability for sub-dimensions was also computed. Bully Scale’s Cronbach Alpha was 0.88 and convergent validity 0.654, and for Victim Scale’s Cronbach Alpha was 0.93, and validity 0.735. Furthermore, the data was normally distributed.

3.5.3 Revised Cyberbullying inventory II (RCBI-II)

This standardized valid inventory RCBI-II was developed by Topcu & Erdur-Baker (2018), and this inventory has ten items with two scoring columns. In this inventory, each item is scored twice. Once for the “I did it” column, or cyberbullying, and the second for the “It happened to me” column, or cyber victimization. Moreover, this inventory is self-reported with a four-point Likert scale, which is a rating from never to more than three times. "On the internet..." has been written at the top of the items. The score range of these inventory forms is 10 to 40 for each column. Furthermore, ten means zero in the frequency of cyberbullying and cyber victimization, whereas more than ten means the reputation of cyber-offensive behavior exists. To be more precise, this scale has open cyber statements and four dimensions of scoring. The first dimension is cyberbullied, the second is cyber victim, the third is cyber bullies and cyber victims, and the last dimension is not involved in any cyber bullying or cyber

victim behavior or that person who has a ten in the column "it happened to me" and a ten in the column "I did it." The internal reliability of consistency, or in other words, the Cronbach alpha coefficient, is 0.80 for the cyber victimization part and reliability 0.79 for the cyberbullying portion. Pearson correlation coefficient or relationship between cyberbullying and cyber victimization is $r=.54$, $p<.001$. It is large and positive. This inventory can be applied to different age ranges, such as from children to college-aged students, and this inventory does not have any specific application or technological name (Topcua & Erdur-Bakerb, 2018).

The data was normally distributed and the overall reliability of the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory-II (RCB-II) was examined for the study, and it was 0.902 which means the reliability is good for the research. In addition, the generalization of the results of this study is valid up to 90.2% for computing the cyberbullying and cyber victimization of RCBI-II. Additionally, the norms and validation of the scale were reviewed. Cronbach Alpha for sub-dimensions was also computed. The Cronbach Alpha for the Cyber Bullying dimension was 0.833 and convergent validity 0.644, and for the Cyber Victim dimension was 0.868 and convergent validity 0.684, which means very good for assessing the cyber bullying and victim behavior respectively for visiting the scale please see (Appendix B).

3.5.4 Pilot Test phase

The study's pilot phase was carried out in Ahmedabad, Gujarat. The pilot phase had 61 individuals in all. The participants were chosen at random during their students' class recess. The selection process was convenience-based and took into account factors like age, gender, internet use, and others. The reliability, or Cronbach's alpha, of ethnocentrism was 0.737, which had 15 items. The Cronbach Alpha of cyberbullying behavior in the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory (RCBI) with 14 items was 0.802, and the Cronbach Alpha of cyber victim behavior in the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory (RCBI) with 14 items was 0.827. The Cronbach Alpha of cyberbullying behavior in the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory II (RCBI-II) with 10 items was 0.729, and the Cronbach Alpha of cyber victim behavior in the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory II (RCBI-II) with 10 items was 0.783. Overall, the reliability of all tests was good.

Similarly, the translated and back-translated versions of the research tools were tested in Afghanistan on 101 pilot samples. The result of the Cronbach Alpha for the

ethnocentrism scale was 0.702, which had 15 items. The Cronbach Alpha of cyberbullying behavior in the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory (RCBI) with 14 items was 0.78, and the Cronbach Alpha of cyber victim behavior in the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory (RCBI) with 14 items was 0.77. The Cronbach Alpha of cyberbullying behavior in the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory II (RCBI-II) with 10 items was 0.701, and the Cronbach Alpha of cyber victim behavior in the Revised Cyberbullying Inventory II (RCBI-II) with 10 items was 0.73. Overall, the reliability of all tests was good.

3.6 Data collection and Procedure

All academic research principles were followed, including maintaining confidentiality, establishing reports, and the informed permission form was conducted. This quantitative research's primary data was self-reported by the participants of the study. Each participant could leave the questionnaire at any time. In addition, it was requested from each subject to take participation voluntarily.

For collecting data in Ahmedabad city universities an official permission letter was granted for data collection that was taken from the Psychology Department, at Gujarat University. Similarly, one official letter was taken from the Department and Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR) Ahmedabad. Through this, the researcher got a permission letter from the Ministry of Higher Education (MoHE) of Afghanistan for data collection in Kabul from different public and private universities. After that, MoHE officially grants me permission and authorization to conduct the study. Then a copy of the authorization letter was submitted to each university vice-chancellor's office for further support and legal and ethical issues.

Furthermore, the subject did not need to write his/her name. Participants' signatures were kept confidential. All students were guided for scoring the questionnaire. Besides that, data was taken during the break time. Moreover, this data was conducted through a simple random sampling design. For instance, Yes and NO cards were placed and the participants had the choice to select one. Meanwhile, the participant was taping one of the cards on the backside. If s/he tapped "YES" the questionnaire was filled by that participant, and if it was taped "NO" vice versa.

3.6.1 Sample selection of the Participants

Participants voluntarily joined the research and responded anonymously. Furthermore, every questionnaire had a serial number. All students were asked to take part in the survey, and they could leave the questionnaire at any time. It was requested by all participants to take part in the research. Students participated voluntarily. Data were collected from November 2019 up to December 2021, the academic year. They had a maximum of 30 minutes to fill up the questionnaire. Furthermore, full instruction was given to the participants, both written and verbal. Moreover, each participant had the choice to leave the questionnaire at any time if they wanted to leave. In other words, they could leave the questionnaire at any time. All the data was collected in their free time at different places such as classrooms and open areas of each institution. It had one thousand and five hundred sample sizes, which consisted of both genders. After applying the inclusion area the remaining sample was 772 males and 644 females. Moreover, demographic details were also collected, such as age, internet surfing per day, social media usage, and becoming the perpetrator, victim, or bystander of cyberbullying in the last twelve months.

3.6.1.1 Participants of India

Students of Gujarat University, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, participated voluntarily from November 2019 to December 2021. After signing the consent form, each of the participants was guided to answer the questions, and every participant was told that they could leave at any time without any excuse. An official permission letter was also delivered to different departments and schools of universities in Ahmedabad, such as School of Law, Department of Philosophy, Department of Psychology, Department of Chemistry, Department of Biotechnology and Forensic Science, Department of Animation, School of Commerce, KS school of Business Management, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, Department of Computer Science, Department of Environment Science, Department of Physics Electronics and space science, ITMS and Mobile Application, 12th Grade, School of Social Science, Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, HK center for Professional Training, BK School of Business Management, J.G College, Somlalit College, Department of Physical Education, Department of Geography and Earth Science, Department of botany Bioinformatics and Climate Change, School of Science, Department of Economics,

Department of Statistics, Twenty four participants have not mentioned their departments which was coded as Missing department. After applying the condition of exclusion sample the remaining sample was 707 participants which consist of 305 males and 402 females' participants for more details visit (Table 3).

3.6.1.2 Participants of Afghanistan

Half of this portion of this research was conducted in Kabul province in 2020 by both public and private universities such as from Jahan University, Avicenna University, Katam-al-Nabieen University, Bayan University, Karwan University, Dunya University, Bakhtar University, Kateb University, Rabia-Balkhi University, Dawat University, Kabul University of Medical Sciences "Abu Ali Ibn Sina", Kabul University, Rana University, Burhanuddin Rabbani University "Kabul Education University". In addition, some participants who had completed their 12th grade participated in this study. After applying the exclusion area condition the Afghan participants were 709 samples which consist 467 males and 242 females (Table 3).

3.6.1.3 Overall Participants

Overall, the sample size was One thousand and five hundred samples. In addition, after screening and applying the conditions, the data sample of 94.4% was included due to inclusion criteria and 5.6% sample was excluded due to exclusion condition. Following this, it had 772 males, which was 54.51% of all the data; 644 females, which was 45.48% of all the data; and some other demographic details were measured (Table 3). Furthermore, the age factor was taken as ratio data, which ranged from 17 to 30 years, and its mean age was 21.65 years, visit for further information (Table 2). Moreover, participants' internet usage ranged from 15 minutes to 20 hours per day, and its mean was 3.58 hours per day for Indian participants and 3.17 hours per day for Afghan participants (Table 5).

3.7 Statistical Analysis

Overall, the data was normally distributed therefore parametric test were applied. There is difference between the parameter and statistical test. A parameter is a number that describes an entire population, such as the population mean, whereas a statistic is a number that describes a sample, such as the sample mean (Kothari, 2004).

Furthermore, parametric tests were applied because parametric tests presume that the sample data originates from a population with a given set of characteristics and follows a probability distribution normally distributed (Kothari, 2004).

3.7.1 Descriptive Statistics

The mean (with graphical representation) and standard deviation for all considered variables, namely Ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying, and Cyber victimization, were analyzed. Furthermore, independent variables' descriptive data was collected. The mean is one of the central tendencies, which is known as the arithmetical average. It has flaws when the extreme outlier. Similarly, standard deviation is one of the measures of the deviation. It means square-root of the average of squares of deviations, which is taken from the arithmetic average (Kothari, 2004).

3.7.2 Inferential Statistics

Two-Way Analysis of Variances (2-way ANOVA) was used to study the main effects of countries and gender, as well as the effect of interaction among them, on measures of ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization. As Kothari (2004) argued that evaluating more than two dimensions in interaction at one time is called ANOVA. Furthermore, in this study, there are two factors and some other dimension because of that two-way ANOVA was applied.

Regression Analysis: To ascertain ethnocentrism as a predictor of cyberbullying and cyber victimization, regression analysis was employed. Regression is used in different fields for prediction and relations among variables. Regression has two types, such as simple regression and multiple regression. In this method, the dependent variable is predicted to show its strength with an independent variable or variables (Kothari, 2004; Schinka & Velicer, 2013).

Chapter IV

Results and Discussion

4

4.0 Introduction

4.1 Descriptive statistical analysis

4.2 Inferential Statistical analysis

4.3 Discussion

4.0 Introduction

The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). There are two sections of analysis. First is descriptive statistical results and findings with diagrams and figures. The second section is inferential statistics results and findings with graphical representations for better understanding. The results are described according to respective statistical analyses and discussed in the light of relevant research following the hypotheses laid down. Furthermore, discussion was also highlighted through the previous literature review.

4.1 Descriptive statistical analysis

Table 2
Descriptive statistics of the participants' age

Participants' age range	Indian count	Afghan count	Total	Mean of age	Mode of age	Median of age
17	12	6	18	21.65	21	21
18	49	30	79			
19	52	77	129			
20	133	129	262			
21	219	103	322			
22	96	105	201			
23	45	88	133			
24	41	53	94			
25	27	46	73			
26	10	15	25			
27	9	14	23			
28	7	13	20			
29	7	16	23			
30	0	14	14			
Total	707	709	1416			

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistical data on age. There were 1416 participants, whose ages ranged from 17 to 30 years. The mean age was 21.65 years, with a mode of 21 years and a median age of 21 years.

Figure 5
A bar chart shows the countries' participants student

Note: Bar chart (Figure 5) showing the Afghan and Indian students who participated in the study. The chart shows that most of the participants' ages ranged from 18 to 25 years.

Table 3
Descriptive statistics of the participants' gender

		Indian	Afghan	Total
Gender	Male	305	467	772
	Female	402	242	644
Total		707	709	1416

Table 3 enumerated the descriptive statistics of both genders with a country wise. There were 772 males and 644 females selected for this study. Furthermore, Indian participants were 707 and Afghans were among 709 in this study analysis.

Figure 6

A bar chart indicates the gender with country-wise distribution.

Note: Bar chart (Figure 6) showing the male and female participants of the study in both countries. The chart shows that there are more Afghan male participants and fewer Afghan female participants in the study.

Table 4

Descriptive statistics of the participants' Country with gender difference

Country		Male	Female	Total
Indian	Number	305	402	707
	Percentage	43.1%	56.9%	100%
Afghan	Number	467	242	709
	Percentage	65.9%	34.1%	100%

Table 4

Descriptive statistics of the participants' Country with gender difference describes the descriptive statistics of the participants' ethnicity. There were 707 Indian and 709 Afghan students. In addition, there were 43.1% of Indian males and 56.9% of Indian females. Moreover, there were 65.9% of Afghan males and 34.1% of Afghan females.

Figure 7

A pie chart shows the countries' participants

Note: Pie chart (Figure 7) shows the whole percentile, which shows that 49.93% were Indian and 50.07% were Afghan students.

Table 5

The descriptive statistics of Internet surfing per day hours of the participants

		Mean	Median	Mode	Maximum	Minimum	Missing	Range
Country	Indian	3.58	3.00	3.00	20.00	0.50	9	19.50
	Afghan	3.17	3.00	2.00	14.00	0.25	0	13.75

Table 5 shows the descriptive statistics of Internet users per day by hour type. Indian students were using the internet per day for 3.58 hours on average, and Afghan students were using it for 3.17 hours per day.

Figure 8
A pie chart shows the internet surfing hours.

Note: Pie chart (Figure 8) depicts all internet surfing. The least internet user surfs the internet 15 minutes per day and the highest internet user is 20 hours per day.

Table 6
Descriptive statistics of the education level of the participants

Country		up to 12th grade		under graduate		Post-graduate (Master, M.Phil., Ph.D.)	
		N	Percentage In row	N	Percentage In row	N	Percentage In row
Indian	Indian	16	2.3%	236	33.4%	455	64.4%
	Afghan	27	3.8%	636	89.7%	46	6.5%

Table 6 shows the descriptive statistics of the education level of the students. Indian participants consist of 12th graders or high school (23.3%), undergraduates

(33.4%), and postgraduates (66.4%). On the other hand, Afghan students consist of 12th grade (3.8%), undergraduate (89.7%), and postgraduate (6.5%).

Figure 9
A multi-population pyramid difference between countries' educational qualifications

Note: The population pyramid (Figure 9) tells us the number of each grade in the education level of the participants.

Table 7
Descriptive statistics of the educational fields of the participants

Educational Fields	Country		Total
	Number of Indians	Number of Afghans	
Social Sciences	135	236	371
Natural Sciences	339	42	381

Medical Sciences	0	117	117
Legal and Administrative studies	174	194	368
Computer and Engineering Sciences	27	93	120
High School or General Studies	8	27	35
Missing Edu. field	24	0	24
Total	707	709	1416

Table 7 is the descriptive statistics of the education fields of the participants. There were 707 Indian participants, which consisted of 135 social science fields, 339 belonged to the natural science field, 174 were studying the legal and administrative fields, 27 were in the computer and engineering science fields, 8 were from high school, and 27 participants had not completed the education field. Furthermore, there were 709 Afghan participants, which consisted of 236 from the social science field, 42 from the natural science field, 117 from the medical sciences field, 194 were studying the legal and administrative field, 93 were in the computer and engineering science field, and 27 from high school or general field.

Figure 10 A multi-population pyramid difference between countries' educational fields

Note: A multi-population pyramid (Figure 10) difference between countries' educational fields of the participants.

Table 8
Descriptive statistics on social media of the participants

Social Media name	Indian social media users		Afghan social media users	
	Count	N %	Count	N %
Facebook	416	59.2%	644	91.2%
Twitter	199	28.3%	237	33.6%
WhatsApp	684	97.3%	590	83.6%
IMO	29	4.1%	327	46.3%
LinkedIn	173	24.6%	41	5.8%
WeChat	19	2.7%	63	8.9%
Viber	19	2.7%	307	43.5%

Instagram	568	80.8%	301	42.6%
Google Duo	322	45.8%	190	26.9%
YouTube	570	81.1%	316	44.8%
Line	12	1.7%	19	2.7%
Myspace	5	0.7%	17	2.4%
Skype	64	9.1%	82	11.6%
Snapchat	298	42.4%	137	19.4%
Tiktok	85	12.1%	210	29.7%
Hike	63	9.0%	19	2.7%
Telegram	290	41.3%	403	57.1%

Table 8 shows the descriptive statistics of social media users in both countries. Of Indian students, the most were using WhatsApp (97.3%) and the least were using MySpace (0.7%). On the other hand, Afghan students most often used Facebook (91.2%), and the least used MySpace (2.5%).

Figure 11

A multi-population pyramid difference between countries' social media users

Note: The population pyramid (Figure 11) shows the number of social media users in India and Afghanistan.

The descriptive statistics of cyberbullying contaminant the participants

Table 9
The Descriptive statistics of cyberbullying contaminant of the participants

Cyber contaminant	Indian		Afghan	
	N	Percentage	N	Percentage
Victim	65	23.38%	158	25%
Perpetrator	24	8.6%	97	15.37%
Bystander	189	67.98%	376	59.58%

Table 9

The Descriptive statistics of cyberbullying contaminant of the participants shows the descriptive statistics of cyberbullying as perpetrator, victim, and bystander. Indian cyber victims were 23.38%, perpetrators were 8.6%, and bystanders were 67.98%. Moreover, Afghan cyber victims were 25%, perpetrators were 15.37%, and bystanders were 59.58%.

Figure 12
A multi-population pyramid difference between countries' cyberbullying behavior

Note: Multi-population pyramid (Figure 12) showed the cyber contaminant, for instance, cyber victim, cyber bullying as a perpetrator, and cyber bystander of the participants of both countries.

Table 10
Descriptive statistics of Indian caste and Afghan Tribes of the participants

Castes and Tribes	Indian		Afghan	
	N	Percentage	N	Percentage
Open/General category (OC/GC)	391	55.3%		
Scheduled Tribe (ST)	67	9.5%		
Scheduled Extremely Backward Caste (SEBC)	143	20.2%		

Scheduled Caste (SC)	58	8.2%		
Other Backward Caste (OBC)	38	5.4%		
Economically Weaker Section (EWS)	10	1.4%		
Pashtun			214	30.2%
Tajik			246	34.7%
Hazara			211	29.8%
Baloch			2	0.3%
Uzbek			7	1.0%
Bayat			6	0.8%
Sadat			17	2.4%
Qazalbash			6	0.8%
Total	707	100.0%	709	100.0%

Table 10 depicts the descriptive statistics of the Indian Castes and Afghan Tribes. Indian castes consist of General/Open category (G/OC) 55.3%, Scheduled Tribe (ST) 9.5%, Scheduled Extremely Backward Caste (SEBC), 20.2%, Scheduled Caste (SC) 8.2%, Other Backward Caste (OBC) 5.4%, and Economically Weaker Section (EWS) 1.4%. Furthermore, the Afghan tribe consist of Pashtun 30.2%, Tajik 34.7%, Hazara 29.8%, Baloch 0.3%, Uzbek 1.0%, Bayat 0.8%, Sadat 2.4%, and Qazalbash 0.8%.

Figure 13
A multi-line chart depicted the Indian castes and Afghan tribe numbers.

Note: A multi-line chart (Figure 13) shows the Indian castes and Afghan tribes' numbers. The Indian Open caste participants were the most; there were 391 participants, and the least number was the Economically Weaker Section (EWS) caste. On the other hand, Afghans also had different tribes participating. The largest number of tribes was Tajik; it had 246 participants, and the least number of tribes was the Baloch; it had 2 participants.

4.2 Inferential Statistical analysis

Hypotheses framed for the present study are:-

Table 11

Descriptive statistics of the participants' age, Revised Cyberbullying Inventory-II (RCBI-II), and Revised Cyberbullying Inventory (RCBI)

Variables	Mean	SD	N
Age	21.65	2.516	1416
Ethnocentrism	35.2453	8.37116	1378
RCBI-ii	11.8733	3.70398	1381
Cyberbullying			
RCBI-ii Cyber victim	13.1647	5.09082	1384
RCBI Cyberbullying	3.0326	5.56728	1382
RCBI cyber victim	3.3487	6.74702	1391

Table 11 shows the descriptive measures of central tendency. It computed and summarized the variables such as Age, Ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying of RCBI-II, Cyber Victimization of RCBI-II, Cyberbullying of RCBI, and Cyber Victimization of RCBI variables. Result of Age variable was as N= 1416, M=21.65 , SD= 2.516. The result of the ethnocentrism variable was N = 1378, M = 35.24, SD = 8.37. The result of cyberbullying of the RCBI-II variable was N = 1381, M = 11.87, SD = 3.70. The result of the cyber victimization of the RCBI-II variable was N= 1384, M = 13.16, SD = 5.09. The result of the cyberbullying of the RCBI variable was N = 1382, M = 3.0326, SD = 5.56728. The result of the cyber victimization of the RCBI variable was N = 1391, M = 3.35, SD = 6.75.

The SD of cyberbullying RCBI-II scale was not too large. However, cyber victimization RCBI-II scale SD was very large. It conveys the message that victimization was on a large scale and it was varied among the students. However, the SD of the RCBI scale (cyberbullying, cyber victimization) was too large. It means the responses varied quite a bit. Similarly, the SD of the Ethnocentrism variable is also too large. It also conveys the message that the responses are too varied.

Table 12

Pearson Product Moment correlation among Age, Ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying, and Cyber Victim and two scales via RCBI-II and RCBI

Variables		Age	Ethnocentris m	RCBI-ii Cyberbullyin g	RCBI -ii Cyber victim	RCBI- Cyber bullyin g	RCBI -cyber victim
Age	Correlatio n	-					
	Sig. (2- tailed)	-					
	N	-					
Ethnocentris m	Correlatio n	0.01 9	-				
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.47 2	-				
	N	1378	-				
RCBI-ii Cyberbullyin g	Correlatio n	- 0.00 5	.113**	-			
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.86 5	0.000	-			
	N	1381	1351	-			
RCBI-ii Cyber victim	Correlatio n	0.01 8	0.026	.629**	-		
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.51 5	0.341	0.000	-		
	N	1384	1354	1367	-		
RCBI- Cyberbullyin g	Correlatio n	0.01 6	.139**	.489**	.445**	-	
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.54 5	0.000	0.000	0.000	-	
	N	1382	1350	1357	1357	-	
RCBI-Cyber victim	Correlatio n	.062 *	.114**	.445**	.538**	.615**	-
	Sig. (2- tailed)	0.02 0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-
	N	1391	1357	1365	1365	1375	-

* $p < .05$. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). ** $p < .01$. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 12 shows a Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient computed to assess the relationship between age, ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization. First, it was assessed that there was a non-significant positive correlation between age and ethnocentrism ($r = 0.019$, $n = 1378$, $p = 0.472$). Second, there was a non-significant negative correlation between age and cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale with $r = -0.005$, $n = 1381$, and $p = 0.865$. Third, there was a non-significant positive correlation between age and cyber victimization on the RCBI-II scale with $r = 0.018$, $n = 1384$, and $p = 0.515$. Fourth, there was a non-significant positive correlation

between age and cyberbullying on the RCBI scale with $r = 0.016$, $n = 1382$, and $p = 0.545$. Fifth, there was a significant positive correlation between age and cyber victimization on the RCBI scale with $r = 0.062$, $n = 1391$, and $p = 0.020$.

A multi-line chart (Figure 14) summarizes the results. Overall, the age variable of the participants did not have a significant association except with cyber victimization on the RCBI scale. It means that an increase in age had a positive significant correlation with an increase in cyber victimization of the participants.

The correlation was assessed between ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization. First, it assessed that there was a significant positive correlation between ethnocentrism and cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale with $r = 0.113$, $n = 1351$, and $p < 0.001$. Second, there was a non-significant positive correlation between ethnocentrism and cyber victimization on the RCBI-II scale with $r = 0.026$, $n = 1354$, and $p = 0.341$. Third, there was a significant positive correlation between ethnocentrism and cyberbullying on the RCBI scale with $r = 0.139$, $n = 1350$, and $p < 0.001$. Fourth, there was a significant positive association between ethnocentrism and cyber victimization on the RCBI scale with $r = 0.114$, $n = 1357$, and $p < 0.001$.

Overall, the ethnocentrism variable of the participants did have a significant association with all variables except cyber victimization on the RCBI-II scale. It means that an increase in ethnocentrism had a positive significant correlation with an increase in cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale and cyberbullying and victimization on the RCBI-II scale.

The correlation was assessed between cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale and cyber victimization on the RCBI-II scale. It was assessed that there was a significant positive correlation between cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale and cyber victimization on the RCBI-II scale with $r = 0.629$, $n = 1367$, and $p < 0.001$.

Overall, cyberbullying of the RCBI-II scale participants did have a significant association with cyber victimization on the RCBI-II scale. It means that the increase in cyberbullying measured by the RCBI-II scale had a positive significant correlation with the increase in cyberbullying measured by the RCBI-II scale. In other words, an

increase in cyberbullying is associated with an increase in cyber victims among the participants.

The correlation was assessed between cyberbullying on the RCBI scale and cyber victimization on the RCBI scale. It was assessed that there was a significant positive correlation between cyberbullying on the RCBI scale and cyber victimization on the RCBI scale with $r = 0.615$, $n = 1375$, and $p < 0.001$.

Overall, cyberbullying in the RCBI variable of the participants did have a significant association with cyber victimization on the RCBI scale. It means that the increase in cyberbullying on the RCBI scale had a positive significant correlation with the increase in cyberbullying by RCBI. In other words, an increase in cyberbullying is associated with an increase in cyber victims among the participants.

Figure 14
A multi-line Chart differences of age vairable

A multi-line chart (Figure 14) depicted relationships of variable age with ethnocentrism, cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale, cyber victimization on the RCBI-II scale, cyberbullying on the RCBI scale, and cyber victimization on the RCBI scale variables in both countries; India and Afghanistan.

Hypothesis One

H₁: There will be a significant difference in level of ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization among adults age.

Overall, H₁ is rejected in the case of the association variable of age with cyberbullying and cyber victimization. There was almost zero correlation between the variable of age and other variables. However, there is only one case of age with a cyber-victim on the RCBI scale, which showed a significant correlation at the 0.05 level. Furthermore, in the case of the ethnocentrism variable with cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale, cyberbullying on the RCBI scale, and cyber victims on the RCBI scale had a significant association at 0.01 level. However, just cyber victims on the RCBI-II scale did not have a significant association with ethnocentrism. So overall, it is inferred that H₁ is accepted in the case of the association of ethnocentrism with other variables. Moreover, H₁ was accepted in the case of cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale in correlation with the cyber victim on the RCBI-II scale on a 0.01 level. Similarly, H₁ was accepted in the case of cyberbullying on the RCBI scale and correlated with the cyber victim on the RCBI scale at a 0.01 level.

Table 13
Descriptive Group Statistics of ethnocentrism, RCBI-II, and RCBI scales' cyberbullying, and cyber victimization

Variables	Country	N	Mean	SD
Ethnocentrism	Indian	675	34.0756	7.57878
	Afghan	703	36.3684	8.92925
RCBI-ii Cyberbullying	Indian	689	11.7010	2.93000
	Afghan	692	12.0448	4.33503
RCBI-ii Cyber victimization	Indian	684	12.8743	4.24733
	Afghan	700	13.4486	5.78676
RCBI-Cyberbullying	Indian	686	2.0306	3.92379
	Afghan	696	4.0201	6.66676
RCBI-Cyber victimization	Indian	693	1.9625	4.49679
	Afghan	698	4.7249	8.17923

Table 13 shows the descriptive measures of the central tendency of both countries via India and Afghanistan. It computed and summarized the variables such as Ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale, Cyber Victimization on the RCBI-II scale, Cyberbullying on the RCBI scale, and Cyber Victimization on the RCBI scales variables. Results of Ethnocentrism variable India's participants was as (N= 675, M=34.08, SD= 7.58) and Afghanistan's participants was as (N= 703, M=36.37, SD= 8.93). Results of Cyberbullying of RCBI-II variable India's participants were as (N= 689, M=11.70, SD= 2.93) and Afghanistan's participants were as (N= 692, M=12.04, SD= 4.34). Results of Cyber Victimization of RCBI-II variable India's participants were as (N= 684, M=12.87, SD= 4.25) and Afghanistan's participants were as (N= 700, M=13.45, SD= 5.79). Results of Cyberbullying of RCBI variable India's participants were as (N= 686, M=2.03, SD= 3.92) and Afghanistan's participants were as (N= 696, M=4.02, SD= 6.67). Results of Cyber Victimization of RCBI variable India's participants was as (N= 693, M=1.96, SD= 4.50) and Afghanistan's participants were as (N= 698, M=4.72, SD= 8.18). Overall, the SD of the RCBI scale (cyberbullying, cyber victimization) was too large. It means the responses were too varied quite a bit. Other variables are not too different.

Table 14

Independent Samples t-Test of country with ethnocentrism level, RCBI-II and RCBI scales' Cyberbullying, and cyber victimization

Variables	t	Df	P
Ethnocentrism	-5.129	1376	0.000
RCBI-ii Cyberbullying	-1.726	1379	0.085
RCBI-ii Cyber victimization	-2.101	1382	0.036
RCBI-Cyberbullying	-6.749	1380	0.000
RCBI-Cyber victimization	-7.798	1389	0.000

p<.05. t-test is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).* p<.001. t-test is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Table 14 depicted an independent-samples t-test among the countries (India, Afghanistan) to compare Ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying of RCBI-II, Cyber Victimization of RCBI-II, Cyberbullying of RCBI, and Cyber Victimization of RCBI variables.

There was a significant difference between the level of ethnocentrism and countries. The mean score for India was (M=34.08, SD=7.58), and the mean score for

Afghan was ($M=36.37$, $SD=8.93$) conditions; $t(1376) = -5.129$, $p < .001$, at the 0.001 level on the two-tailed test. These results suggested that level of ethnocentrism does affect the countries. Especially, our results suggested that Afghans were more influenced than Indians. In other words, Afghan participants statistically proved that they had more ethnocentric behavior compared to Indian participants.

Moreover, there was not a significant difference between the level of Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) and countries. The mean score for India was ($M=11.70$, $SD=2.93$) and the mean score for Afghan was ($M=12.04$, $SD=4.34$) conditions; $t(1379) = -1.726$, $p=0.085$, at the 0.05 level on the two-tailed test. These results suggest that level of Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) does not affect the countries significantly.

There was a significant difference between the level of Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II) and countries. The mean score for India was ($M=12.87$, $SD=4.25$), and the mean score for Afghan was ($M=13.45$, $SD=5.79$) conditions; $t(1382) = -2.101$, $p=0.036$, at the 0.05 level on the two-tailed test. These results suggest that level of e Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II) does affect the countries. Especially, our results suggested that Afghans were more influenced than Indians. In other words, Afghan participants statistically proved that they become more cyber victimized compared to Indian participants.

There was a significant difference between the level of Cyberbullying (RCBI) and countries. The mean scores for India were ($M=2.03$, $SD=3.92$), and the mean score for Afghan was ($M=4.02$, $SD=6.67$) conditions; $t(1380) = -6.749$, $p < 0.001$, at the 0.001 level on the two-tailed test. These results suggest that level of e Cyberbullying (RCBI) does affect the countries. Especially, our results suggested that Afghans were more influenced than Indians. In other words, Afghan participants statistically proved that they did more cyberbullying activities as perpetrators compared to Indian participants.

There was a significant difference between the level of Cyber Victimization (RCBI) and countries. The mean score for India was ($M=1.96$, $SD=4.50$) and the mean score for Afghan was ($M=4.72$, $SD=8.18$) conditions; $t(1389) = -7.798$, $p < 0.001$, at the 0.001 level on the two-tailed test. These results suggested that level of e Cyber Victimization (RCBI) does affect the countries. Especially, our results suggested that

Afghans were more influenced than Indians. In other words, Afghan participants showed that they become cyber victimized more compared to Indian participants.

Furthermore, a multi-line chart (Figure 15) summarized the results. Overall, the country variable suggested that Afghan participants have been largely affected by Ethnocentrism, Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II), Cyberbullying (RCBI), and Cyber Victimization (RCBI) compare to Indian participants.

Hypothesis Two

H₂: Adults belonging to India and Afghanistan will be significantly different on their measure of-

- Ethnocentrism
- Cyberbullying
- Cyber victimization

H₂ was accepted in those cases which measured the difference between India and Afghanistan on ethnocentrism, Cyber Victim (RCBI-II), Cyberbullying (RCBI), and Cyber victim (RCBI). However, in the case of Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) result was rejected. It means that it is statistically proven that Afghan students were significantly different compared to Indian students in all cases, except Cyberbullying (RCBI-II).

Figure 15
A multi-line Chart difference between countries

Note: A multi-line chart (Figure 15) depicted the difference between countries' variables (India and Afghanistan) with ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying (RCBI-II), Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II), Cyberbullying (RCBI), Cyber Victimization (RCBI) variables.

Table 15
Descriptive Group Statistics of ethnocentrism, RCBI-II and RCBI scales' Cyberbullying, and cyber victimization

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	SD
Ethnocentrism	Male	754	35.6618	8.73095
	Female	624	34.7420	7.89228
Cyberbullying (RCBI-ii)	Male	755	12.1219	4.03249
	Female	626	11.5735	3.24200
Cyber victimization (RCBI-ii)	Male	757	13.3197	5.20742
	Female	627	12.9777	4.94405
Cyberbullying (RCBI)	Male	753	3.8127	6.04467
	Female	629	2.0986	4.77518

Cyber victimization (RCBI)	Male	757	4.4042	7.78330
	Female	634	2.0883	4.96863

Table 15 showed the descriptive measures of the central tendency of both Genders via male and female. It computed and summarized the variables such as Ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying of RCBI-II, Cyber Victimization of RCBI-II, Cyberbullying of RCBI, and Cyber Victimization of RCBI variables. Results of Ethnocentrism variable male participants were as (N= 754, M=35.66, SD= 8.73) and female participants were as (N= 624, M=34.74, SD= 7.89). Results of Cyberbullying of RCBI-II variable male participants were as (N= 755, M=12.12, SD= 4.03) and female participants were as (N= 626, M=11.57, SD= 3.24). Results of Cyber Victimization of RCBI-II variable male participants were as (N= 757, M=13.31, SD= 5.21) and female participants were as (N= 627, M=12.98, SD= 4.94). Results of Cyberbullying of RCBI variable male participants were as (N= 753, M=3.81, SD=6.04) and female participants were as (N=629, M=2.09, SD=4.77). Results of Cyber Victimization of RCBI variable male participants were as (N=757, M=4.40, SD= 7.78) and female participants were as (N= 634, M=2.09, SD= 4.97). Overall, the SD of the RCBI scale (cyberbullying, cyber victimization) was too large. It means the responses were too varied quite a bit. Other variables are not too different.

Table 16
Independent Samples t-Test of gender with ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying, and cyber victimization

Variables	t	Df	P
Ethnocentrism	2.033	1376	0.042
Cyberbullying (RCBI-ii)	2.745	1379	0.006
Cyber victimization (RCBI-ii)	1.244	1382	0.214
Cyberbullying (RCBI)	5.766	1380	0.000
Cyber victimization (RCBI)	6.469	1389	0.000

p<.05. t-test is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).* p<.01. t-test is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Table 16 depicted an independent-samples t-test among the genders (male, female) to compare Ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying of RCBI-II, Cyber Victimization of RCBI-II, Cyberbullying of RCBI, and Cyber Victimization of RCBI variables.

There was a significant difference between the level of ethnocentrism and gender. The mean score for males was (M=35.66, SD=8.73), and the mean score for females was (M=34.74, SD=7.89) conditions; $t(1376) = 2.033, p = 0.042$, at the 0.05 level on the two-tailed test. These results suggested that level of ethnocentrism does

affect gender. Especially, our results suggested that males were more influenced than females. In other words, male participants did offensive activity more than females.

Moreover, there was a significant difference between the level of Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) and countries. The mean score for males was ($M=12.12$, $SD=4.03$), and the mean score for females was ($M=11.57$, $SD=3.24$) conditions; $t(1379) = 2.745$, $p=0.006$, at the 0.01 level on the two-tailed test. These results suggested that level of Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) does affect the gender significantly. Especially, our results suggested that males were doing more cyberbullying activities and becoming perpetrators than females were.

There was not a significant difference between the level of Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II) and gender. The mean score for males was ($M=13.31$, $SD=5.21$), and the mean score for females was ($M=12.98$, $SD=4.94$) conditions; $t(1382) = 1.244$, $p=0.214$, at the 0.05 level on the two-tailed test. These results suggested that level of e Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II) does not affect gender.

There was a significant difference between the level of Cyberbullying (RCBI) and gender. The mean score for males was ($M=3.81$, $SD=6.04$) and the mean score for females was ($M=2.09$, $SD=4.77$) conditions; $t(1380) = 5.766$, $p<0.001$, at the 0.001 level on the two-tailed test. These results suggest that level of e Cyberbullying (RCBI) does affect the countries. Especially, our results suggested that males were more influenced than females. In another word, male participants showed that they did more offensive behavior compared to female participants.

There was a significant difference between the level of Cyber Victimization (RCBI) and gender. The mean score for males was ($M=4.40$, $SD=7.78$), and the mean score for females was ($M=2.09$, $SD=4.97$) conditions; $t(1389) = 6.469$, $p<0.001$, at the 0.001 level on the two-tailed test. These results suggested that level of e Cyber Victimization (RCBI) does affect the countries. Especially, our results suggested that males were more influenced than females. In another word, male participants showed that they become more victimized compared female participants.

Furthermore, a multi-line chart (Figure 16) summarized the results. Overall, the gender variable suggested that male participants have largely affected by Ethnocentrism, Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II), Cyberbullying (RCBI), and Cyber Victimization (RCBI) compared to the female participants.

Hypothesis Three

H₃: Gender will be significantly different in their measures of-

- Ethnocentrism
- Cyberbullying
- Cyber victimization

H₃ was accepted in cases of differences between gender with ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying (RCBI-II), Cyberbullying (RCBI), and Cyber victim (RCBI). However, in the case of cyber victimization (RCBI-II) results here was rejected. It means that it is statistically proven that male students were significantly different compared to female students in all cases, except for Cyber victims (RCBI-II).

Figure 16
Multi-line Chart difference between gender

Note: A multi-line chart (Figure 16) depicted the difference between gender variables with ethnocentrism, Cyberbullying (RCBI-II), Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II), Cyberbullying (RCBI), and Cyber Victimization (RCBI) variables.

Table 17
Descriptive Statistics of Ethnocentrism on the bases of Gender, and Countries

Gender	Country	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	India	34.5000	7.82827	292
	Afghanistan	36.3961	9.18885	462
	Total	35.6618	8.73095	754
Female	India	33.7520	7.37681	383
	Afghanistan	36.3154	8.42764	241
	Total	34.7420	7.89228	624
Both Gender	India	34.0756	7.57878	675
	Afghanistan	36.3684	8.92925	703
	Total	35.2453	8.37116	1378

Table 17 showed the descriptive measures of the central tendency of Ethnocentrism behavior on the bases of Gender (male, female) and countries (India, Afghanistan). It computed and summarized the variables such as Ethnocentrism via gender and country levels.

Results of the Ethnocentrism variable based on Indian male participants were as (N= 292, M=34.50, SD= 7.83) and Afghan male participants were as (N= 462, M=36.40, SD= 9.19). Overall, males of both countries were as (N= 754, M=35.66, SD= 8.73). Results of the Ethnocentrism variable on the base of Indian female participants were as (N= 383, M=33.75, SD=7.38) and Afghan female participants were as (N= 241, M=36.31, SD= 8.43). Overall, females of both countries were as (N= 624, M=34.74, SD= 7.89). Results of the Ethnocentrism variable on the base of Indian both gender participants were as (N= 675, M=34.08, SD= 7.58) and Afghan both gender participants were as (N= 703, M=36.37, SD= 8.93). Overall both countries and gender were as (N= 1378, M=35.25, SD= 8.37). Overall, the SD of Afghans in every variable was too large. It means the responses were too varied quite a bit.

Table 18
Two-way ANOVA of Ethnocentrism with Gender and Countries

Variables	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared/ η_p^2
Gender	55.621	1	55.621	0.808	0.369	0.001
Countries	1610.358	1	1610.358	23.392	0.000	0.017
Gender*countries	36.056	1	36.056	0.524	0.469	0.000
Error	94590.982	1374	68.844			
Total	1808288.000	1378				

R Squared = .020 (Adjusted R Squared = .018)

Table 18 showed the results of the Two Way Independent ANOVA. It showed that there was no significant main effect of Gender on ethnocentrism score ($F(1,1374) = 0.808, p > 0.05, \eta_p^2 = 0.001$) with males (mean = 35.66; SD = 8.73) and females (mean = 34.74; SD = 7.89) showing similar ethnocentrism scores.

However, there was a significant main effect of Countries on Ethnocentrism scores ($F(1,1374) = 36.255, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.017$). Participants in India condition performed significantly low ethnocentrism score (mean = 34.08, SD = 7.58) than those in the Afghanistan condition (mean = 36.37, SD = 8.93) with a large level of eta square.

It means that Afghanistan participants have been largely affected by ethnocentrism compared to Indian participants.

In addition, no significant interaction was found between the two variables ($F(1,1374) = 0.524, p > 0.05, \eta_p^2 < 0.001$). Furthermore, Figure 15 and Figure 16 also proved these findings and suggested that ethnocentrism of Afghan participants of both genders has a small effect compared to the gender of Indian participants.

Furthermore, a multi-line chart (Figure 17) also proved these findings and suggested that Ethnocentrism of Afghan participants (male and female) has the highest means score (Mean=36.37; SD=8.93) and the Indian participants (male and female) have the lowest mean score (Mean=34.08; SD=7.58). It means that condition of Afghan country ethnocentrism behavior was higher than in India. On another side, Indian female participants had the lowest mean score. It means that Indian females had very less ethnocentric behavior compared to Indian male and Afghan participants. Overall, it was inferred that Afghan students' ethnocentrism behavior effect was the highest level of effect size (0.017) level, which was significantly different from that, of Indian students.

Figure 17
A multi-line chart depicted difference between countries variable with ethnocentrism variables.

Note: A multi-line chart (Figure 17) depicted the difference between gender variables, ethnocentrism, and country variables. These lines also showed that Afghans both male and female have more ethnocentrism levels compared to the Indian gender.

Table 19
Descriptive Statistics of Cyberbullying (RCBI-ii) on bases of Gender, and Countries

Gender	Country	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	India	11.6467	2.77021	300
	Afghanistan	12.4352	4.65881	455
	Total	12.1219	4.03249	755
Female	India	11.7429	3.05039	389
	Afghanistan	11.2954	3.52312	237
	Total	11.5735	3.24200	626
Both Gender	India	11.7010	2.93000	689
	Afghanistan	12.0448	4.33503	692
	Total	11.8733	3.70398	1381

Table 19 showed the descriptive measures of the central tendency of Cyberbullying (RCBI-ii) on the bases of Gender (male, female) and countries (India, Afghanistan). It computed and summarized the variables such as Cyberbullying (RCBI-ii) via gender and country levels.

Results of Cyberbullying (RCBI-ii) variable on the base of Indian male participants was as (N= 300, M=11.65, SD= 2.77) and Afghan male participants were as (N= 455, M=12.44, SD= 4.66). The overall male of both countries was as (N= 755, M=12.12, SD= 4.03). Results of Cyberbullying (RCBI-ii) variable on the base of Indian female participants was as (N= 389, M=11.74, SD=3.05) and Afghan female participants were as (N= 237, M=11.29, SD= 3.52). Overall females of both countries were as (N= 626, M=11.57, SD= 3.24).

Results of Cyberbullying (RCBI-ii) variable on the base of both Indian gender participants were as (N= 689, M=11.70, SD= 2.93) and both Afghan gender participants were as (N= 692, M=12.04, SD= 4.34). Overall both countries and gender were as (N= 1381, M=11.87, SD= 3.70). Overall, the SD of the Afghan participants' variable was too large. It means the responders were too varied quite a bit.

Table 20
Two-way ANOVA of cyberbullying (RCBI-II) on the bases of Gender and Countries

Variables	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared/ η_p^2
Gender	88.382	1	88.382	6.512	0.011	0.005
Countries	9.433	1	9.433	0.695	0.405	0.001
Gender*countries	124.003	1	124.003	9.137	0.003	0.007
Error	18688.002	1377	13.572			
Total	213619.000	1381				

R Squared = .013 (Adjusted R Squared = .011)

Table 20 showed the results of the Two Way Independent ANOVA. It showed that there was significant main effect of Gender ($F(1,1377) = 6.51, p = 0.011, \eta_p^2 = 0.005$) with males (mean = 12.12; SD = 4.03) and females (mean = 11.57; SD = 3.24) showing different Cyberbullying scores and medium level of effect size or eta square. However, there was not a significant main effect of Countries on RCBI-II Cyberbullying scores ($F(1,1377) = 0.695, p = 0.405, \eta_p^2 = 0.001$). Participants in India condition performed low cyber bullying score (mean = 11.70, SD = 2.93) than those in the Afghanistan condition (mean = 12.04, SD = 4.34). In addition, two variables interaction of gender and countries were found significant ($F(1,1377) = 9.14, p = 0.003, \eta_p^2 = 0.007$). It means

that the condition of Afghan participants with gender interaction had a significant difference with a medium level of effect or eta square.

Furthermore, a multi-line chart (Figure 18) also proved these findings and suggested that Cyberbullying of Afghan male participants had the highest means score of cyberbullying (Mean=12.44; SD=4.66) and the Afghan female participants have the lowest mean score for cyberbullying (Mean=11.29; SD=3.52). It means that Afghan male cyber users are the most cyberbullying and become perpetrators and the Afghan female participants become almost zero time cyberbullying behavior. On the other side, Indian female participants had a high mean score (Mean=11.74; SD=3.05) and male participants have a low mean score for cyberbullying (Mean=11.65; SD=2.77). It means that Indian females do more cyberbullying behavior compared to Indian male participants. Overall, it was inferred that Afghan students' Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) behavior effect was medium level, which was significantly different from Indian students.

Figure 18
A multi-line chart between countries and cyberbullying (RCBI-II)

Note: a multi-line chart (Figure 18) depicted the difference between countries' variables with Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) variable. In addition, Afghan male participants had more cyberbullying (RCBI-II) behavior compared to both Indian gender and Afghan female. However, Afghan female participants had the least cyberbullying (RCBI-II) score compared to other variables.

Table 21
Descriptive Statistics of Cyber victimization (RCBI-ii) on bases of Gender and Countries

Gender	Country	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	India	12.4747	3.65767	297
	Afghanistan	13.8652	5.93935	460
	Total	13.3197	5.20742	757
Female	India	13.1809	4.63075	387
	Afghanistan	12.6500	5.40517	240
	Total	12.9777	4.94405	627
Both Gender	India	12.8743	4.24733	684
	Afghanistan	13.4486	5.78676	700
	Total	13.1647	5.09082	1384

Table 21 showed the descriptive statistic of the central tendency of Cyber victimization (RCBI-ii) on the bases of Gender (male, female) and countries (India, Afghanistan). It computed and summarized the variables such as Cyber victimization (RCBI-ii) via gender and country levels.

Results of Cyber victimization (RCBI-ii) variable on base of Indian male participants were as (N= 297, M=12.47, SD= 3.66) and Afghan male participants were as (N= 460, M=13.86, SD= 5.94). The overall male of both countries was as (N= 757, M=13.32, SD= 5.21). It means that Afghan male participants were more cyber victimized compared to Indian participants.

Results of Cyber victimization (RCBI-ii) variable on the base of Indian female participants was as (N= 387, M=13.18, SD=4.63) and Afghan female participants were as (N= 240, M=12.65, SD= 5.40). Overall females of both countries were as (N= 627, M=12.97, SD= 4.94). It means that Indian female participants were more cyber victimized compared to Afghan participants.

Results of Cyber victimization (RCBI-ii) variable on the base of Indian both gender participants were as (N= 684, M=12.87, SD= 4.25) and Afghan both gender participants were as (N= 700, M=13.45, SD= 5.79). Overall both countries and gender were as (N= 1384, M=13.16, SD= 5.09). It means the SD of overall Afghan participants was too large. It inferred that the Afghan responses were too varied quite a bit.

Table 22
Two-way ANOVA of cyber victimization (RCBI-II) on the bases of Gender and Countries

Variables	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared/ η_p^2
Gender	21.085	1	21.085	0.822	0.365	0.001
Countries	60.114	1	60.114	2.343	0.126	0.002
Gender*countries	300.334	1	300.334	11.704	0.001	0.008
Error	35411.643	1380	25.661			
Total	275704.000	1384				

R Squared = .012 (Adjusted R Squared = .010)

Table 22 showed the results of the Two Way Independent ANOVA. It showed that there was not a significant main effect of Gender ($F(1,1380) = 0.822, p = 0.365, \eta_p^2 = 0.001$) with males (mean = 13.32; SD = 5.21) and females (mean = 12.97; SD = 4.94).

However, there was not a significant main effect of Countries on Cyber victimization RCBI-II scores ($F(1, 1380) = 2.343, p = 0.126, \eta_p^2 = 0.002$). Participants in Indian condition performed low cyber bullying score (mean = 12.87, SD = 4.25) than those in the Afghanistan condition (mean = 13.45, SD = 5.79). In addition, two variables interaction of gender and countries were found significant ($F(1, 1380) = 11.704, p = 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.008$). It means that the condition of Afghan participants with gender interaction has a significant difference with a medium level of effect or eta square.

Furthermore, a multi-line chart (Figure 19) also proved these findings and suggested that Cyber victimization of Afghan male participants had the highest means score (Mean=13.86; SD=5.94) and the Indian male participants have the lowest mean score for cyber victimization (Mean=12.47; SD=3.66). It means that Afghan male cyber users were the most cyber victim and the Indian male participants become the least cyber victim. On another side, Indian female participants had a high mean score (Mean=13.18; SD=4.63) compared to Afghan female and Indian male participants. It means that Indian females become more cyber victims compared to Indian male and Afghan female participants. Overall, it was inferred that the interaction of two variables (gender and county) on Cyber victimization (RCBI-II) behavior had a medium-level effect, which was significantly important.

Figure 19
A multi-line chart between countries with Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II)

Note: A multi-line chart (Figure 19) depicted the difference between countries' variables with Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II) variable. Afghan males became more cyber victimized (RCBI-II) However, Indian males are the least cyber victimized (RCBI-II). In addition, Indian females were more cyber victimized compared to Afghan female participants.

Table 23
Descriptive Statistics of Cyberbullying (RCBI) on the bases of Gender and Countries

Gender	Country	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	India	2.4218	4.17031	294
	Afghanistan	4.7037	6.84318	459
	Total	3.8127	6.04467	753
Female	India	1.7372	3.70661	392
	Afghanistan	2.6962	6.11061	237
	Total	2.0986	4.77518	629
Both Gender	India	2.0306	3.92379	686
	Afghanistan	4.0201	6.66676	696
	Total	3.0326	5.56728	1382

Table 23 showed the descriptive statistic of the central tendency of Cyberbullying (RCBI) on the bases of Gender (male, female) and country (India, Afghanistan). It computed and summarized the variables such as Cyberbullying (RCBI) via gender and country levels.

Results of Cyberbullying (RCBI) variable on the base of Indian male participants were (N= 294, M=2.42, SD= 4.17) and Afghan male participants were as (N= 459, M=4.70, SD= 6.84). Overall males of both countries were as (N= 753, M=3.81, SD= 6.04). It means that Afghan male participants were more perpetrators compared to Indian participants.

Results of Cyberbullying (RCBI) variable on the base of Indian female participants were (N= 392, M=1.74, SD=3.71) and Afghan female participants were as (N= 237, M=2.69, SD= 6.11). Over females of both countries were as (N= 629, M=2.09, SD= 4.77). It means that Afghan female participants were doing more cyberbullying compare to Indian female participants.

Results of Cyberbullying (RCBI) variable on the base of Indian both gender were as (N= 686, M=2.03, SD= 3.92) and Afghan both gender were as (N= 696, M=4.02, SD= 6.67). Overall both countries and gender were as (N= 1382, M=3.03, SD= 5.57). It means the SD of overall Afghan participants was too large. It inferred that the Afghan responses were too varied quite a bit. Moreover, the mean score of Afghan participants was also larger than Indians, which conveys the message that Afghan participants were doing cyber-bullying activities more than Indians did.

Table 24
Two-way ANOVA of Cyberbullying (RCBI) with Gender and Countries

Variables	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared/ η_p^2
Gender	586.781	1	586.781	19.854	0.000	0.014
Countries	850.446	1	850.446	28.775	0.000	0.020
Gender*countries	141.717	1	141.717	4.795	0.029	0.003
Error	40727.467	1378	29.555			
Total	55513.000	1382				

R Squared = .049 (Adjusted R Squared = .046)

Table 24 showed the results of the Two Way Independent ANOVA. It showed that there was a significant main effect of Gender ($F(1,1378) = 19.854$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.014$) with males (mean = 3.81; SD = 6.04) and females (mean = 2.09; SD = 4.77) with a large level of effect size or eta square.

Moreover, there was a significant main effect of Countries on Cyber victimization RCBI-II scores ($F(1, 1378) = 28.775$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.020$). Participants in Indian condition performed low cyber bullying score (mean = 2.03, SD = 3.92) than those in the Afghanistan condition (mean = 4.02, SD = 6.67) with a large level of effect size. In addition, two variables interaction of gender and countries were also found significant ($F(1, 1378) = 4.795$, $p = 0.029$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.003$). It means that the condition of Afghan participants with gender interaction has a significant difference with a low level of effect size or eta square.

Furthermore, a multi-line chart (Figure 20) also proved these findings and suggested that Cyberbullying (RCBI) of Afghan male participants had the highest means score (Mean=4.02; SD=6.67) and the Indian male participants had the lowest mean score for cyberbullying (Mean=2.03; SD=3.92). It means that Afghan male and female cyber users are the most cyberbullying or cyber perpetrators and the Indian male and female participants become the least cyberbullying. Overall, it was inferred that the interaction of two variables (gender and county) on Cyberbullying (RCBI) behavior had a low-level effect, which was significantly important at 0.05 level.

Figure 20
 A multi-line chart difference between countries and Cyber Bullying (RCBI)

Note: A multi-line chart (Figure 20) depicted the difference between countries' variables with Cyber Bullying (RCBI) variable. In addition, Afghan male participants had the highest score on the Cyberbullying (RCBI) scale and Afghan female participants had higher scores compared to the Indian gender. However, Indian female participants had the least score on cyberbullying (RCBI).

Table 25
Descriptive Statistics of Cyber victimization (RCBI) on bases of Gender and Countries

Gender	Country	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	India	2.4595	5.09952	296
	Afghanistan	5.6529	8.88189	461
	Total	4.4042	7.78330	757
Female	India	1.5919	3.95489	397
	Afghanistan	2.9198	6.23395	237
	Total	2.0883	4.96863	634
Both Gender	India	1.9625	4.49679	693
	Afghanistan	4.7249	8.17923	698
	Total	3.3487	6.74702	1391

Table 25 showed the descriptive statistic of the central tendency of Cyber victimization (RCBI) on the basis of Gender (male, female) and country (India, Afghanistan). It computed and summarized the variables such as Cyber victimization (RCBI) via gender and country levels.

Results of the Cyber victimization (RCBI) variable on the base of Indian male participants were (N= 296, M=2.46, SD= 5.10) and Afghan male participants were as (N= 461, M=5.65, SD= 8.88). The overall male of both countries was as (N= 757, M=4.40, SD= 7.78). It means that Afghan male participants were more cyber victimized compared to Indian participants.

Results of the Cyber victimization (RCBI) variable on the base of Indian female participants were (N= 397, M=1.59, SD=3.95) and Afghan female participants were as (N= 237, M=2.91, SD= 6.23). Overall females of both countries were as (N= 634, M=2.08, SD= 4.97). It means that Indian female participants were less cyber victimized compared to Afghan participants.

Results of Cyber victimization (RCBI) variable on the base of Indian both gender participants were as (N= 693, M=1.96, SD= 4.50) and Afghan both gender participants were as (N= 698, M=4.72, SD= 8.18). Overall both countries and gender were as (N= 1391, M=3.35, SD= 6.75). It means the SD of overall Afghan participants was too large. It inferred that the Afghan responses were too varied quite a bit.

Table 26
Two-way ANOVA of Cyber victimization (RCBI) with Gender and Countries

Variables	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared/ η_p^2
Gender	1055.231	1	1055.231	24.671	0.000	0.017
Countries	1663.919	1	1663.919	38.902	0.000	0.027
Gender*countries	283.283	1	283.283	6.623	0.010	0.005
Error	59325.353	1387	42.772			
Total	78874.000	1391				

R Squared = .062 (Adjusted R Squared = .060)

Table 26 showed the results of the Two Way Independent ANOVA. It showed that there was a significant main effect of Gender ($F(1,1387) = 24.671, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.017$) with males (mean = 4.40; SD = 7.78) and females (mean = 2.09; SD = 4.97) with a large level of effect size.

Similarly, there was a significant main effect of Countries on Cyber victimization RCBI scores ($F(1, 1387) = 38.902, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2 = 0.027$). Participants in India condition performed low cyber victimization score (mean = 1.96, SD = 4.50) than those in the Afghanistan condition (mean = 4.72, SD = 8.18) with a very large effect size. In addition, two variables interaction of gender and countries were also found significant ($F(1, 1387) = 6.623, p = 0.010, \eta_p^2 = 0.005$). It means that the condition of Afghan participants with gender interaction has a significant difference with a medium level of effect size or eta square.

Furthermore, a multi-line chart (Figure 21) also proved these findings and suggested that Cyber victimization of Afghan participants; both male and female, have the highest mean score compared to the Indian participants. It means that Afghan cyber users were the most victimized than the Indian participants. Overall, it was inferred that the interaction of two variables (gender and county) on Cyber victimization (RCBI) behavior had a medium-level effect, which was significantly important.

Figure 21
A multi-line chart difference between countries and Cyber Victimization (RCBI)

Note: A multi-line chart (Figure 21) depicted the difference between countries' variables with Cyber Victimization (RCBI) variable. In addition, Afghan male participants had the highest score on the Cyber victim (RCBI) scale and Afghan female participants had higher scores compared to the Indian gender. However, Indian female participants had the least score on cyber victimization on the RCBI scale.

Hypothesis Four

H₄: There will be a significant difference among the adults belonging to India & Afghanistan concerning their gender on their measures of-

- Ethnocentrism
- Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) and (RCBI)
- Cyber victimization (RCBI-II) and (RCBI)

H₄ was accepted in case of differences between countries' ethnocentrism. However, gender and interaction of gender with countries' ethnocentrism were rejected. Overall, it means that Afghan students' mean score of ethnocentrism was significantly high compared to Indian students.

H₄ was rejected in case of differences between countries' Cyberbullying (RCBI-II). However, H₄ regarding the gender and interaction of gender with countries' Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) was accepted. It means that Afghan male students' mean score of Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) was significantly high compared to Indian students. Moreover, Afghan female students' mean score for Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) is significantly low compared to Indian students.

H₄ was rejected in the case of gender and country conditions with cyber victimization (RCBI-II). However, H₄ regarding the interaction of gender and country was proved and accepted because there was a significant medium level of effect in the condition of interaction with cyber victimization (RCBI-II).

H₄ was accepted in all conditions of Cyberbullying (RCBI). Because Afghan both male and female participants had a significant difference with important effect size compared to Indian gender.

H₄ was accepted in all conditions of Cyber victimization (RCBI). Because male and female participants from Afghanistan had a significant difference with important effect, size compared to Indian gender.

Table 27
Linear regression of Ethnocentrism as predictor of Cyber Bullying (RCBI-II) of Indian Adults

R	R square	Adjusted R ²	Std. error	B	t	F	Level of sig
.052	0.003	0.001	2.91352	0.020	1.335	1.783	.182

Dependent Variable: RCBI-II cyber bullying *Predictors: (Constant), Ethnocentrism*

Table 27 showed a simple linear regression analysis with the entering method that was used to predict cyberbullying (RCBI-II) from ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism behavior explained a non-significant amount of variance in cyberbullying behavior, $F(1,659) = 1.783$, $p = 0.182$, $R^2_{Adjusted} = 0.001$. The regression coefficient ($B = 0.020$) indicated that an increase in one score level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyberbullying score of (0.020) points. In other words, the participants' predicted cyberbullying (RCBI-II) was equal to (+10.988, + 0.020) one-level ethnocentrism.

In simple words, the regression coefficient ($B = 0.02$, $t = 1.335$) indicated that an increase in one level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyberbullying (RCBI-II) score of 0.02 points in a 95% confidence interval. In other words, the participants' predicted ethnocentrism was equal to (constant (+10.988) and unstandardized coefficient Beta (+0.02)) in the ethnocentrism score level. $Y = 10.988 + 0.02 * \text{ethnocentrism score level}$. While ethnocentrism was measured as score level. In other words, participants' cyberbullying behavior (RCBI-II) increases by 0.02 for each ethnocentrism score level.

Furthermore, the Scatterplot (Figure 22) also proved the findings that increasing one level of ethnocentrism in Indian participants did not significantly increase cyberbullying (RCBI-II) behavior. It means that Indian cyber users as bullies had an almost zero association with ethnocentrism.

Figure 22
A Scatterplot between Ethnocentrism and Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) of Indian participants

Note: A Scatterplot (Figure 22) depicted the prediction between the Ethnocentrism variable and the Cyberbullying (RCBI) variable of Indian participants. Furthermore, the scatterplot of equal residuals was also tested. That was not heteroscedasticity. It was homoscedasticity.

Table 28
Indian Adults: Linear regression of Ethnocentrism as a predictor of Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II)

R	R square	Adjusted R ²	Std. error	B	t	F	Level of sig
.026	0.001	-0.001	4.27040	-0.014	-0.658	0.433	.511
<i>Dependent Variable: RCBI-II cyber victimization</i>				<i>Predictors: (Constant), Ethnocentrism</i>			

Table 28 showed a simple linear regression analysis with the entering method that was used to predict cyber victimization (RCBI-II) from ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism behavior explained a non-significant amount of variance in cyber victimization behavior, $F(1,655) = 0.433$, $p = 0.511$, $R^2_{Adjusted} = -0.001$. The regression coefficient ($B = -0.014$) indicated that an increase in one score level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to a decrease in cyber victim score of (0.014) points. In other words, the participants' predicted cyber victimization (RCBI-II) was equal to (+13.346, -0.014) one-level ethnocentrism.

In simple words, the regression coefficient ($B = -0.014$, $t = -1.658$) indicated that an increase in one level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to a decrease in cyber victimization (RCBI-II) score of 0.014 points in a 95% confidence interval. In other words, the participants' predicted ethnocentrism was equal to (constant (+13.346) and unstandardized coefficient Beta (-0.014)) in ethnocentrism score level. $Y = 13.346 + (-0.014) * \text{ethnocentrism score level}$. While ethnocentrism was measured as score level. In other words, participants' cyber victimization behavior (RCBI-II) decreases by 0.014 for each ethnocentrism score level.

Furthermore, the scatter plot (Figure 23) also proved the findings that increasing one level of ethnocentrism of Indian participants did not significantly decrease the cyber victim (RCBI-II) behavior. It means that Indian cyber users as the victims had a non-significant association with ethnocentrism.

Figure 23
A Scatterplot between Ethnocentrism and Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II) of Indian participants

Note: A scatterplot (Figure 23) depicted the prediction between the Ethnocentrism variable and the Cyber Victimization (RCBI) variable of Indian participants.

Table 29
Indian adults: Linear regression of Ethnocentrism as a predictor of Cyberbullying (RCBI)

R	R square	Adjusted R ²	Std. error	B	t	F	Level of sig
.107	0.011	0.010	3.79932	0.055	2.755	7.591	.006

Dependent Variable: cyber bullying (RCBI) Predictors: (Constant), Ethnocentrism

Table 29 showed a simple linear regression analysis with an entry method that was used to predict cyberbullying (RCBI) from ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism behavior explained a significant amount of variance in cyber victimization behavior $F(1,655) = 7.591, p = 0.006, R^2_{Adjusted} = 0.01$. The regression coefficient ($B = 0.055$) indicated that an increase in one level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to a decrease in cyberbullying scores of (0.014) points. In other words, the participants' predicted cyberbullying (RCBI) was equal to (+0.057, +0.055) one level of ethnocentrism.

In simple words, the regression coefficient ($B = 0.055, t = 2.755$) indicated that an increase in one level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyberbullying (RCBI) score of 0.055 points in a 95% confidence interval. In other words, the participants' predicted ethnocentrism was equal to (constant (+0.057) and unstandardized coefficient Beta (+0.055)) in terms of ethnocentrism score level. $Y = 0.057 + 0.055 * \text{ethnocentrism score level}$. While ethnocentrism was measured as score level. In other words, participants' cyberbullying behavior (RCBI) increases by 0.055 for each ethnocentrism score level.

Furthermore, the scatter plot (Figure 24) also proved the findings that increasing one level of ethnocentrism in Indian participants significantly decreases cyberbullying (RCBI) behavior. It means that Indian cyber users as perpetrators had significant associations with ethnocentrism.

Figure 24
The Scatterplot between Ethnocentrism and Cyberbullying (RCBI) of Indian participants

Note: The Scatterplot (Figure 24) depicted the prediction between the Ethnocentrism variable with Cyber bullying (RCBI) variable of Indian participants.

Table 30
Indian Adults: Linear regression of Ethnocentrism as a predictor of Cyber Victimization (RCBI)

R	R square	Adjusted R ²	Std. error	B	t	F	Level of sig
.068	0.005	0.003	4.46948	0.041	1.744	3.040	.082

Dependent Variable: cyber victimization (RCBI) Predictors: (Constant), Ethnocentrism

Table 30 showed a simple linear regression analysis with an entry method that was used to predict cyber victimization (RCBI) from ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism

behavior explained a non-significant amount of variance in cyber victimization behavior, $F(1,661) = 3.040$, $p = 0.082$, $R^2_{Adjusted} = 0.003$. The regression coefficient ($B = 0.068$) indicated that an increase in one level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to a decrease in cyber victim score of (0.041) points. In other words, the participants' predicted cyberbullying (RCBI) was equal to (+0.531, +0.041) one level of ethnocentrism.

In simple words, the regression coefficient ($B = 0.041$, $t = 1.744$) indicated that an increase in one level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyber victimization (RCBI) score of 0.041 points in 95% confidence interval. In other words, the participants' predicted ethnocentrism was equal to (constant (+0.531) and Unstandardized coefficient Beta (+0.041)) in to ethnocentrism score level. $Y = 0.531 + 0.041 * \text{ethnocentrism score level}$. While ethnocentrism was measured as a score level. In other words, participants' cyber victimization behavior (RCBI) increases by 0.041 for each ethnocentrism score level.

Furthermore, the scatter plot (Figure 25) also proved the findings that increasing one level of ethnocentrism of Indian participants did not significantly increase the cyber victim (RCBI) behavior. It means that Indian cyber users as victims had no significant association with ethnocentrism.

Figure 25
The Scatterplot between Ethnocentrism and Cyber Victimization (RCBI) of Indian participants

Note: The scatterplot (Figure 25) depicted the prediction between the Ethnocentrism variable and the Cyber Victimization (RCBI) variable of Indian participants. The scatterplot equal residuals. So this is not heteroscedasticity. It is homoscedasticity.

Hypothesis Five

H₅: There will be a significant predictive role of ethnocentrism on cyberbullying and cyber victimization of Indian adults.

The H₅ was rejected in the case of ethnocentrism's significant effect on cyberbullying (RCBI-II). The results proved that the ethnocentrism of Indian

participants did not have a significant contribution to cyberbullying (RCBI-II) at a 0.05 level of significance.

The H₅ was rejected in the case of ethnocentrism's significant effect on cyber victimization (RCBI-II). The results proved that the ethnocentrism of Indian participants did not have a significant contribution to the cyber victim (RCBI-II) at a 0.05 level of significance. Even though increasing one level of ethnocentrism decreases 0.014 points for the cyber victim (RCBI-II), it may be due to a chance.

The H₅ was accepted in the case of ethnocentrism for its significant effect on cyberbullying (RCBI). The results proved that ethnocentrism of Indian participants had a significant predicted cyberbullying (RCBI) at a 0.01 level of significance. On one measure of ethnocentrism, it increased by 0.055 points of cyberbullying (RCBI).

The H₅ was rejected in the case of ethnocentrism's significant effect on cyber victimization (RCBI). The results proved that the ethnocentrism of Indian participants did not have a significant contribution to the cyber victim (RCBI) at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 31
Afghan Adults: Linear Regression of Ethnocentrism as a predictor of Cyberbullying (RCBI-II)

R	R square	Adjusted R ²	Std. error	B	t	F	Level of sig
.138	0.019	0.018	4.26477	0.067	3.663	13.417	.000

Dependent Variable: Cyberbullying (RCBI) Predictors: (Constant), Ethnocentrism

Table 31 showed a simple linear regression analysis with the entering method that was used to predict cyberbullying (RCBI) from ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism behavior explained a significant amount of variance in cyberbullying behavior, $F(1,688) = 13.417, p < 0.001, R^2_{Adjusted} = 0.018$. The regression coefficient ($B = 0.067$) indicated that an increase in one score level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyberbullying score of (0.067) points. In other words, the participants' predicted cyberbullying (RCBI-II) was equal to (+9.601, +0.067) one-level ethnocentrism.

In simple words, *the regression coefficient* ($B = 0.067$, $t = 3.663$) indicated that an increase in one level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyberbullying (RCBI-II) score of 0.067 points in a 95% confidence interval. In other words, the participants' predicted ethnocentrism was equal to (constant (+9.601) and unstandardized coefficient Beta (+0.067)) in the ethnocentrism score level. $Y=9.601+0.067*\text{ethnocentrism score level}$. While ethnocentrism was measured as a score level. In other words, participants' cyberbullying behavior (RCBI-II) increases by 0.067 for each ethnocentrism score level.

Furthermore, the scatter plot (Figure 26) also proved the findings that increasing one level of ethnocentrism in participants from Afghanistan had significantly increased cyberbullying (RCBI) behavior. It means that Afghan cyber users as perpetrators had a significant association with ethnocentrism.

Figure 26
A Scatterplot between Ethnocentrism and Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) of Afghan Participants

Note: The scatterplot (Figure 26) depicted the prediction between the Ethnocentrism variable and the Cyberbullying (RCBI) variable of Afghan participants.

Table 32
Afghan Adults: Linear regression of Ethnocentrism as a predictor of Cyber Victimization (RCBI-II)

R	R square	Adjusted R ²	Std. error	B	t	F	Level of sig
.044	0.002	0.000	5.79630	0.028	1.155	1.334	.249

Dependent Variable: cyber victimization (RCBI) Predictors: (Constant), Ethnocentrism

Table 32 showed a simple linear regression analysis with the entering method that was used to predict cyber victims (RCBI) from ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism

behavior explained not a significant amount of variance in Cyber victim behavior, $F(1,695) = 1.334$, $p = 0.249$, $R^2_{Adjusted} < 0.001$. The regression coefficient ($B = 0.028$) indicated that an increase in one score level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in Cyber victim score of (0.028) points. In other words, the participants' predicted cyber victim (RCBI-II) was equal to (+12.422, +0.028) one level of ethnocentrism.

In simple words, the regression coefficient ($B = 0.028$, $t = 1.155$) indicated that an increase in one level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyber victimization (RCBI-II) score of 0.02 points in a 95% confidence interval. In other words, the participants' predicted ethnocentrism was equal to (constant (+10.988) and the unstandardized coefficient Beta (+0.028)) in the ethnocentrism score level. $Y = 12.422 + 0.028 * \text{ethnocentrism score level}$. While ethnocentrism was measured as score level. In other words, participants' cyber victimization behavior (RCBI-II) increases by 0.028 for each ethnocentrism score level.

Furthermore, the scatter plot (Figure 27) also proved the findings that increasing one level of ethnocentrism in Afghan participants did not significantly increase cyberbullying (RCBI-II) behavior.

Figure 27
The Scatterplot between Ethnocentrism and Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) of Afghan participants

Note: The scatterplot (Figure 27) depicted the prediction between the Ethnocentrism variable and the Cyberbullying (RCBI-II) variable of Afghan participants.

Table 33
Afghan Adults: Linear Regression of Ethnocentrism as a predictor of Cyberbullying (RCBI)

R	R square	Adjusted R ²	Std. error	B	t	F	Level of sig
.122	0.015	0.013	6.63450	0.091	1.155	10.386	.001

Dependent Variable: cyber victimization (RCBI-II) Predictors: (Constant), Ethnocentrism

Table 33 showed a simple linear regression analysis with the entering method that was used to predict cyberbullying (RCBI) from ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism

behavior explained a significant amount of variance in cyberbullying behavior, $F(1,691) = 13.417$, $p = 0.001$, $R^2_{Adjusted} = 10.386$. The regression coefficient ($B = 0.091$) indicated that an increase in one score level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyberbullying score of (0.091) points. In other words, the participants' predicted cyberbullying (RCBI) was equal to (+0.716, + 0.091) one-level ethnocentrism.

In simple words, the regression coefficient ($B = 0.091$, $t = 1.155$) indicated that an increase in one level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyberbullying (RCBI) score of 0.091 points in a 95% confidence interval. In other words, the participants' predicted ethnocentrism was equal to (constant (+0.716) and unstandardized coefficient Beta (+0.091)) in the ethnocentrism score level. $Y = 0.716 + 0.091 * \text{ethnocentrism score level}$. While ethnocentrism was measured as a score level. In other words, participants' cyberbullying behavior (RCBI) increases by 0.091 for each ethnocentrism score level.

Furthermore, the scatter plot (Figure 28) also proved the findings that increasing one level of ethnocentrism in participants from Afghanistan had significantly increased cyberbullying (RCBI) behavior. It means that Afghan cyber users as perpetrators had a significant association with ethnocentrism.

Figure 28
A Scatterplot between Ethnocentrism and Cyberbullying (RCBI) of Afghan Participants

Note: The scatterplot (Figure 28) depicted the prediction between the Ethnocentrism variable and the Cyberbullying (RCBI) variable of Afghan participants.

Table 34
Afghan Adults: Linear Regression of Ethnocentrism as a predictor of Cyber Victimization (RCBI)

R	R square	Adjusted R ²	Std. error	B	t	F	Level of sig
.097	0.009	0.008	8.16543	0.089	2.561	6.558	.011

Dependent Variable: cyber victimization (RCBI) Predictors: (Constant), Ethnocentrism

Table 34 showed a simple linear regression analysis with the entering method that was used to predict cyber victims (RCBI) from ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism behavior explained a significant amount of variance in cyberbullying behavior, F(1,692

=6.558, $p=0.011$, $R^2_{Adjusted}=0.018$. The regression coefficient ($B=0.089$) indicated that an increase in one score level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyber victim score of (0.089) points. In other words, the participants' predicted cyberbullying (RCBI) was equal to (+1.499, +0.089) one level of ethnocentrism.

In simple words, the regression coefficient ($B=.089$, $t=2.561$) indicated that an increase in one level of ethnocentrism corresponded, on average, to an increase in cyber victimization (RCBI) score of 0.02 points in a 95% confidence interval. In other words, the participants' predicted ethnocentrism was equal to (constant (+1.499) and Unstandardized coefficient Beta (+0.089)) in ethnocentrism score level. $Y = 1.499+0.089*\text{ethnocentrism score level}$. While ethnocentrism was measured as a score level. In other words, participants' cyber victimization behavior (RCBI) increases by 0.02 for each ethnocentrism score level.

Furthermore, the scatter plot (Figure 29) also proved the findings that increasing one level of ethnocentrism of participants from Afghanistan had significantly increased cyber victim (RCBI) behavior. It means that Afghan cyber users as the victim had a significant association with ethnocentrism.

Figure 29
A Scatterplot between Ethnocentrism and Cyber Victims (RCBI) of Afghan participants

Note: The scatterplot (Figure 29) depicted the prediction between the Ethnocentrism variable and the Cyber Victim (RCBI) variable of Afghan participants.

Hypothesis Six

H₆: There will be a significant predictive role of ethnocentrism on cyberbullying and cyber victimization of Afghan adults.

The H₆ was accepted in the case of ethnocentrism and significant effect on cyberbullying (RCBI-II). The results proved that ethnocentrism of participants from Afghanistan had a significant predicted cyberbullying (RCBI-II) at a 0.001 level of

significance. On one score of ethnocentrism, it increased by 0.067 points in cyberbullying (RCBI-II).

The H₆ was rejected in the case of ethnocentrism because of its significant effect on cyber victimization (RCBI-II). The results proved that the ethnocentrism of Afghan participants did not have a significant contribution to cyber victims (RCBI-II) at a 0.05 level of significance. Even though increasing one level of ethnocentrism increases 0.028 points as a cyber victim (RCBI-II), it may be due to a chance.

The H₆ was accepted in the case of ethnocentrism for its significant effect on cyberbullying (RCBI). The results proved that the ethnocentrism of participants from Afghanistan had a significant predicted cyberbullying (RCBI) at a 0.01 level of significance. On one score of ethnocentrism, it increased by 0.091 points in cyberbullying (RCBI).

The H₆ was accepted in the case of ethnocentrism for its significant effect on cyber victimization (RCBI). The results proved that the ethnocentrism of participants from Afghanistan had a significant predicted cyber victims (RCBI) at a 0.05 level of significance. On one measure of ethnocentrism, it increased by 0.089 points in cyber victimization (RCBI).

4.3 Discussion

The relationships between age and ethnocentrism, cyberbullying on the RCBI and RCBI-II scales, and cyber victimization on the RCBI-II scale factors were almost nil. However, there is just one instance of age and cyber victimization on the RCBI scale that demonstrated a significant relationship at the 0.05 level of significance.

Moreover, P. K. Smith et al. (2014) conducted data from the United Kingdom and also reported that particularly females aged 11 to 16 are sexually cyber victimized significantly differently from males of the same age group. Furthermore, Hashemi (2021) added that internet users of different age groups in Afghanistan have a significantly positive correlation between cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior.

Similarly, Chandra (2018) also discovered that cyberbullying and cyber victimization took place among different age groups and genders of internet users. Parks (2013) found that youngsters use cyberbullying behavior against one another. Even though it takes place in every stage of life and doesn't have any age limit (Minor et al., 2014). Safaria (2016) discovered that the majority of children every day either do cyberbullying or are victims of cyber activities with psychological effects.

On the other hand, Rafi (2019) remarked that an increase in the age of the participants has a negative relationship with cyberbullying and cyber victimization. In other words, an increase in the age of the participants significantly decreased cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior.

However, Khawrin et al. (2021a) noted that the age variable of Afghan participants has no significant correlation between cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior. They added that the gender of the participants made a significant difference in cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior. It must be clear that male participants had more cyber perpetrator and cyber victim behavior compared to Afghan female participants. Furthermore, Khawrin et al. (2022b) discovered every hour of internet browsing had a significant impact on cyberbullying and cyber victimization. However, there was no significant relationship between age and education level, and age with cyberbullying and cyber victimization behavior among Ahmedabad participants.

Cyberbullying behavior on the RCBI and RCBI-II Scales, and cyber victims on the RCBI Scale exhibited a significant relationship with the ethnocentrism variable at the 0.01 level of significance. However, cyber victimization behavior on the RCBI-II scale and the ethnocentrism variable did not have any significant relationship. Furthermore, Khawrin (2021) statistical analysis demonstrated that ethnocentrism behavior considerably exacerbated problems between the ethnic and outside groups. Additionally, he demonstrated through cyberbullying and cyber victimization that ethnocentrism has a statistically significant positive link with Afghan nationals online. In addition, he demonstrated that ethnic chauvinism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization were unaffected by Afghan gender, age, or other variables. However, another study used ethnocentrism to demonstrate that there were no appreciable differences among the Afghan ethnic groups, including Pashtun, Tajik, Hazara, and

other minorities. Additionally, it was discovered that internet use had a favorable and substantial connection with victimization and cyberbullying (Khawrin et al., 2021b).

There was a significant correlation between cyberbullying behavior on the RCBI-II scale and a cyber victim on the RCBI-II scale. Similarly, cyberbullying behavior on the RCBI scale and cyber victim behavior on the RCBI scale also had a significant relationship at the 0.01 level of significance. There is a considerable positive direct association between cyberbullying and cyber victimization. Additionally, there is a strong direct connection between cyberbullying behavior and anger (Dalla Pozza et al., 2016).

On measuring scales of ethnocentrism, cyberbullying, and cyber victimization, Afghan participants scored significantly higher than Indian participants, according to statistical data. Additionally, the variables for ethnocentrism, cyberbullying activity on the RCBI scale, cyber victimization behavior on the RCBI scale, and the RCBI-II scale were statistically distinct from one another, except for cyberbullying behavior on the RCBI-II scale was shown similarly. According to the RCBI-II scale, all individuals from both nations exhibited almost equal cyberbullying behaviors.

The ethnocentrism, cyberbullying conducted on the RCBI-II and RCBI scales, and cyber victim behavior on the RCBI scale were significantly different between male and female participants. However, cyber victimization behavior on the RCBI-II scale did not alter substantially from the baseline. In other words, compared to female participants, men were statistically more likely to engage in cyberbullying, cyber victimization, and ethnocentric behaviors. According to cyberbullying behavior on the RCBI-II scale of Indians and Afghans with gender interaction, statistically proved that Afghan male participants exhibited significantly greater cyberbullying behavior on the RCBI-II scale than Indian and Afghan female participants. However, as compared to Indian gender and Afghan male participants, Afghan female participants showed the lowest levels of cyberbullying behavior on the RCBI-II scale. In addition, Indian males are the least likely to have been victimized online compared to Afghan male participants. Furthermore, compared to Afghan female participants, Indian females were more frequently cyber-victimized. It is worth noting that on the Cyberbullying (RCBI) scale, Afghan male participants scored the highest, and Afghan female participants scored higher than the Indian gender. The participants from India, however,

scored the lowest on cyberbullying (RCBI). In other words, on the Cyber Victim (RCBI) scale, Afghan male participants scored the highest, and Afghan female participants scored higher than Indian male participants did. On the RCBI scale, however, the Indian female participants received the lowest scores for cyber victimization. The gender interaction of the ethnocentrism behaviors of India and Afghanistan revealed that both male and female Afghans exhibit significantly higher degrees of ethnocentrism scores than the Indian gender.

Furthermore, some authors, like Chandra (2018), Tiffany (2018), and Muhammad Shaban Rafi (2019), also noticed that gender variables have a significant difference with cyber bullying and cyber victim behavior. In other words, female participants were cyber-victimized more than male participants. According to Shaban Rafi (2019), victimization and cyberbullying decline as the average age rises. It indicates a considerable negative relationship between these two variables. Additionally, the author stated that the participants' gender did not significantly affect the prevalence of cyberbullying or cyber victim behavior.

However, Shaban Rafi (2019) argued that the gender of the participants did not have any significant difference between cyberbullying and cyber victimization. Patchin & Hinduja (2008) also showed that gender was not related to cyber victimization or cyberbullying.

Bullying has existed in several Indian cultures. Even though ragging is frequently used to refer to bullying in schools and colleges. Technology misuse and abuse, including instances of cyberbullying among Indian college students, have been well-documented, and use tools like the internet and mobile phones.

Cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale had less of an impact on the ethnocentrism of Indian individuals. Additionally, ethnocentrism behavior did not significantly change the behavior of cyber victims on the RCBI-II scale. On the contrary, on the RCBI scale, cyberbullying was highly impacted by the ethnocentrism of Indian individuals. However, ethnocentrism did not have a significant impact on cyber victim behavior on the RCBI scale.

Similarly, some authors document that Indian youngsters have the third highest level of cyber victimization and cyberbullying behavior around the globe (Wright et al., 2015). In addition, to that half of the youngsters are involved in this behavior (Chandra,

2018). Furthermore, Sivakumar (2013) also cited that just in the last six months, 57% of the participants reported being involved in cyberbullying and victim behavior.

Ethnocentrism among participants from Afghanistan had a significant impact on cyberbullying behavior on the RCBI-II scale. Additionally, add 0.067 points of cyberbullying to every point of ethnocentrism. However, it did not significantly alter the behavior of the cyber victim (RCBI-II). Furthermore, the ethnocentrism of the participants from Afghanistan had a significant impact on cyberbullying on the RCBI scale also. For instance, one point of ethnocentrism causes cyberbullying (RCBI) to rise by 0.091 points. Ethnocentrism behavior also had a considerable impact on how cyber victims behaved on the RCBI scale. For instance, a rise of 0.089 points in cyber victimization (RCBI) for every point of ethnocentrism. Furthermore, Hashemi (2021) added that Afghan participants are significantly influenced by multiple factors; age and gender; misuse of cyberspace and involvement in cyber unethical activities.

Chapter V

Summary, Conclusion, Suggestions, Limitations, and Implications

5

5.0 Introduction

5.1 Summary

5.2 Conclusion

5.3 Suggestions

5.4 Limitations

5.5 Implications

5.0 Introduction

This chapter included a summary of the research, which relived the all result in the short form. Conclusion of this research relived all the descriptive and inferential statistics summation of the study. Implication of this study was also highlighted for the practical field works of criminal, social, and counseling psychologist and students. In addition, finally, suggestions were made for Indian and Afghan society. It is worth noting to mention that the limitations of the study was also written.

5.1 Summary

It is summed up below.

5.1.1 Descriptive Analysis

- Age: The mean age was 21.65 years, with a mode of 21 years and a median age of 21 years. Ages ranged from 17 to 30 years.
- Gender: There were 772 males and 644 females participated in this study. There were 43.1% of Indian males and 56.9% of Indian females. Moreover, there were 65.9% of Afghan males and 34.1% of Afghan females.
- Country: Indian participants were 707 and Afghans were 709 selected on the bases of inclusion area for this study, making a total of 1416 participants.
- Internet usage per day: Indian students were using the internet per day for 3.58 hours on average, and Afghan students were using it for 3.17 hours per day.
- Indian caste consist of General/Open category (G/OC) 55.3%, Scheduled Tribe (ST) 9.5%, Scheduled Extremely Backward Caste (SEBC), 20.2%, Scheduled Caste (SC) 8.2%, Other Backward Caste (OBC) 5.4%, and Economically Weaker Section (EWS) 1.4%. Furthermore, the Afghan tribe consist of Pashtun 30.2%, Tajik 34.7%, Hazara 29.8%, Baloch 0.3%, Uzbek 1.0%, Bayat 0.8%, Sadat 2.4%, and Qazalbash 0.8%, participated in the study.
- Cyberbully and cyber victim: Indian cyber victims were 23.38%, perpetrators were 8.6%, and bystanders were 67.98%. Moreover, Afghan cyber victims were 25%, perpetrators were 15.37%, and bystanders were 59.58%.

5.1.2 Inferential Analysis

It is as below:

5.1.2.1 Correlational analysis

- The ethnocentrism variable of the participants did have a significant association with all variables such as cyber bullying (RCBI) and (RCBI-II) and cyber victimization (RCBI) except cyber victimization on the RCBI-II scale.
- There was not a significant correlation between the variable of age and other variables such as ethnocentrism, cyber bullying (RCBI) and (RCBI-II) and cyber victimization (RCBI-II). However, there was only one case of age with a cyber-victim on the RCBI scale had significant correlation.
- The ethnocentrism variable had significant correlation with cyberbullying on the RCBI-II scale, cyberbullying on the RCBI scale, and cyber victims on the RCBI scale. However, just cyber victims on the RCBI-II scale did not have a significant association with ethnocentrism.

5.1.2.2 T-test analysis

- The difference between India and Afghanistan on ethnocentrism, Cyber Victim (RCBI-II), Cyberbullying (RCBI), and Cyber Victim (RCBI) was examined. In all cases except cyberbullying (RCBI-II), Afghan students were significantly different compared to Indian students.
- The difference between gender and ethnocentrism, cyberbullying (RCBI-II), cyberbullying (RCBI), and cyber victimization (RCBI) also examined. Except for cyber victims (RCBI-II), male students were significantly different compared to female students in all cases.
- The difference between countries' ethnocentrism was also tested. Afghan students' mean score of ethnocentrism was significantly higher compared to Indian participants.
- The difference between countries' cyberbullying (RCBI-II) proved that Afghan male participants' mean score of cyberbullying (RCBI-II) is significantly high compared to Indian students. Moreover, Afghan female students' mean score for cyberbullying (RCBI-II) is significantly lower compared to Indian female students.

5.1.2.3 Two-way ANOVA analysis

- Gender and country conditions of cyber victimization (RCBI-II) tested. The interaction between gender and country proved and accepted because there was a significant medium level of effect in the condition of interaction with cyber victimization (RCBI-II).
- The adults of India and Afghanistan concerning their gender on the measure of ethnocentrism did not have significant interaction.
- The interaction of gender with India & Afghanistan participants' cyberbullying (RCBI-II) was significant. It means that Afghan male students' mean score of cyberbullying (RCBI-II) was significantly higher compared to Indian students. Moreover, Afghan female students' mean score for cyberbullying (RCBI-II) was significantly lower compared to Indian students.
- The interaction of gender and country on cyber victimization (RCBI-II) was significant. It had a medium level of effect in the condition of interaction with cyber victimization (RCBI-II).
- All conditions of cyberbullying (RCBI) with gender and country were significant. Because Afghan male and female participants had a significant difference with a significant effect, size compared to Indian participants and gender condition.
- All conditions of cyber victimization (RCBI) with gender and countries were significant. Because male and female participants from Afghanistan had a significant difference with a significant effect, size compared to the Indian gender.

5.1.2.4 Liner Regression analysis

- The results proved that the ethnocentrism of Indian participants did not have a significant contribution to cyberbullying (RCBI-II) and cyber victims (RCBI-II) at a 0.05 level of significance. Similarly, the ethnocentrism of Indian participants did not have a significant contribution to the cyber victim (RCBI) at 0.05 level of significance. However, the ethnocentrism behavior of Indian participants had significantly predicted cyberbullying (RCBI) at a 0.01 level of significance. It means that on one measure of ethnocentrism, it increased by 0.055 points of cyberbullying (RCBI) behavior.

- The results found that ethnocentrism of participants from Afghanistan had a significant predicted cyberbullying (RCBI-II) at a 0.001 level of significance. It means one score of ethnocentrism, increased by 0.067 points in cyberbullying (RCBI-II) behavior. However, the results proved that the ethnocentrism of Afghan participants did not have a significant contribution to cyber victims (RCBI-II) at a 0.05 level of significance.
- It was statistically proved that the ethnocentrism of participants from Afghanistan had a significant predicted cyberbullying (RCBI) at a 0.01 level of significance. It means one score of ethnocentrism, increased by 0.091 points in cyberbullying (RCBI) behavior. Similarly, the ethnocentrism of participants from Afghanistan significantly predicted cyber victims (RCBI) behavior at a 0.05 level of significance. It means one measure of ethnocentrism, increased by 0.089 points in cyber victimization (RCBI) behavior of the participants.

5.2 Conclusion

The cross-cultural study showed that the adults of Afghanistan and India were significantly different at the levels of ethnocentrism, cyber bullying and cyber victimization behavior. Furthermore, the interaction of gender with Afghanistan participants' cyberbullying and cyber victim behavior on (RCBI-II) was significantly different from Indian participants. Consequently, the ethnocentrism behavior of Indian participants significantly predicted cyberbullying (RCBI) at a 0.01 level of significance. The results found that Afghanistan participants' ethnocentrism significantly predicted cyberbullying (RCBI-II) and cyberbullying and cyber victim (RCBI) behavior.

5.3 Suggestions

- Afghan and Indian legal authorities must make specific laws and regulations to protect and prevent any kind of cyberbullying behavior that triggers other bad consequences.
- Academicians and researchers are highly advised to do more research in this field of ethnocentrism and cyberbullying, which could clear the path for legal authorities, academicians, and non-academic organizations.

- Furthermore, mix method research is needed via qualitative and quantitative research, to explore ethnocentrism and to provide all its bad consequences and its formation of it. This will provide a controlling factor for the manipulation and change it to its positive goals.
- Every citizen have to take preventive and legal measures.
- Launching awareness programs on different platforms such as media, marches, conferences, etc.
- Teaching the new culture of other societies helps one another understand one another's priorities and necessities.
- Cyberbullying behavior could be reduced and avoided by showing and proving its bad consequences to civilians, organizational stakeholders, and students.
- It is necessary for colleges and universities to establish rules and standards for dealing with professors, colleagues, and class fellows who are cyberbullied by students has been noted.
- Anti-bullying sites, anti-ethnocentrism campaigns, and support groups for families are highly advised.
- The psychological counselor must include anti-cyberbullying behavior and ethnocentric behavior and facilitate the victims.
- Social awareness programs are also needed to make youth aware of the risks of cyberbullying behavior.
- India and specifically Afghanistan should make anti-cyber ragging rules and regulations, which could root out the current conundrum.
- User-friendly Cyber rights information should be available to all. However, these internet users understand his and other rights. This will also serve as a notification to prevent them from internet misuse.
- The solutions provided in the research and which the respondents endorsed should be considered.
- Bystanders should intervene to protect the cyber victim and prevent cyber bullying, and inform the related organization.
- This research suggest new emerging academic subjects such as cyber psychology and cyber behavior in cyberspace.

5.4 Limitations

The research had very few resources, which could not provide more data from all parts of both countries, India and Afghanistan. Furthermore, Afghanistan's security conditions were not normal at the time of my data collation for collecting data from the whole country. Moreover, students were included because of the limited time and resources. The data was collected only on quantitative method. Therefore, for better understanding a mix method research is needed which explain the cause and relationship of the ethnocentrism with cyberbullying behavior.

5.5 Implications

The results of the current study are used to improve the psychological knowledge of internet users. Law enforcement agencies, lawmakers, clinical psychologists, counseling psychologists, forensic psychologists, and criminal psychologists can all benefit from it. The study emphasizes the value of this area of research in understanding deviant cyber behavior. Additionally, it benefits the community and society as a whole. Some practical examples from the different areas are discussed below.

Criminal psychology, crime triggering in cyberspace, cyber-psychological crime prevention, and curation are identified as aspects of the new cyber generation. This study helps criminal psychology to identify the trigger behavior that lasts to the crime, it also identifies the anti-social behavior in cyberspace, even though ethnocentrism is a kind of influence factor in cyber behavior in the generation of cyberspace.

Forensic psychology, judges, courts, lawyers, prosecutors, police, and intelligence organizations prove that cyber-generation criminal and harmful behavior is a new challenge to the attorney, police, and prosecution. This study is a source for the judges and law enforcement to explicate factors of anti-normal cyber behavior. Moreover, this study is applicable to facilitate and improve the cyber-judicial system.

This research provides a foundation for new emerging academic subjects such as cyber psychology and cyber behavior in cyberspace, as well as an academic topic as

a department that is critical for cyber police, the identification of normal and abnormal cyber behavior.

References

- Aboujaoude, E., Savage, M. W., Starcevic, V., & Salame, W. O. (2015). Cyberbullying: Review of an old problem gone viral. In *Journal of Adolescent Health* (Vol. 57, Issue 1, pp. 10–18). Elsevier USA. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2015.04.011>
- Abu Bakar, H. S., Yusof, N., & Budiman, A. M. (2013). The Paradigm Model of Cyberbullying Phenomenon. *International Journal on Media & Communications (JMC)*, 1(1), 98–112. <https://doi.org/10.5176/2335-6618>
- Agustina, J. R. (2015). Understanding cyber victimization: Digital architectures and the disinhibition effect. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 9(1), 35–54. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.22239>
- Akrim, A., & Sulasmi, E. (2020). Talent Development & Excellence Student Perception of Cyberbullying in Social Media. *Talent Development and Excellence*, 12(1), 322–333. <http://www.iratde.com>
- Ali, F. (2015). Afghanistan: the rise of ethnic consciousness through history. *Open Access Repository*, 1–12. <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar-438323>
- Allen, N. W., & Barter, S. J. (2016). Ummah or tribe? Islamic practice, political ethnocentrism, and political attitudes in Indonesia. *Asian Journal of Political Science*, 25(1), 45–67. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02185377.2016.1245153>
- Arora, S. K. (2020). Cyberbullying Laws in India. *International Journal of Law Management & Humanities*, 3(6), 351–360. <https://doi.org/10.1732/IJLMH.25115>
- Axelrod, R., & Hammond, R. A. (2003). The Evolution of Ethnocentric Behavior. *Midwest Political Science Convention*, 2, 1–30.
- Ayyub, R. (2019). *Religious Hate Crimes in India Surge in Modi's Second Term* | Time. Time. <https://time.com/5617161/india-religious-hate-crimes-modi/>
- Barlett, C., & Coyne, S. M. (2014). A meta-analysis of sex differences in cyber-bullying behavior: The moderating role of age. *Aggressive Behavior*, 40(5), 474–488. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ab.21555>
- Barlett, C. P., Madison, C. S., Heath, J. B., & DeWitt, C. C. (2019). Please browse responsibly: A correlational examination of technology access and time spent online in the Barlett Gentile Cyberbullying Model. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 92, 250–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.11.013>
- Barón, J. O., Postigo, J., Iranzo, B., Buelga, S., & Carrascosa, L. (2018). Parental communication and feelings of affiliation in adolescent aggressors and victims of cyberbullying. *Social Sciences*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci8010003>
- Basu, A., Mukherjee, N., Roy, S., Sengupta, S., Banerjee, S., Chakraborty, M., Dey, B., Roy, M., Roy, B., Bhattacharyya, N. P., Roychoudhury, S., & Majumder, P. P. (2003). Ethnic India: A genomic view, with special reference to peopling and structure. *Genome Research*, 13(10), 2277–2290. <https://doi.org/10.1101/gr.1413403>
- Bauman, S. (2007). Cyberbullying. a Virtual Menace. *The National Coalition Against Bullying National Conference*, 1–23.
- Bendiksen, R., Field, D., Hockey, J., & Small, N. (1999). Death, Gender and Ethnicity. In

- Contemporary Sociology* (Vol. 28, Issue 2). <https://doi.org/10.2307/2654907>
- Beran, T., Mishna, F., McInroy, L. B., & Shariff, S. (2015). Children's Experiences of Cyberbullying: A Canadian National Study. *Children and Schools*, 37(4), 207–214. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cs/cdv024>
- Betts, L. R., & Spenser, K. A. (2017). Developing the Cyber Victimization Experiences and Cyberbullying Behaviors Scales. *Journal of Genetic Psychology*, 178(3), 42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221325.2017.1295222>
- Bhatia, N. (2022). *CYBER B.A.A.P. – Cyber Bullying, Awareness, Action and Prevention*. CYBER B.A.A.P. <https://www.cyberbaap.org/>
- Birkbeck, C. (1993). Against ethnocentrism: A cross-cultural perspective on criminal justice theories and policies. *Journal of Criminal Justice Education*, 4(2), 307–323. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511259300086161>
- Bizumic, B. (2014). Who coined the concept of ethnocentrism? A brief report. *Journal of Social and Political Psychology*, 2(1), 3–10. <https://doi.org/10.5964/jspp.v2i1.264>
- Bizumic, B. (2015a). Ethnocentrism. *Brill Academic Publishers*, 1, 533–539.
- Bizumic, B. (2015b). Ethnocentrism and Prejudice: History of the Concepts. In *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences: Second Edition* (Second Edi, Issue March). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.03153-6>
- Bizumic, B., & Duckitt, J. (2012). What Is and Is Not Ethnocentrism? A Conceptual Analysis and Political Implications. *Political Psychology*, 33(6), 887–909. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j>
- Bizumic, B., & Sheppard, H. (2021). A Political Psychology of Ethnocentrism. In *The Cambridge Handbook of Political Psychology* (Issue March, p. 31). Cambridge University Press.
- Black, M. P. (2014). *Cyberbullying , Bullying , and Victimization among Adolescents : Rates of Occurrence , Internet Use and Relationship to Parenting Styles*. https://trace.tennessee.edu/utk_graddiss/2803
- Bolaffi, G., Bracalenti, R., Braham, P., & Gindro, S. (2003). Dictionary of Race , Ethnicity & Culture. In *Athenaeum Studi Periodici Di Letteratura E Storia Dell Antichita*.
- Borden, A. W. (2007). The Impact of Service-Learning on Ethnocentrism in an Intercultural Communication Course. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 30(2), 171–183. <https://doi.org/10.1177/105382590703000206>
- Braithwaite, J. (2022). *Macrocriminology and Freedom* (Australian). Anu press. <https://doi.org/10.22459/MF.2021>
- Campbell, M. (2010). Research on Cyberbullying. In *Australian Journal of Guidance and Counselling* (Vol. 20, pp. 129–242).
- Campfield, D. C. (2008). *Cyber bullying and victimization: Psychosocial characteristics of bullies, victims, and bully/victims*. <https://scholarworks.umt.edu/etd/288>
- Canter, D. (2012). Criminal psychology. In *Hodder Education*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203721902>
- Chandra, R. (2018). Cyberbullying and Indian legal regime: an overview. *Creative Cunnect International Puablisher Group*, 4(July), 137–158.
- Chow, J. (2015). *Ethnocentrism and Rhetorical Sensitivity in the New Media Age: A Case*

Study of Bangkok University Students [Bangkok University].
<http://dspace.bu.ac.th/handle/123456789/1282>

- Chowdhury, R. G. (2014). A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF LEADERSHIP STYLES ON EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION AND COMMITMENT : AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF SELECTED IN Submitted by Enrolment Number DYP-PhD-116100003 Research Guide A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF LEADERSHIP STYLES ON EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION AND COMMI. *Thesis, 10*, 426.
- Chu, X., Li, Y., Wang, P., Zeng, P., & Lei, L. (2021). Social support and cyberbullying for university students: The mediating role of internet addiction and the moderating role of stress. *Current Psychology, 59*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-01607-9>
- Criminal Code of Afghanistan, Ministry of Justice of Afghanistan 795 (2017).
<https://mcit.gov.af/dr/افغانستان-جزای-در-کود-سایبری>
- Cunningham, W. A., Nezlek, J. B., & Banaji, M. R. (2004). Implicit and explicit ethnocentrism: Revisiting the ideologies of prejudice. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin, 30*(10), 1332–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167204264654>
- Cyberbullying: Adults can be Victims Too!* / CSU. (2020). Vishwas.
<https://csultimates.com/blog/2021/07/cyberbullying-adults-can-be-victims-too/>
- Dalla Pozza, V., Di Pietro, A., Morel, S., & Psaila, E. (2016). Cyberbullying among young people. In *European Parliament Think Tank*. <https://doi.org/10.2861/748350>
- Das, S., & Uddin, M. (2022). Race, ethnicity and religion in conflict across Asia. *International Affairs, 98*(3), 1112–1114. <https://doi.org/10.1093/IA/IIAC068>
- De Dreu, C. K. W., Greer, L. L., Van Kleef, G. A., Shalvi, S., & Handgraaf, M. J. J. (2011). Oxytocin promotes human ethnocentrism. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America, 108*(4), 1262–1266.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1015316108>
- Demographics of Afghanistan Population statistics, Vital statistics, Development and health indicators, Ethnic groups, The Free Encyclopedia*. (2022). Mobilewiki.
https://www.mobilewiki.org/en/Demographics_of_Afghanistan-8888046242
- Desai, S. (2015). *Mahatma Gandhi opposed son marrying young* | *India News - Times of India*. The Times of India. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/mahatma-gandhi-opposed-son-marrying-young/articleshow/47126787.cms>
- Dhar, R. L. (2013). Intercaste Marriage: A Study from the Indian Context. *Taylor & Francis Online, 49*(1), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01494929.2012.714720>
- Dictionaries, O. learner's. (2022). *ethnicity noun - Definition, pictures, pronunciation and usage notes* | *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary at OxfordLearnersDictionaries.com*. Oxford Universtiy Press.
<https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/ethnicity?q=ethnicity>
- DICTIONARY, C. E. (2012). *Bullycide Definition & Meaning* | *Dictionary.com*. WILLIAM COLLINS SONS & CO. LTD. <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/bullycide>
- Didden, R., Scholte, R. H. J., Korzilius, H., De Moor, J. M. H., Vermeulen, A., O'Reilly, M., Lang, R., & Lancioni, G. E. (2009). Cyberbullying among students with intellectual and developmental disability in special education settings. *Developmental Neurorehabilitation, 12*(3), 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17518420902971356>
- Digital Around the World — DataReportal – Global Digital Insights*. (2022). DataReportal – Global Digital Insights. <https://datareportal.com/global-digital-overview>

- Dinh, T., Farrugia, L., O'Neill, B., Vandoninck, S., & Velicu, A. (2016). *Internet safety helplines: exploratory study first findings*. 1–8. <http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/65358/>
- Djuraskovic, O. (2022a). *Cyberbullying Statistics, Facts, and Trends (2022) with Charts*. <https://firstsiteguide.com/cyberbullying-stats/>
- Djuraskovic, O. (2022b). *Cyberbullying Statistics 2022 (with Charts): 36 “Key” Facts*. <https://firstsiteguide.com/cyberbullying-stats/>
- Donegan, R. (2012). Bullying and Cyberbullying: History, Statistics, Law, Prevention and Analysis. *The Elon Journal of Undergraduate Research in Communications*, 3(1), 33–42.
- Duman, N., & Bridge, E. N. (2020). Cyberbullying Victimization: a study of middle and high school students. *Motif Akademi Halkbilimi Dergisi*, 13(29), 466–482. <https://doi.org/10.12981/mahder.599254>
- Durán, M., & Martinez-Pecino, R. (2015). Cyberbullying trough mobile phone and the internet in dating relationships among youth people. *Comunicar*, 22(44), 159–167. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C44-2015-17>
- Durrant, R. (2018). An Introduction to Criminal Psychology. In *Routledge*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315625041>
- Ekhtyar, H. (2017). *Afghanistan: Cyber Crime Code Signed into Law*. Library of Congress. <https://www.loc.gov/item/global-legal-monitor/2017-08-16/afghanistan-cyber-crime-code-signed-into-law/>
- Ember, Ca. R., & Ember, M. (1998). On Cross-Cultural Research. In *Handbook of methods in cultural anthropology* (pp. 647–687).
- Englander, E. K. (2020). 25 Myths about Bullying and Cyberbullying. In *Wiley Blackwell*.
- Erdur-Baker, Ö. (2010). Cyberbullying and its correlation to traditional bullying, gender and frequent and risky usage of internet-mediated communication tools. *New Media and Society*, 12(1), 109–125. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444809341260>
- Espinoza, G. (2015). Daily cybervictimization among Latino adolescents: Links with emotional, physical and school adjustment. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 38, 39–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appdev.2015.04.003>
- Ethnocentric behavior*. (n.d.). Google Search. Retrieved October 30, 2022, from <https://www.google.com/imgres?imgurl=https%3A%2F%2Fqph.cf2.quoracdn.net%2Fmain-qimg-a140b5c735290637289feb1d43d89f38-pjlq&imgrefurl=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.quora.com%2FWhat-are-some-examples-of-ethnocentrism-in-everyday-life&tbid=cjNxyR81NYEoTM&vet=10CBoQxiAoB>
- Faucher, C., Jackson, M., & Cassidy, W. (2014). Cyberbullying among University Students: Gendered Experiences, Impacts, and Perspectives. *Education Research International*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/698545>
- Felt, M. (2001). *THE INCESSANT IMAGE: HOW DOMINANT NEWS COVERAGE SHAPED CANADIAN CYBERBULLYING LAW* (pp. 138–160).
- Francis, R. G., LeVine, R. A., & Campbell, D. T. (1973). Ethnocentrism: Theories of Ethnic Attitudes, and Group Behavior. *The Journal of Politics*, 35, 1022–1024. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3002563>
- Gautam, M. K. (2013). Indian Diaspora: Ethnicity and Diasporic Identity. In *CARIM-India Project*.

- Gianesini, G., & Brighi, A. (2015). Cyberbullying in the Era of Digital Relationships: The Unique Role of Resilience and Emotion Regulation on Adolescents' Adjustment. *Sociological Studies of Children and Youth*, *19*, 1–46. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1108/S1537-466120150000019001>
- Gillborn, D. (2003). "Race", ethnicity and education: Teaching and learning in multiethnic schools. In *Routledge*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203400265>
- Giumetti, G. W., & Kowalski, R. M. (2019). Cyberbullying in schools, workplaces, and romantic relationships. In *Routledge*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315110554>
- Goldstein, A. M. (2003). *Handbook of Psychology: Forensic Psychology* (Vol. 11).
- Gould, R. V. (1999). Collective violence and group solidarity: Evidence from a feuding society. *American Sociological Review*, *64*(3), 356–380. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2657491>
- Gowen, A., & Sharma, M. (2018). *India hate crimes: A spike in reports of religious-based crime since Modi's BJP came power - Washington Post*. https://www.washingtonpost.com/graphics/2018/world/reports-of-hate-crime-cases-have-spiked-in-india/?noredirect=on&utm_term=.70091688424a
- Green, D. P., & Seher, R. L. (2003). What role does prejudice play in ethnic conflict? In *Annual Review of Political Science* (Vol. 6, pp. 509–531). <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.polisci.6.121901.085642>
- Guan, N. C., Kanagasundram, S., Ann, Y. H., Loong Hui, T., & Kar Mun, T. (2016). Cyber Bullying-a new Social Menace. In *ASEAN Journal of Psychiatry* (Vol. 17, Issue 1). XX XX.
- Gudjonsson, G. (1994). The psychology of criminal conduct: Theory, research and practice. *Wiley*, *32*(7), 1–795. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967\(94\)90042-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967(94)90042-6)
- Halder, D., & Jaishankar, K. (2011). Cyber gender harassment and secondary victimization: A comparative analysis of the United States, the UK, and India. *Victims and Offenders*, *6*(4), 386–398. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15564886.2011.607402>
- Hammond, R. A., & Axelrod, R. (2006). The evolution of ethnocentrism. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, *50*(6), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022002706293470>
- Hanley, R. (2011). Ethnic violence, impact on afghanistan. In *US Army War College*.
- Hashemi, A. (2021). Cyberbullying phenomenon: an investigation among Afghan university students. *Cogent Social Sciences*, *7*(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2021.1988217>
- Heiman, T., & Olenik-Shemesh, D. (2016). Computer-based communication and cyberbullying involvement in the sample of Arab teenagers. *Education and Information Technologies*, *21*(5), 1183–1196. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-015-9375-7>
- Heirman, W., & Walrave, M. (2012). Predicting adolescent perpetration in cyberbullying: an application of the theory of planned behavior. *Psicothema*, *24*(4), 614–620. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23079360>
- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2007). Offline consequences of online victimization: School violence and delinquency. *Journal of School Violence*, *6*(3), 89–112. https://doi.org/10.1300/J202v06n03_06
- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2008). Cyberbullying: An exploratory analysis of factors related to offending and victimization. *Deviant Behavior*, *29*(2), 129–156. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639620701457816>

- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2010). Cyberbullying Identification, Prevention, and Response. In *Cyberbullying Research Center*.
- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2011). Overview of Cyberbullying. In *White House Conference of Bullying Prevention*, 21–31. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13632752.2011.569426>
- Holfeld, B. (2014). Perceptions and attributions of bystanders to cyber bullying. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 38, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.05.012>
- Howitt, D. (2009). Introduction to Forensic and Criminal Psychology. In *Pearson Education Limited*. Pearson education limited. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1475725715622172>
- Huang, Y. Y., & Chou, C. (2010). An analysis of multiple factors of cyberbullying among junior high school students in Taiwan. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 26(6), 1581–1590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2010.06.005>
- Huntington, S. P. (1993). The Clash of Civilizations? *Council on Foreign Affairs*, 72(3), 99–118. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-62965-7_6
- Huxley, E., Bizumic, B., & Kenny, A. (2015). Ethnic and Cultural Identity: Perceptions, Discrimination and Social Challenges. In *Focus on Civilizations and Cultures* (pp. 85–101). <http://search.proquest.com.libraryproxy.griffith.edu.au/docview/2134475679?accountid=14543%0Ahttp://hy8fy9jj4b.search.serialssolutions.com/directLink?&atitle=Ethnic+and+Cultural+Identity%3A+Perceptions%2C+Discrimination+and+Social+Challenges&author=&issn=>
- The Indian Penal Code, Gazette 1 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351220149-2>
- Isometric cyberbullying-infographics with online threats aggressive comments vector illustration*. (n.d.). Freepik. Retrieved October 30, 2022, from https://img.freepik.com/free-vector/isometric-cyberbullying-infographics-with-online-threats-aggressive-comments-vector-illustration_1284-75228.jpg?w=996&t=st=1667124594~exp=1667125194~hmac=2cc6982380384ae0afe08db27f3d7df791440a5b646f58a608c9482fac053ede
- Jean Camp, L., & Eric Johnson, M. (2012). The economics of financial and medical identity theft. In *The Economics of Financial and Medical Identity Theft* (Vol. 9781461419). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-1918-1>
- Jenaro, C., Flores, N., & Frías, C. P. (2018). Systematic review of empirical studies on cyberbullying in adults: What we know and what we should investigate. *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 38, 113–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2017.12.003>
- Jonker, J., & Pennink, B. W. (2010). The Essence of Research Methodology. In *Springer*. <http://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&btnG=Search&q=intitle:No+Title#0>
- Jurczak, C. A., Adorno, T. W., Frenkel-Brunswick, Levinson, D. J., & Nevitt-Sanford, R. (1950). The Authoritarian Personality. *The American Catholic Sociological Review*, 11(2), 96. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3707481>
- Kadel, B. S. (2014). Caste: A Socio-political Institution in Hindu Society. *Janapriya Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 3(December), 9–15. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jjis.v3i0.17892>
- Kam, C. D., & Kinder, D. R. (2007). Terror and ethnocentrism: Foundations of American support for the war on terrorism. In *Journal of Politics* (Vol. 69, Issue 2, pp. 320–338). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2508.2007.00534.x>
- Karabacak, K., Öztunç, M., Eksioğlu, S., Erdoğan, D. G., Yar, S., Ekenler, D., & Selim, K.

- (2015). Determination of the Level of Being Cyber Bully/Victim of Eighth Grade Students of Elementary Schools. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 176, 846–853. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.549>
- Keibell, M. R., & Davies, G. M. (2006). Practical Psychology for Forensic Investigations and Prosecutions. In *Wiley*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470713389>
- KEMP, S. (2022a). *Digital 2022: Afghanistan — DataReportal – Global Digital Insights*. DataReportal – Global Digital Insights. <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2022-afghanistan>
- KEMP, S. (2022b). *Digital 2022: India — DataReportal – Global Digital Insights*. DataReportal – Global Digital Insights. <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2022-india>
- Khawrin, M. K. (2021). Ethnocentrism correlates with Cyberbullying : Afghan Facebook Users. *Aegaeum Journal*, 9(3), 306–332. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7163757>
- Khawrin, M. K., Mathur, K., & Kumar, K. (2021a). Relationship of Gender and Age with Cyberbullying Behavior among Afghan students. *Actualizing Human Potential Souvenir*, 361.
- Khawrin, M. K., Mathur, K., & Kumar, K. (2021b). Afghan Ethnicities and Internet Surfing Correlate with Digital Bullying and Victimization. *Towards Excellence*, 13(4), 449–460. <https://doi.org/10.37867/TE130441>
- Khawrin, M. K., Mathur, K., & Kumar, K. (2022a). A Comparative Analysis of Indian Castes and Gender with Ethnocentrism among Adult Students in Ahmedabad City. *Towards Excellence*, 14(2), 1–7. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361281939_A_COMPARATIVE_ANALYSIS_OF_INDIAN_CASTES_AND_GENDER_WITH_ETHNOCENTRISM_AMONG_ADULT_STUDENTS_IN_AHMEDABAD_CITY
- Khawrin, M. K., Mathur, K., & Kumar, K. (2022b). Age and Internet Surfing of the Participants as predictors of Cyberbullying among the Students in Ahmedabad City. *International Conference on Healthy Ageing*, 21.
- Khutbah al-Hajah: How to begin a Khutbah Sermon in Arabic and English*. (n.d.). Retrieved March 27, 2022, from <https://www.abuaminaelias.com/dailyhadithonline/2011/12/26/khutbah-al-hajah-how-to-begin-a-khutbah-sermon-in-arabic-and-english/>
- Kidd, C. (2004). British Identities Before Natinalism: Ethnicity and Nationhood in the Atlantic World 1600-1800. In *Cambridge Universtiy Press*.
- Kim, S., Kimber, M., Boyle, M. H., & Georgiades, K. (2019). Sex Differences in the Association Between Cyberbullying Victimization and Mental Health, Substance Use, and Suicidal Ideation in Adolescents. *Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 64(2), 126–135. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0706743718777397>
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). Research Methodology Methods and techniques. In S. Edition (Ed.), *New Age International (P) Limited*. <http://publications.lib.chalmers.se/records/fulltext/245180/245180.pdf%0Ahttps://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12380/245180%0Ahttp://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jsames.2011.03.003%0Ahttps://doi.org/10.1016/j.gr.2017.08.001%0Ahttp://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.precamres.2014.12>
- Kowalski, R. M., Giumetti, G. W., Schroeder, A. N., & Lattanner, M. R. (2014). Bullying in the digital age: A critical review and meta-analysis of cyberbullying research among

- youth. *Psychological Bulletin*, 140(4), 1073–1137. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0035618>
- Kumar, R. (2011). *Research Methodology a step by step guide for beginners* (3rd edition). Sage.
- LeVine, R. A. (2015). Ethnocentrism. In *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences: Second Edition* (pp. 166–167). Elsevier Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.12063-X>
- Li, Q. (2006). Cyberbullying in schools: A research of gender differences. *School Psychology International*, 27(2), 157–170. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034306064547>
- Li, Q., Cross, D., & Smith, P. K. (2012). Cyberbullying in the Global Playground: Research from International Perspectives. In Q. Li, D. Cross, & P. K. Smith (Eds.), *John Wiley & Sons Ltd.*
- Malesevic, S. (2004). The Sociology of Ethnicity. In *Sage Publications*.
- Manor, J. (1996). “Ethnicity” and politics in India. *Wiley*, 72(3), 459–475.
- Mantovani, G. (2012). Exploring borders: Understanding culture and psychology. In *Routledge Taylor and Francis group*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203130926>
- Marcum, C. D., Higgins, G. E., Freiburger, T. L., & Ricketts, M. L. (2012). Battle of the sexes: An examination of male and female cyber bullying. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 6(1), 904–911.
- Marcum, C. D., Higgins, G. E., Freiburger, T. L., & Ricketts, M. L. (2014). Exploration of the Cyberbullying Victim/Offender Overlap by Sex. *American Journal of Criminal Justice*, 39(3), 538–548. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12103-013-9217-3>
- Marr, K. L., & Duell, M. N. (2020). Cyberbullying and cybervictimization: Does gender matter? *Psychological Reports*, 0(0), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033294120916868>
- Marsden, P. (2001). Afghanistan : Minorities , Conflict and the Search for Peace. In *Minority Rights Group International*.
- Mazhar, M. S., Khan, S. O., & Goraya, N. (2012). Ethnic Factor in Afghanistan. *Journal of Political Studies*, 19(2), 97–109.
- McNamara, L., Colley, P., & Franklin, N. (2017). School recess, social connectedness and health: A Canadian perspective. In *Health Promotion International* (Vol. 32, Issue 2, pp. 392–402). <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapro/dav102>
- Meeusen, C., de Vroome, T., & Hooghe, M. (2013). How does education have an impact on ethnocentrism? A structural equation analysis of cognitive, occupational status and network mechanisms. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 37(5), 507–522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2013.07.002>
- Minor, M., Smith, G., & Brashen, H. (2014). Cyberbullying in Higher Education: Implications and Solutions. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 3(1), 50–60. <https://doi.org/10.5590/JERAP.2014.04.1.05>
- Mirchandani, M. (2018). Digital hatred, real violence: Majoritarian radicalisation and social media in India. In *ORF Occasional Paper* (Issue August). <https://doi.org/August 29, 2018>
- Monroe, K. R., Hankin, J., & Vechten, R. B. Van. (2000). The Psychological Foundations of Identity Politics. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 3(1), 419–447. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.polisci.3.1.419>

- Mounsey, S. (2007). *Ethnocentrism and attitudes to cultural diversity and immigration: A review ; ethnocentrism and attitudes to cultural diversity and immigration in Western Australia*. https://ro.ecu.edu.au/theses_hons/1145
- Münster, J. (2005). Simultaneous Inter- and Intra-Group Conflicts. In *SOCIAL SCIENCE RESEARCH CENTER BERLIN*. Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.722474>
- Navarro, R., Youbero, S., Larranaga, E., & Smith, P. K. (2015). Cyberbullying across the globe: Gender, family, and mental health. In R. Navarro, S. Yubero, & E. Larrañaga (Eds.), *Springer*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-25552-1>
- Neuliep, J. W., & McCroskey, J. C. (2013). *Ethnocentrism Scale*. www.midss.ie
- Neuliep, J. W., & McCroskey, J. C. (1997). The development of a U.S. and generalized ethnocentrism scale. *Communication Research Reports*, 14(4), 385–398. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08824099709388682>
- Nilan, P., Burgess, H., Hobbs, M., Threadgold, S., & Alexander, W. (2015). Youth, Social Media, and Cyberbullying Among Australian Youth: “Sick Friends.” *Social Media and Society*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305115604848>
- Nycyk, M. (2015). *Adult-to-adult cyberbullying: An exploration of a dark side of the Internet*. http://www.123rf.com/profile_kmitu
- Olatundun, I. O. (2009). What is Cross-cultural Research? *International Journal of Psychological Studies*, 1(2), 82–96. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijps.v1n2p82>
- Ozgun, H. (2015). Exploring the Distance Education Students’ Cyberbullying, Cybervictimization and Cyberbullying Sensibility Levels. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 16(October), 3–17. <https://files-eric-ed.gov.sabidi.urv.cat/fulltext/EJ1092864.pdf>
- Parks, P. J. (2013). Cyberbullying. In *Reference Point Press*.
- Patchin, J. W., & Hinduja, S. (2010). Cyberbullying and Self-Esteem. *Journal of School Health*, 80(12), 614–621. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1746-1561.2010.00548.x>
- Patchin, J. W., & Hinduja, S. (2012). Cyberbullying Prevention and Response: Expert Perspectives. In *Routledge*. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-8556-7.ch007>
- Patchin, J. W., & Hinduja, S. (2015). Measuring cyberbullying: Implications for research. In *Aggression and Violent Behavior* (Vol. 23, pp. 69–74). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2015.05.013>
- Pereira, A., Hsu, C., & Kundu, S. (2002). A Cross-Cultural Analysis of Ethnocentrism in China, India, and Taiwan. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 15(1), 77–91. <http://www.haworthpressinc.com/store/product.asp?sku=J046>
- Pitchkites, M. (2022). *26 Cyber Security Statistics, Facts & Trends in 2022*. <https://www.cloudwards.net/cyber-security-statistics/>
- Pratama, R. (2019). Ethnocentrism and Bias Incidents : Is there a Common Thread ? *CULTURALISTICS: Journal of Cultural, Literary, and Linguistic Studies*, 3(1), 39–44. <http://ejournal.undip.ac.id/index.php/culturalistics>
- Pratto, F., & Stewart, A. L. (2011). Social Dominance Theory. In *The Encyclopedia of Peace Psychology* (pp. 1–4). Blackwell Publishing Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470672532.WBEPP253>
- Raskauskas, J., & Stoltz, A. D. (2007). Involvement in traditional and electronic bullying

- among adolescents. *Developmental Psychology*, 43(3), 564–575.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.43.3.564>
- Ray, J. J. (1971). Ethnocentrism-attitudes and behaviour. *The Australian Quarterly*, 43(2), 89–97.
- Ridzuan, A. R., Bolong, J., Omar, S. Z., Osman, M. N., Yusof, R., & Abdullah, S. F. M. (2012). Social Media Contribution Towards Ethnocentrism. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 65, 517–522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.11.158>
- Romm, N. R. A. (2012). Revisiting Social Dominance Theory: Invoking a More Retroductively-Oriented Approach to Systemic Theorizing. *Systemic Practice and Action Research*, 26(2), 111–129. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11213-012-9245-9>
- Safaria, T. (2016). Prevalence and impact of cyberbullying in a sample of Indonesian junior high school students. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 15(1), 82–91.
- Sahih International. (n.d.). *Surah Hujurat Ayat 13 (49:13 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam*. Retrieved March 27, 2022, from <https://myislam.org/surah-hujurat/ayat-13/>
- Sakellariou, T., Carroll, A., & Houghton, S. (2012). Rates of cyber victimization and bullying among male Australian primary and high school students. *School Psychology International*, 33(5), 533–549. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034311430374>
- Schinka, J. A., & Velicer, W. F. (2013). *Handbook of Psychology: Research methods in Psychology* (I. B. W. John A. Schinka, Wayne F. Velicer (Ed.); 2nd edition). John Wiley & Sons, Inc. <https://cybercrime.gov.in/UploadMedia/MHA-CitizenManualReportCPRGRcomplaints-v10.pdf>
- Scupin, R. (2012). Race and ethnicity : the United States and the world. In *Pearson* (Edited).
- Sengupta, A., & Chaudhuri, A. (2011). Are social networking sites a source of online harassment for teens? Evidence from survey data. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 33(2), 284–290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2010.09.011>
- Sengupta, P., Chokshi, A., Ozacar, B. H., Dutta, S., Sanyal, M., & Shanahan, M.-C. (2022). Language and symbolic violence in computational models of ethnocentrism: A critical phenomenology and Southern re-orientations. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2022.2025475>
- Sevcikova, A., & Šmahel, D. (2009). Online harassment and cyberbullying in the Czech Republic: Comparison across age groups. *Journal of Psychology*, 217(4), 227–229. <https://doi.org/10.1027/0044-3409.217.4.227>
- Ševčíková, A., Šmahel, D., & Otavová, M. (2012). The perception of cyberbullying in adolescent victims. *Emotional and Behavioural Difficulties*, 17(3–4), 319–328. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632752.2012.704309>
- Shaban Rafi, M. (2019). Cyberbullying in Pakistan: Positioning the Aggressor, Victim, and Bystander. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 34(3), 601–620. <https://doi.org/10.33824/PJPR.2019.34.3.33>
- Shankarmahesh, M. N. (2006). Consumer ethnocentrism: An integrative review of its antecedents and consequences. In *International Marketing Review* (Vol. 23, Issue 2, pp. 146–172). <https://doi.org/10.1108/02651330610660065>
- Sharma, S. (2013). Hate Crimes in India: An Economic Analysis of Violence and Atrocities Against Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. *CDE*, 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2055549>
- Siddique, A. (2012). Afghanistan's ethnic divides. In *CIDOB Policy Research Project*.

- Šimko, M. I. (2013). *Ethnocentrism: Uses and Usability*.
- Sivakumar, R. (2013). *Computer Mediated Interpersonal Crimes : A Study of Cyber Bullying among College Students in Cosmopolitan Cities*. Manonmaniam Sundaranar University.
- Smith, J. A., & Yoon, J. (2013). Cyberbullying Presence, Extent, & Forms in a Midwestern Post-secondary Institution. *Information Systems Education Journal (ISEDJ)*, 11(3), 52–78.
- Smith, P. K., López-Castro, L., Robinson, S., & Görzig, A. (2019). Consistency of gender differences in bullying in cross-cultural surveys. In *Aggression and Violent Behavior* (Vol. 45, Issue 2017). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2018.04.006>
- Smith, P. K., Mahdavi, J., Carvalho, M., Fisher, S., Russell, S., & Tippett, N. (2008). Cyberbullying: Its nature and impact in secondary school pupils. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry and Allied Disciplines*, 49(4), 376–385. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.2007.01846.x>
- Smith, P. K., Thompson, F., & Davidson, J. (2014). Cyber safety for adolescent girls: Bullying, harassment, sexting, pornography, and solicitation. *Current Opinion in Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 26(5), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1097/GCO.000000000000106>
- Social Dominance Theory and the Dynamics of Gendered Prejudice - YouTube*. (n.d.). Institute of Personality & Social Research. Retrieved September 15, 2021, from https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IqP_PIH2zcw
- Sorrentino, A., Baldry, A. C., Farrington, D. P., & Blaya, C. (2019). Epidemiology of cyberbullying across europe: Differences between countries and genders. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 19(2), 74–91. <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2019.2.005>
- Speece, M., & Pinkaeo, K. (2002). Service Expectations and Consumer Ethnocentrism. *Australasian Marketing Journal (AMJ)*, 10(3), 59–75. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1441-3582\(02\)70158-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1441-3582(02)70158-4)
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (1986). The social Theory of Intergroup Behaviour. *The Psychology of Intergroup Relations*, 276–293.
- Tanner, C. J., & Jackson, A. L. (2011). The combination of social and personal contexts affects dominance hierarchy development in shore crabs, *Carcinus maenas*. *Animal Behaviour*, 82(5), 1185–1192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ANBEHAV.2011.09.004>
- Tennant, J. E., Demaray, M. K., Coyle, S., & Malecki, C. K. (2015). The dangers of the web: Cybervictimization, depression, and social support in college students. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 50, 348–357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.04.014>
- The Information Technology Act of India, 1 (2000). https://www.indiacode.nic.in/bitstream/123456789/13116/1/it_act_2000_updated.pdf
- Tiffany, F. (2018). Cyberbullying: A narrative review. *Journal of Addiction Therapy and Research*, 2(1), 10–27. <https://doi.org/10.29328/journal.jatr.1001007>
- Todorov, G. (2022). *50 Crucial Cyberbullying Stats, Trends, and Facts 2022*. <https://thrivemyway.com/cyberbullying-stats/>
- Tokunaga, R. S. (2010). Following you home from school: A critical review and synthesis of research on cyberbullying victimization. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 26(3), 277–287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2009.11.014>
- Topcu, Ç., & Erdur-Baker, Ö. (2010). The Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory (RCBI): Validity and reliability studies. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 5, 660–664.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.07.161>

- Topcu, Ç., & Erdur-Baker, Ö. (2012). Affective and cognitive empathy as mediators of gender differences in cyber and traditional bullying. *School Psychology International*, 33(5), 550–561. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034312446882>
- Topcu, Ç., & Erdur-Baker, Ö. (2018). RCBI-II: The second revision of the Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory. *Measurement and Evaluation in Counseling and Development*, 51(1), 32–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07481756.2017.1395705>
- Tupat, A. R., & Panda, U. K. (2021). Advantageous and adversative impacts of social media on undergraduate law students. *Innovations*, 64, 799–809.
- Valunaite Oleskeviciene, G., & Sliogeriene, J. (2020). Research methodology. *Humanities - Arts and Humanities in Progress*, 13, 1–53. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-37727-4_2
- Weiner, M. (1983). The Political Demography of Assam Movement. *Population and Development Review*, 9(2), 279–292. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1973053>
- Wright, M. F., Kamble, S. V., & Soudi, S. P. (2015). Indian adolescents' cyber aggression involvement and cultural values: The moderation of peer attachment. *School Psychology International*, 36(4), 410–427. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034315584696>
- Wright, M. F., & Li, Y. (2013). The Association Between Cyber Victimization and Subsequent Cyber Aggression: The Moderating Effect of Peer Rejection. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 42(5), 662–674. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-012-9903-3>
- Yeh, K.-H., Dueck, A., Teo, T., & Ansloos, J. P. (2021). Indigenous Psychology of Spirituality in my beginning is my end. In K.-H. Yeh, A. Dueck, T. Teo, & J. P. Ansloos (Eds.), *Palgrave macmillan*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-50869-2>
- Yiğit, M. F., Keskin, S., & Yurdugül, H. (2018). Investigating the Relationship between Cyberbullying and Perceived Family Support in Middle-School Students in Relation to Gender, Frequency of Internet Use, and Grade. *Addicta: The Turkish Journal on Addictions*, 5(2), 249–282. <https://doi.org/10.15805/addicta.2018.5.2.0050>
- Zsila, Á. (2018). *Psychological vulnerability and protective factors of cyberbullying victimization and perpetration*.
- Zych, I., Ortega-Ruiz, R., & Del Rey, R. (2015). Systematic review of theoretical studies on bullying and cyberbullying: Facts, knowledge, prevention, and intervention. In *Aggression and Violent Behavior* (Vol. 23, pp. 1–21). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2015.10.001>

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Demographic of the participants

1: Age: _____

2: Gender: 1) Male 2) Female

3: Current dwelling: 1) Ahmedabad , 2) Kabul
3) if other place please write it: _____

4: Country: 1) India , 2) Afghanistan
3) if other country please write: _____

5: How many profiles do you have in social networks? Please tick those social networks, which you have and, if it is not written there, please write it.

1) Facebook , 2) Twitter , 3) WhatsApp , 4) IMO , 5) LinkedIn , 6) WeChat , 7) Viber , 8) Instagram , 9) Google Duo , 10) YouTube , 11) Line , 12) Myspace , 13) Skype , 14) Snapchat , 15) Tiktok , 16) Hike , 17) Telegram ,
18) *If any other please write:* _____

6: On average, how many hours a day are you on the Internet (chatting, visiting social networking, writing e-mails, etc.)? _____

7: Have you ever been victim of cyber bullying acts in the last twelve months?

1) Yes , 2) No

8: Have you ever been involved in cyber bullying as a perpetrator in the last twelve months?

1) Yes , 2) No

9: Have you ever seen cyber bullying perpetrator or victim in the last twelve months?

1) Yes , 2) No

Participant's informed Consent Form

Serial number: _____

Date: / /

Title of research:

Ethnocentrism as a Predictor of Cyber Bullying & Cyber Victimization among adults: A Cross-Cultural Study

Consent to take part in research:

I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study. I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind. I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study. I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research. I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially. I understand that in any report on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous. I understand that under freedom of information legalization I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above. I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

Name: Mohammad Khalid, degree: Perusing Ph.D., affiliated from Gujarat University.

Contact details of researcher. Cellphone and WhatsApp: (XXXXXXXXXXXX)

Email:

mk.ahmadzai@yhao.com

Signature of research participant Date

Signature of researcher Date

I believe the participant is giving informed consent to participate in this study

Generalized Ethnocentrism Scale

Below are items that relate to the cultures of different parts of the world. Work quickly and record your first reaction to each item. There are no right or wrong answers. Please indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree with each item using the following five-point scale:

Strongly Disagree = 1; Disagree = 2; Neutral = 3; Agree = 4; Strongly Agree = 5;

No	Items	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	agree	Strongly agree
1	Most other cultures are backward compared to my culture.	1	2	3	4	5
2	My culture should be the role model for other cultures.	1	2	3	4	5
3	People from other cultures act strange when they come to my culture.	1	2	3	4	5
4	Lifestyles in other cultures are just as valid as those in my culture.	1	2	3	4	5
5	Other cultures should try to be more like my culture.	1	2	3	4	5
6	I am not interested in the values and customs of other cultures.	1	2	3	4	5
7	People in my culture could learn a lot from people in other cultures.	1	2	3	4	5
8	Most people from other cultures just don't know what's good for them.	1	2	3	4	5
9	I respect the values and customs of other cultures.	1	2	3	4	5
10	Other cultures are smart to look up to our culture.	1	2	3	4	5
11	Most people would be happier if they lived like people in my culture.	1	2	3	4	5

12	I have many friends from different cultures.	1	2	3	4	5
13	People in my culture have just about the best lifestyles of anywhere.	1	2	3	4	5
14	Lifestyles in other cultures are not as valid as those in my culture.	1	2	3	4	5
15	I am very interested in the values and customs of other cultures.	1	2	3	4	5
16	I apply my values when judging people who are different.	1	2	3	4	5
17	I see people who are similar to me as virtuous.	1	2	3	4	5
18	I do not cooperate with people who are different.	1	2	3	4	5
19	Most people in my culture just don't know what is good for them.	1	2	3	4	5
20	I do not trust people who are different.	1	2	3	4	5
21	I dislike interacting with people from different cultures.	1	2	3	4	5
22	I have little respect for the values and customs of other cultures.	1	2	3	4	5

Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory-II (RCBI-II)

Please read the items carefully. Please tell us how often the instances described below have happened to you and you have done them to others during the last 12 months. Tell us if and how often you have done this to others by marking the appropriate boxes in the “I did this” column. Tell us if and how often this has happened to you by marking the appropriate boxes in the “This happened to me” column. Please make sure that you marked your responses for all the items twice, one for “I did this” and one for “This happened to me” column.

No	Through the INTERNET;	I did this.				This happened to me.			
		never	once	2-3 times	More than 3 times	never	once	2-3 times	More than 3 times
1	taking over the password of someone’s account	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
2	using someone’s account without his/her permission and publishing humiliating posts	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
3	threatening someone	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
4	insulting someone	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
5	sending embarrassing and hurtful messages	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
6	sharing an inappropriate photo or a video of	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4

	someone without his/her permission									
7	sharing a secret with others without the permission of the owner	1	2	3	4		1	2	3	4
8	spreading rumors	1	2	3	4		1	2	3	4
9	creating an account on behalf of someone without letting him/her know and acting like the account's owner	1	2	3	4		1	2	3	4
10	creating a humiliating website	1	2	3	4		1	2	3	4

Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory (RCBI)

Please select any of the below behavior, If you have performed against someone during the previous twelve months.

No.	Cyberbullying behavior	Never	Once	Two to three times	More than three times
1	stealing of personal information from computer (like files, email, addresses, pictures, IM messages, or Facebook info)	0	1	2-3	>3
2	stealing of computer nicknames or screen names	0	1	2-3	>3
3	threatening in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter)	0	1	2-3	>3
4	Insulting in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter)	0	1	2-3	>3
5	excluding in online forums by blocking others' comments or removing them	0	1	2-3	>3
6	slander by posting fake photos on the internet	0	1	2-3	>3
7	sharing private internet conversations without the other's knowledge (such as chatting with a friend on Skype with other(s) in the room)	0	1	2-3	>3
8	Making fun of comments in online forums (such as Facebook)	0	1	2-3	>3
9	Sending threatening or hurtful comments through email	0	1	2-3	>3

10	stealing email access (usernames and passwords) and blocking true owner's access	0	1	2-3	>3
11	stealing email access and reading personal messages	0	1	2-3	>3
12	sending threatening and or hurtful text messages	0	1	2-3	>3
13	misleading by pretending to be other gender (male/female)	0	1	2-3	>3
14	publishing online an embarrassing photo without permission	0	1	2-3	>3

Please select any of the below behavior, If someone have performed against you during the previous twelve months.

No.	Cyber victim behavior	Never	Once	Two to three times	More than three times
1	stealing of personal information from computer (like files, email, addresses, pictures, IM messages, or Facebook info)	0	1	2-3	>3
2	stealing of computer nicknames or screen names	0	1	2-3	>3
3	threatening in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter)	0	1	2-3	>3

4	Insulting in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter)	0	1	2-3	>3
5	excluding in online forums by blocking others' comments or removing them	0	1	2-3	>3
6	slander by posting fake photos on the internet	0	1	2-3	>3
7	sharing private internet conversations without the other's knowledge (such as chatting with a friend on Skype with other(s) in the room)	0	1	2-3	>3
8	Making fun of comments in online forums (such as Facebook)	0	1	2-3	>3
9	receiving threatening or hurtful comments through email	0	1	2-3	>3
10	stealing email access (usernames and passwords) and blocking true owner's access	0	1	2-3	>3
11	stealing email access and reading personal messages	0	1	2-3	>3
12	receiving threatening and or hurtful text messages	0	1	2-3	>3
13	misleading by pretending to be other gender (male/female)	0	1	2-3	>3
14	publishing online an embarrassing photo without permission	0	1	2-3	>3

تاریخ: / /

مسلسل شمیره: _____ /

د څیړني عنوان:

توکمیز پالنه د لویانو په سایبر ځورونې او سایبر قرباني کې د یو وړاندوینې عامل په توګه: د کلتورنو مقایسوي مطالعه

Ethnocentrism as a predictor of cyberbullying & cyber victimization among adults: A Cross-Cultural Study

قوم ګرایی به عنوان پیش بینی کننده قلدری و قربانی سایبری در بزرگسالان: یک مطالعه فرا فرهنگی

د دې څیړني د پیلولو موخه د توکمیز معلومول او د هغې اغیزې موندل دي. تاسو ته ډاډ درکول کيږي چې ستاسو هويت او شخصي معلومات به مو پټ ساتل کيږي. په دې پوښتنلیک کې هیڅ سم یا غلط ځواب نشته، مګر د هغې ټول موضوعات ستاسو په شخصي نظرونو پورې اړه لري. له همدې امله، زه په صادقانه توګه له تاسو څخه هیله کوم چې د دې پوښتنو ځوابولو کې زموږ سره همکاري وکړئ. مننه.

هدف از راه اندازی این تحقیق معلوم نمودن فرهنگ ګرایی و اثرات آن میباشد. به شما اطمینان داده میشود که هويت و معلومات شخصی تان مخفی نگهداشته می شود. در این پرسشنامه هیچ جواب درست و یا اشتباه نیست، ولی همهء موضوعات آن به نظریات شخصی تان ارتباط می گیرد. بناءً از شما صمیمانه تقاضا مینمایم تا در قسمت ارایه جوابات به این پرسشنامه ما را همکاری نموده ممنون سازید.

د رضاینت نېسه / نشانی رضای

د څیړونکي تایید / تایید محقق

اصطلاحاتو تعریفونه

توکمیز یا قوم پرستی

د یو قوم، نژاد یا توکم کلتور ته لومړیتوب ورکول د توکمیز پرستی په نوم یادېږي.

Ethnocentrism

Giving priority to the same national, caste, or ethnicity's culture is called ethnocentrism.

قوم گرایی

اولویت دادن به فرهنگ ملی، کاست یا قومی یکسان را قوم گرایی می نامند.

توکم یا قوم

د انسانانو حیاتیاتی نسل تسلسل چې د یو اساس څخه شروع او د قبیلې په نوم یادېږي. چې په مجموع کې ټول وګړی د قبیلو چې ورته فرهنگ ولری د قوم په نوم یادېږي. دا یو حیاتیاتی-ټولنیز هویت یا پیژندنه ده.

Ethnicity

It is the biological descendant of humans from one baseline called a tribe. Collectively, all members of tribes from one biological baseline and same culture are called ethnicity. It is a bio-social identification.

قوم

نسل حیاتیاتی انسان که از یک پایه شروع آن را بنام قبيله یاد می شود. در مجموع، تمام اعضای قبایل از یک پایه حیاتیاتی و فرهنگ یکسان، قومیت نامیده می شوند. این یک هویت حیاتیاتی-اجتماعی است.

ذات

د قانون له مخې، د ټولني د ټولنيز جوړښت د فعاليت او د اتباعو د کم عاید پر بنسټ په ډلو ویشل ذات بلل کېږي. دا یو اکتسابی هویت دی.

Caste

According to the law, the division of society into groups based on the social structure function and low-income of citizens is called caste. This is an acquired identity.

کاست

طبق قانون، یک جامعه بر اساس عملکرد ساختار اجتماعی و درآمد پایین شهروندان، به تقسیم گروه‌ها عبارت از کاست است. این یک هویت اکتسابی است.

کلتور یا فرهنگ

د هر قسم ډلې د غړو جوړښت لکه ذات، نژاد، قوم، قبيلې او داسې نور چې د کردار او رفتار چلند يې سره ورته وي د کلتور په نامه يادېږي.

Culture

It is the same pattern of behavior among the group members such as caste, race, nation, tribe, or any other formation of the group that is called culture.

فرهنگ

اين همان الگوي رفتاری در بين اعضای گروه مانند کاست، نژاد، ملت، قبيله يا هر شکل ديگری از گروه است که فرهنگ نامیده می شود.

سایبری خورونه

د الکترونيکي شبکو وسايلو له لارې د ملگرو خورول د سايبير خورونې په نوم يادېږي.

Cyberbullying

Teasing peers through electronic networking gadgets is called cyberbullying.

زورگویی سایبری

اذیت کردن همسالان از طریق ابزارهای شبکه الکترونيکی، آزار سايبيری نامیده می شود.

د سايبير قرباني

د الکترونيکي شبکو وسايلو له لارې د ملگرو لخوا زيانمن کيدل د سايبير قرباني بلل کېږي.

Cyber Victimization

To be harmed by peers through electronic networking gadgets is called cyber victimization.

قربانی سایبری

آسيب ديدن توسط همتايان از طریق ابزارهای شبکه الکترونيکی قربانی سايبيری نامیده می شود.

If anyone still has any doubt please ask the researcher for further explanation.

فردی خانگیرنی/مشخصات فردی

1: Age (سن): _____

2: Gender (جنسیت): 1) Male 2) Female

3: Current dwelling (سکونت فعلی): 1) Ahmedabad , 2) Kabul
3) if other place please write it:

4: Country (دولت): 1) India , 2) Afghanistan
3) if other country please write:

5: How many profiles do you have in social networks? Please tick those social networks, which you have and, if it is not written there, please write it.

در شبکه های اجتماعی چند پروفایل دارید؟ لطفاً آن شبکه های اجتماعی را که استفاده می کنید نشانی کرده و نیز اگر (نظریات بیشتر داشته باشید) می توانید ارائه کنید.

- 1) Facebook , 2) Twitter , 3) WhatsApp , 4) IMO , 5) LinkedIn , 6) WeChat , 7) Viber , 8) Instagram , 9) Google Duo , 10) YouTube , 11) Line , 12) Myspace , 13) Skype , 14) Snapchat , 15) Tiktok , 16) Hike , 17) Telegram ,
18) *If any other please write:* _____

6: On average, how many hours a day are you on the Internet (chatting, visiting social networking, writing e-mails, etc.)? _____

(در یک روز چند ساعت اینترنت را استفاده میکنید)

(په یوه ورځ کې څو ساعته انټرنیټ کاروی)

7: Have you ever been victim of cyber bullying acts in the last twelve months?

- 2) Yes , 2) No

(آیا تا کنون در دوازده ماه گذشته قربانی اعمال سایبری شده اید؟)

8: Have you ever been involved in cyber bullying as a perpetrator in the last twelve months?

2) Yes , 2) No

(آیا تاکنون در دوازده ماه گذشته درگیر رفتار سایبری به عنوان مجرم بوده اید؟)

9: Have you ever seen cyber bullying perpetrator or victim in the last twelve months?

2) Yes , 2) No

(آیا تاکنون در دوازده ماه گذشته مرتکب یا قربانی اعمال سایبری را دیده و یا شنیده اید؟)

10: Educational qualification (میزان تحصیلات):

1) Up to 12th grade , 2) Under Graduate (Bachelor) ,
3) Post graduate (master, M.Phil. or Ph.D.)

11: Education field / department (تحصیلی خانگه یا دیپارتمنت): _____

12: Ethnicity/ Caste (قوم یا ذات):

Indian national please select your caste below:

1) Open/General category (OC/GC) 2) Scheduled Tribe (ST)
3) Scheduled Extremely Backward Caste (SEBC) 4) Scheduled Caste (SC)
5) Other Backward Caste (OBC) 6) Economically Weaker Section (EWS)
7) if any other caste please write it _____

Afghan National please select your ethnicity below:

11) Pashtun 12) Tajik 13) Hazara 14) Baloch
15) Uzbek 16) Bayat 17) Sadat
18) Qazalbash 19) if any other ethnicity please write it _____

Ethnocentrism Scale

Below are items that relate to the cultures of different parts of the world. Work quickly and record your first reaction to each item. There are no right or wrong answers. Please indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree with each item using the following five-point scale:

توکم پالنې مقیاس

لاندې جملې د نړۍ د کلتورونو د توپيرونو پر بنسټ ليکل شوي. په دې جملو کې هيڅ سم يا غلط ځواب نشته. تاسو د خپلې خوښې سره سم د هر يو چلند تکرار غوره کوئ، کوم چې د ليکړد اندازه کولو پر اساس تنظيم شوی، يو اندازه چې تاسو فکر مناسب وي په نښه يې کړي.

مقیاس قوم گرایی

جملات ذیل به اساس تفاوت فرهنگهای جهان نوشته شده است. در این جملات کدام جواب درست و غلط وجود ندارد. شما یک گزینه مطابق میل تان که به اساس اندازه گیری لیکن ترتیب گردیده است یک اندازه را، که به نظر شما مناسب باشد، انتخاب کنید.

No.	Items موضوعات	Strongly Disagree (شدیداً مخالف)	Disagree (مخالف)	Neutral (بیطرف)	Agree (موافق)	Strongly agree (شدیداً موافق)
1	<p>ز مور د کلتور او فرهنگ په پرتله نور فرهنگونه روسته پاتي دي.</p> <p>Most other cultures are backward compared to my culture.</p> <p>اکثر فرهنگ های دیگر نسبت به فرهنگ من عقب مانده است.</p>	1	2	3	4	5
2	<p>زما فرهنگ باید نورو فرهنگونو لپاره يوه اولگو وي.</p> <p>My culture should be the role model for other cultures.</p> <p>فرهنگ من باید برای فرهنگ های دیگر یک الگو باشد.</p>	1	2	3	4	5
3	<p>د نورو فرهنگونو خلک ز مور فرهنگ سره غير عادي چلند کوي.</p>	1	2	3	4	5

	People from other cultures act strange when they come to my culture. مردم سایر فرهنگها نسبت به فرهنگ من برخورد متفاوت دارند.					
4	د نورو فرهنگونو ژوند، زموږ د ژوند په څیر دی. Lifestyles in other cultures are just as valid as those in my culture. سبک زندگی در سایر فرهنگ ها به اندازه فرهنگ خودم با ارزش است.	1	2	3	4	5
5	نور فرهنگونه باید کوبښښ وکړی چې زموږ د فرهنگ په څیر شی. Other cultures should try to be more like my culture. سایر فرهنگها باید تلاش نمایند تا مثل فرهنگ من باشد.	1	2	3	4	5
6	زه د نورو فرهنگونو له ارزښتونو او دودونو سره ډیره لیوالتیا نه لرم. I am not interested in the values and customs of other cultures. من به ارزشها و عنعنات سایر فرهنگها علاقمندی ندارم.	1	2	3	4	5
7	د نورو فرهنگونو خلکو څخه زموږ فرهنگ والا کولای شي ډیر څه زده کوي. People in my culture could learn a lot from people in other cultures. مردم در فرهنگ من می توانند چیزهای زیادی را از مردم فرهنگهای دیگر بیاموزند.	1	2	3	4	5
8	د نورو فرهنگونو ډیر خلک په دې نه پوهیږی چې کوم شی دوی ته ښه دی. Most people from other cultures just don't know what's good for them. بیشتر افراد در فرهنگ های دیگر نمی دانند چه چیزی برای آنها مفید است.	1	2	3	4	5
9	زه د نورو فرهنگونو ارزښتونو او دودونو ته درناوی لرم. I respect the values and customs of other cultures. من به ارزشها و عنعنات سایر فرهنگها احترام میگذارم.	1	2	3	4	5
10	نور فرهنگونه زما تر فرهنگ ډیر زیرک دی. Other cultures are smart to look up to our culture. سایر فرهنگها نسبت به فرهنگ ما، زیرک اند.	1	2	3	4	5
11	که خلک زموږ د فرهنگ په څیر ژوند کړي وای، نو دوی به خوشحاله ول. Most people would be happier if they lived like people in my culture. مردم بیشتر شاد خواهند بود اگر آن ها شبیه کسانی که در فرهنگ ما هستند، زندگی کنند.	1	2	3	4	5
12	زه په نورو فرهنگونو کې ډیر ملگری لرم.	1	2	3	4	5

	I have many friends from different cultures. من از فرهنگهای دیگر دوستانی زیادی دارم.					
13	زما د فرهنگ خلک تر بل هر چا بنه ژوند لری. People in my culture have just about the best lifestyles of anywhere. مردم در فرهنگ من بهترین سبک زندگی هر جایی دیگری را دارد.	1	2	3	4	5
14	د ژوند طرز په نورو فرهنگونو کې زموږ د فرهنگ په اساس اعتبار نه لری. Lifestyles in other cultures are not as valid as those in my culture. سبک های زندگی در سایر فرهنگها به اندازه فرهنگ من معتبر نیست.	1	2	3	4	5
15	زه د نورو فرهنگونوله ارزښتونو سره ډیره لیاوالتیا لرم. I am very interested in the values and customs of other cultures. من به ارزشها و عنعنات فرهنگی سایر فرهنگها علاقمندی دارم.	1	2	3	4	5
16	زه د خپل فرهنگ ارزښتونو سره سم نور فرهنگونه پرتله کوم. I apply my values when judging people who are different. من به اساس ارزشهای فرهنگی خودم دیگران را قضاوت می کنم.	1	2	3	4	5
17	زه هغه خلک باتقوا بولم چي زما په څیر دی. I see people who are similar to me as virtuous. من آن عده مردم را با تقوا میبینم که مثل من باشد.	1	2	3	4	5
18	زه له هغو خلکو سره چي متفاوت وی، کومک نه کوم. I do not cooperate with people who are different. من با مردم که متفاوت باشد هماهنگی نه می کنم.	1	2	3	4	5
19	زما د فرهنگپیر خلک په دې نه پوهیږی چي کوم شی دوی ته بنه دی. Most people in my culture just don't know what is good for them. بیشتر مردم در فرهنگ من نمیدانند که چه برای شان خوب است.	1	2	3	4	5
20	زه په هغو خلکو اعتبار نه کوم، چي زما څخه متفاوت وی. I do not trust people who are different. من به افراد که متفاوت است اعتماد نمیکنم.	1	2	3	4	5
21	زما نه خوښیږی چي د نورو فرهنگونو له خلکو سره اړیکي ولرم. I dislike interacting with people from different cultures. من دوست ندارم با مردم سایر فرهنگها تعامل داشته باشم.	1	2	3	4	5
22	زه د نورو فرهنگونو خلکو ته لږ درناوي لرم.	1	2	3	4	5

	I have little respect for the values and customs of other cultures. من به ارزشها و عنعنات فرهنگ های دیگر احترام کم دارم.					
--	---	--	--	--	--	--

Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory- II

Please read the items carefully. Please tell us how often the instances described below have happened to you and you have done them to others during the last 12 months. Tell us if and how often you have done this to others by marking the appropriate boxes in the “I did this” column. Tell us if and how often this has happened to you by marking the appropriate boxes in the “This happened to me” column. Please make sure that you marked your responses for all the items twice, one for “I did this” and one for “This happened to me” column.

سایبری خورونی تجدیدی پوښتلیک - ۲

مهرباني وکړئ لاندې جملې په دقت سره ولولئ او وواياست چې تاسو په تیرو 12 میاشتو کې لاندې څنګه ترسره کړي. همدارنګه، په یاد ولرئ چې دا ستاسو سره څو ځله پېښ شوي، لکه "ما دا وکړل" او "دا زما سره پېښ شوي". هغه ځوابونه چې تاسو یې غواړئ په دواړو کالمونو کې په نښه کړئ.

پرسشنامه تجدیدی قلدری سایبری - ۲

لطفا جملات ذیل را با دقت بخوانید و بگویید که شما در 12 ماه گذشته موارد ذیل را چگونه انجام داده اید. همچنان یاد آور شوید که این موارد چند بار برایتان تکرار شده است مثلاً "من این کار را انجام دادم" و موارد که برایتان "این برای من اتفاق افتاده" را هم نشانی کنید. جواب های مورد نظر تانرا در هر دو ستون نشانی کنید.

		I did this. من این کار را انجام دادم.				This happened to me. این برای من اتفاق افتاد.			
No.	د انټرنیټ له لارې Through the INTERNET; از طریق انټرنیټ	never (هیڅگاه)	once (یک ځل)	2-3 times (دو تا سه ځل)	More than 3 times (بیشتر از سه بار)	never (هیڅگاه)	once (یک ځل)	2-3 times (دو تا سه ځل)	More than 3 times (بیشتر از سه بار)

1	د یو شخص حساب پیتوم اخیستل. taking over the password of someone's account گرفتن رمز ورود از حساب های شخصی دیگر.	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
2	له اجازې پرته د چا اکاونټ کارول او سپک پوستونه خپرول. using someone's account without his/her permission and publishing humiliating posts استفاده از حساب شخصی بدون اجازه او و انتشار پست های تحقیرآمیز	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
3	یو څوک گواښل threatening someone کسی را تهدید کردن	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
4	د یو چا سپکاوی کول insulting someone کسی را توهین کردن	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
5	شرمونکي او ځورونکي پیغامونه لیرول sending embarrassing and hurtful messages ارسال پیام های شرم آور و ناراحت کننده.	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
6	له اجازې پرته د یو نامناسب عکس یا ویدیو شریکول sharing an inappropriate photo or a video of someone without his/her permission بدون اجازه شخص، عکس و یا ویدیوی نامناسب به اشتراک گذاشتن	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
7	د مالک له اجازې پرته نورو سره راز شریکول	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4

	sharing a secret with others without the permission of the owner بدون اجازه مالک ، رازش را با دیگران به اشتراک گذاشتن									
8	spreading rumors انتشار شایعات اوازي خپرول	1	2	3	4		1	2	3	4
9	creating an account on behalf of someone without letting him/her know and acting like the account's owner ایجاد حساب کاربری به نمایندگی شخصی دیگر بدون اطلاع به وی و مانند صاحب او استفاده کردن د یو چا په استازیتوب د حساب رامینځته کول، پرته لډې چې هغه خبر شي او د حساب مالک په څیر عمل کول	1	2	3	4		1	2	3	4
10	creating a humiliating website ایجاد یک وب سایت تحقیرآمیز سپکاوي ويب پاڼې جوړول	1	2	3	4		1	2	3	4

سایبری خورونی مجدد پوښتلیک

مهرباني وکړئ د لاندې چلندونو تکرار غوره کړی کوم چې تاسو په تیرو دولسو میاشتو کې د یو چا په وړاندې ترسره کړی وي.

Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory (RCBI)

Please select any of the below behavior, If you have performed against someone during the previous twelve months.

پرسشنامه تجدیدی قلدری سایبری

لطفاً هر یک از رفتارهای زیر را انتخاب کنید، اگر در طول دوازده ماه گذشته علیه شخصی انجام داده اید.

No.	سایبری خورونکی چلند Cyberbullying behavior آزار رفتار سایبری	هیڅگاه (Never)	یک بار (Once)	دو تا سه بار (Two to three times)	بیشتر از سه بار (More than three times)
1	له کمپیوټر څخه شخصي معلومات را پټول (د بیلګې په توګه: فایل، ایمیل، ادرس، انځور، آی ایم پیغامونه، یا د فیسبوک معلومات) stealing of personal information from computer (like files, email, addresses, pictures, IM messages, or Facebook info) دزدیدن معلومات شخصی از کامپیوتر (فایل ها، ایمیل، تصویر، ادرس، آی ایم پیام ها، و یا معلومات فیسبوک)	0	1	2-3	>3
2	د کمپیوټر تخلص یا صفحي نوم غلا کول. stealing of computer nicknames or screen names دزدی کردن تخلص یا نام صفحه کمپیوتر.	0	1	2-3	>3
3	په آنلاین توګه ګواښل (مثلاً چټ روم، فیسبوک یا ټویټر) threatening in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter) تهدید کردن به صورت آنلاین در فیسبوک، ټویټر ویا در چټ روم	0	1	2-3	>3
4	فیسبوک کې په آنلاین توګه سپکول (مثلاً چټ روم، فیسبوک یا ټویټر) Insulting in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter)	0	1	2-3	>3

	توهين به صورت آنلاین در فیسبوک، تویتز و یا در چت روم				
5	په آنلاین توگه د نورو محرومول یعنی د بل شخص بلاک کول یا تبصره یی حذفول. excluding in online forums by blocking others' comments or removing them محروم کردن دیگران از طریق آنلاین با بلاک کردن یا حذف کردن تبصره.	0	1	2-3	>3
6	د انترنیت له لاری د جعلی عکسونو په پوست کولو سره تهمت کول. slander by posting fake photos on the internet از طریق انترنیت، تهمت بستن توسط عکس های جعلی و آن را نشر کردن.	0	1	2-3	>3
7	د بل شخص له خبرولو څخه بغیر د هغه شخصی انترنیتی ارتباطاتو استعمالول مثلاً دوستانو سره د سکایپ له طریقه یا کوم بل ارتباطی روم له طریقه خبری اتری کول. sharing private internet conversations without the other's knowledge (such as chatting with a friend on Skype with other(s) in the room) شریک ساختن انترنیت شخصی، بدون در جریان گذاشتن دارنده آن مثلاً از طریق سکایپ مسنجر با دیگران ارتباط برقرار کردن.	0	1	2-3	>3
8	د آنلاین تبصرو له لاری د بل کس په کمنټو ریشخند و هل مثلاً فیسبوک Making fun of comments in online forums (such as Facebook) از طریق تبصره های آنلاین به دیگران تمسخر کردن مثلاً فیسبوک	0	1	2-3	>3
9	د ایمیل له لاری گواښونه یا مضره کمنټونه ورلیزل. Sending threatening or hurtful comments through email از طریق ایمیل اخطار و یا کمنټ های مضر روان کردن.	0	1	2-3	>3
10	ایمیلونه غلاکول (د یوزر نوم، پاسورډ) او اصلی مالک یی بلاکول. stealing email access (usernames and passwords) and blocking true owner's access دزدی کردن توسط ایمیل (نام یوزر، پاسورډ) و مالک اصلی آن را بلاک کردن.	0	1	2-3	>3
11	د ایمیل لاسرسی غلاکول او د هغوی شخصی پیغامونه لوستل. stealing email access and reading personal messages دسترسی به ایمیل ها، دزدی کردن معلومات شخصی و خواندن آنها.	0	1	2-3	>3

12	<p>خطراته ورکول او یا مضره پیغام لیرل. sending threatening and or hurtful text messages</p> <p>اخطار دادن و یا پیام های مضر فرستادن.</p>	0	1	2-3	>3
13	<p>د بل جنسیت (تارینه / بنخینه) په صفت خان بنودل. misleading by pretending to be other gender (male/female)</p> <p>خود را به صفت جنسیت (مرد/زن) متفاوت نشان دادن.</p>	0	1	2-3	>3
14	<p>په آنلاین طریقہ پرتہ له اجازي، شرمونکي عکسونه خپرول. publishing online an embarrassing photo without permission</p> <p>از طریق آنلاین بدون اجازه، عکس های مبتذل و ناراحت کننده را پخش و نشر کردن.</p>	0	1	2-3	>3

مهرباني وکړئ د لاندې چلندونو تکرار غوره کړی کوم چې ستاسو په وړاندې په تیرو دولسو میاشتو کې ترسره کړي وی.

Please select any of the below behavior, If someone have performed against you during the previous twelve months.

لطفاً هر یک از رفتارهای زیر را انتخاب کنید، اگر شخصی در طول دوازده ماه گذشته علیه شما عمل کرده است.

No.	<p>سایبری زیانمنکیدو چلند Cyber victim behavior قربانی رفتار سایبری</p>	Never (هیچگاه)	Once (یک بار)	Two to three times (دو تا سه بار)	More than three times (بیشتر از سه بار)
1	<p>له کمپیوټر څخه شخصي معلومات را پټول (د بیلگي په توگه: فایل، ایمیل، ادرس، انځور، آی ایم پیغامونه، یا د فیسبوک معلومات)</p> <p>stealing of personal information from computer (like files, email, addresses, pictures, IM messages, or Facebook info)</p> <p>دزدیدن معلومات شخصی از کامپیوتر (فایل ها، ایمیل، ادرس، تصویر، ای ایم مسجونه، فیسبوک)</p>	0	1	2-3	>3
2	<p>د کمپیوټر تخلص یا صفحي نوم غلا کیدل. stealing of computer nicknames or screen names</p> <p>دزدی کردن تخلص یا نام صفحه کامپیوتر.</p>	0	1	2-3	>3
3	<p>په آنلاین توگه گوانبل (مثلاً چټ روم، فیسبوک یا تویتر)</p>	0	1	2-3	>3

	threatening in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter) تهدید شدن به صورت آنلاین در فیسبوک، توئیتر و یا چت روم				
4	Insulting in online forums (like chat rooms, Facebook or twitter) توهین به صورت آنلاین در فیسبوک، توئیتر و یا در چت روم.	0	1	2-3	>3
5	excluding in online forums by blocking others' comments or removing them محروم شدن از طریق آنلاین با بلاک کردن یا حذف کردن تبصره.	0	1	2-3	>3
6	slander by posting fake photos on the internet د انترنیت له لاری د جعلی عکسونو په نشرولو سره تهمتول. از طریق انترنیت، تهمت بستن توسط عکس های جعلی و آن را نشرکردن.	0	1	2-3	>3
7	sharing private internet conversations without the other's knowledge (such as chatting with a friend on Skype with other(s) in the room) د بل شخص له خبرولو څخه بغير د هغه شخصی انترنیتی ارتباطاتو استعمالول مثلاً هغه دوستانو سره د سکایپ له طریقو یا کوم بل ارتباطی روم له طریقو خبری اتری کول. شریک ساختن انترنیت شخصی، بدون در جریان گذاشتن دارنده آن مثلاً از طریق فیسبوک مسنجر با دیگران ارتباط برقرار کردن.	0	1	2-3	>3
8	Making fun of comments in online forums (such as Facebook) از طریق تبصره های آنلاین تمسخر کردن مثلاً در فیسبوک	0	1	2-3	>3
9	receiving threatening or hurtful comments through email د ایمیل له لاری گواښونه یا مضره کمنټونه ترلاسه کول. از طریق ایمیل اخطار و یا کمنټ های مضر دریافت کردن.	0	1	2-3	>3
10	stealing email access (usernames and passwords) and blocking true owner's access ایمیلونه غلاکول (د یوزر نوم، پاسورد) او اصلی مالک یی بلاکول. دزدی کردن توسط ایمیل (نام یوزر، پاسورد) و مالک اصلی آن را بلاک کردن.	0	1	2-3	>3

11	<p>د ایمیل لاسرسی غلاکول او د هغوی شخصی پیغامونه لوستل.</p> <p>stealing email access and reading personal messages</p> <p>دسترسی به ایمیل ها، دزدی کردن معلومات شخصی و خواندن آنها.</p>	0	1	2-3	>3
12	<p>اخطار په او یا مضره پیغام تر لاسه کول.</p> <p>receiving threatening and or hurtful text messages</p> <p>اخطار په و یا پیام های مضر دریافت کردن.</p>	0	1	2-3	>3
13	<p>د بل جنسیت (نارینه / بنځینه) په صفت ځان بنودل.</p> <p>misleading by pretending to be other gender (male/female)</p> <p>خود را به صفت جنسیت (مرد/زن) متفاوت نشان دادن.</p>	0	1	2-3	>3
14	<p>په آنلاین طریقې پرته له اجازې، شرمونکي عکسونه خپرول.</p> <p>publishing online an embarrassing photo without permission</p> <p>از طریق آنلاین بدون اجازه، عکس های مبتذل و ناراحت کننده را پخش و نشر کردن.</p>	0	1	2-3	>3

10/30/2019

Gmail - Permission Letter: Ethnocentrism Scale

mohammad khalid <mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com>

Permission Letter: Ethnocentrism Scale

2 messages

mohammad khalid <mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com>
To: jim.neuliep@snc.edu

Sat, Oct 26, 2019 at 11:18 AM

Permission Letter

I am a doctoral student at the Gujarat University completing a thesis and some articles in Criminal and Forensic psychology. I am writing to ask written permission to use the Ethnocentrism Scale in my research study. This study will take place in Afghanistan (Kabul province) and India (Gujarat state). My research is being supervised by Professor Dr. Kamayani Mathur and Co-guidance of Dr. Kapil Kumar under the title of "Ethnocentrism as a predictor of cyber bullying & cyber victimization among adults; A Cross Cultural Study".

It has been planned to use the entire instrument and may bring some changes in the instrument because of two cultures. I would also appreciate receiving copies of supplemental material that will help me administer the test and analyze the results and scoring procedure with standard instruction.

In addition to using the instrument, I also ask your permission to reproduce it in my thesis appendix. The thesis and related articles will be published.

I would like to use and reproduce your Ethnocentrism Scale under the following conditions:

- I will use the instrument only for my research study and will not sell or use it for any other purposes
- I will include a statement of attribution and copyright on all copies of the instrument. If you have a specific statement of attribution that you would like for me to include, please provide it in your response.
- At your request, I will send a copy of my completed research study to you upon completion of the final manuscript.

If you do not control the copyright for these materials, I would appreciate any information you can provide concerning the proper person or organization I should contact.

If these are acceptable terms and conditions, please indicate so by replying to me through e-mail at mk.ahmadzai@yahoo.com or mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com.

According to the Gujarat University rules and regulation, it is mandatory for seeking the permission. So once again, I kindly request you for permission and publication of the instruments.

Sincerely,

Mohammad Khalid

Jim Neuliep <jim.neuliep@snc.edu>
To: mohammad khalid <mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com>

Tue, Oct 29, 2019 at 5:17 PM

Hello Mohammad,

Thank you for your email. You have my permission to use the Generalized Ethnocentrism Scale (GENE) in your research.

Please cite the following source in your references:

Neuliep, J.W., (2002). Assessing the reliability and validity of the generalized ethnocentrism scale. *Journal of Intercultural Communication Research*, 31, (4), 201-216.

Best wishes for a successful thesis.

<https://mail.google.com/mail/u/0/?ik=e19db76785&view=pt&search=all&permthid=thread-a%3Ar3378842598839935546&siml-msg-a%3Ar-2677...> 1/2

10/30/2019

Gmail - Permission Letter: Ethnocentrism Scale

Dr. Neuliep
[Quoted text hidden]

<https://mail.google.com/mail/u/0?ik=e19db76785&view-pt&search=all&permthid=thread-a%3Ar3378842598839935546&siml=msg-a%3Ar-2677...> 2/2

1/5/2020

Gmail - permission for scale

mohammad khalid <mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com>

permission for scale

2 messages

mohammad khalid <mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com>
To: erdur@metu.edu.tr

Sat, Sep 28, 2019 at 9:53 AM

Permission Letter

I am a doctoral student at the Gujarat University completing a thesis and some articles in Criminal and Forensic psychology. I am writing to ask written permission to use the "RCBI: Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory" in my research study. This study will take place in Afghanistan (Kabul province) and India (Gujarat state). My research is being supervised by Professor Dr. Kamayani Mathur and Co-guidance of Dr. Kapil Kumar under the title of "Ethnocentrism as a predictor of cyber bullying & cyber victimization among adults; A Cross Cultural Study".

It has been planned to use the entire instrument and may bring some changes in the instrument because of two cultures. I would also appreciate receiving copies of supplemental material that will help me administer the test and analyze the results and scoring procedure with standard instruction. In addition to using the instrument, I also ask your permission to reproduce it in my thesis appendix. The thesis and related articles will be published. I would like to use and reproduce your "RCBI" instrument under the following conditions:

- I will use the instrument only for my research study and will not sell or use it for any other purposes
- I will include a statement of attribution and copyright on all copies of the instrument. If you have a specific statement of attribution that you would like for me to include, please provide it in your response.
- At your request, I will send a copy of my completed research study to you upon completion of the final manuscript.

If you do not control the copyright for these materials, I would appreciate any information you can provide concerning the proper person or organization I should contact.

If these are acceptable terms and conditions, please indicate so by replying to me through e-mail at mk.ahmadzai@yahoo.com or mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com.

According to the Gujarat University rules and regulation, it is mandatory for seeking the permission. So once again, I kindly request you for giving me permission and its publication of the instruments.

Sincerely,

Mohammad Khalid

Ozgur Erdur Baker <ozgurerdur@gmail.com>

Sat, Sep 28, 2019 at 4:38 PM

To: mohammad khalid <mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com>, Cigdem Topcu <cigdemtopcu@gmail.com>

Dear Mohammad Khalid,

I have already sent you the scale on September 9th. Would you please check your emails?

Ozgur.

[Quoted text hidden]

—

Ozgur Erdur-Baker, Ph.D.
Fulbright Fellow at Boston College
Center of Human Rights and International Justice
Lynch School of Education and Human Development

Prof. of Psy. Counseling and Guidance

1/5/2020

Gmail - permission for scale

Middle East Technical University
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request for permission for publication

4 messages

mohammad khalid <mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com>
To: Ozgur Erdur Baker <ozgurerdur@gmail.com>

Sat, 7 Sep 2019 at 4:28 pm

Permission Letter

I am a doctoral student at the Gujarat University completing a thesis and some articles in Criminal and Forensic psychology. I am writing to ask written permission to use the RCBI-II: The Second Revision of the Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory in my research study. This study will take place in Afghanistan (Kabul province) and India (Gujarat state). My research is being supervised by Professor Dr. Kamayani Mathurand and Co-guidance of Dr. Kapil Kumar under the title of "Ethnocentrism as a predictor of cyber bullying & cyber victimization among adults; A Cross Cultural Study".

It has been planned to use the entire instrument and may bring some changes in the instrument because of two cultures. I would also appreciate receiving copies of supplemental material that will help me administer the test and analyze the results and scoring procedure with standard instruction.

In addition to using the instrument, I also ask your permission to reproduce it in my thesis appendix. The thesis and related articles will be published.

I would like to use and reproduce your RCBI-II instrument under the following conditions:

- I will use the instrument only for my research study and will not sell or use it for any other purposes
- I will include a statement of attribution and copyright on all copies of the instrument. If you have a specific statement of attribution that you would like for me to include, please provide it in your response.
- At your request, I will send a copy of my completed research study to you upon completion of the final manuscript.

If you do not control the copyright for these materials, I would appreciate any information you can provide concerning the proper person or organization I should contact.

If these are acceptable terms and conditions, please indicate so by replying to me through e-mail at mk.ahmadzai@yahoo.com or mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com.

According to the Gujarat University rules and regulation, it is mandatory for seeking the permission. So once again, I kindly request you for giving me permission and its publication of the instruments.

Sincerely,

Mohammad Khalid

mohammad khalid <mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com>
To: cigdemtopcu@gmail.com

Sat, 7 Sep 2019 at 4:42 pm

[Quoted text hidden]

Cigdem Topcu Uzer <cigdemtopcu@gmail.com>
To: mohammad khalid <mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com>

Sun, 8 Sep 2019 at 12:27 pm

Dear Mohammad Khalid,

I am attaching the latest version of the scale (RCBI-II) and the related article that you can read scoring, validity, and reliability information. Feel free to use the RCBI-II for your research.

Good luck!
Cigdem

[Quoted text hidden]

2 attachments

 RCBI-II_Eng.pdf
84 KB

 RCBI II The Second Revision of the Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory.pdf
603 KB

Ozgur Erdur Baker <ozgurerdur@gmail.com>
To: mohammad khalid <mk.ahmadzai786@gmail.com>
Cc: Cigdem Topcu <cigdemtopcu@gmail.com>

Mon, 9 Sep 2019 at 8:10 pm

Dear Mohammad Khalid,

You are welcome to use the scale for your research. As long as it is used for the research purposes, you may reproduce it. Please do let us know the results of the research, especially, the language adaptations.

Good luck with your research.

Ozgur Erdur-Baker
[Quoted text hidden]

—
Ozgur Erdur-Baker, Ph.D.
Fulbright Fellow at Boston College

Prof. of Psy. Counseling and Guidance
Middle East Technical University
Faculty of Education
Dumlupinar Bulvari, No: 1
Ankara 06800
TURKEY
erdur@metu.edu.tr
Ph: +90-312-2104036
Fax: +90-312-2107967

2 attachments

 scaleRCBI-II_Eng.pdf
84 KB

 makaleRCBI II The Second Revision of the Revised Cyber Bullying Inventory.pdf
561 KB

TELEGRAM: UNIGUJARAT

TELEPHONE: 26303562

UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF
PSYCHOLOGY, EDUCATION AND PHILOSOPHY
GUJARAT UNIVERSITY

AHMEDABAD-380009

GUJARAT INDIA

Date: _____

To,

Subject: Permission for data collection for dissertation/Project work of the students of Psychology Department, Gujarat University.

Dear Sir/Madam,

My student _____, is studying in the Department of Psychology Gujarat University, (M.A., M.PHIL., P.G.D.C.P., PH.D). I am writing this letter to request you to kindly grant her / him permission for data collection which is a part of their syllabus. The data collection will be taken as per the subjects' convenience. Thank you for your cooperation and support. The data taken from the subjects will be strictly confidential.

Regards,

Yours Faithfully,

Kamayani Mathur

भारतीय | Indian
सांस्कृतिक | Council for
सम्बन्ध | Cultural
परिषद् | Relations

(Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India)

F. No. ICCR/AHM/2019-20/ 547

26th May 2020

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Mohammad Khalid Khawrin** from Afghanistan has been awarded ICCR Scholarship administered by Ministry of External Affairs (MEA) Government of India, under Special Scholarship Scheme for Afghan Nationals (SSSAN) for pursuing Ph.d (Applied Psychology) at Gujarat University.

Duration of course is three years i.e. from July 2019, to June 2022. The above student's data collection request may be granted as a part of research under Ph.d Programme.

Details of passport are as under:

1. Passport No. P02189456
2. Date of issue 29.05.2019
3. Date of expiry 29.05.2024

Any assistance extended to the above student will be highly appreciated.

Ministry of Higher Education
Department of Students affairs

وزارت تحصیلات عالی
ریاست امور محصلان دولتی
مدیریت عمومی امور متفرقه محصلان

No

نمبر ع ۳۳۲

۹۹/۵/۱۶

بر ریاست محترم پوهنتونها!

نامه شماره 1495 مورخ 1399/6/10 ریاست دفتر مقام وزارت
واصل و چنین مینگار د:-

طی درخواست محترم محمد خالد (خاورین) محصل دوره دوکتورا
پوهنتون کجرات هند خواهش همکاری در زمینه پرمش نامه تیزس
خویش را نموده موضوع به کمیته اختصاصی محول گردید:-

کمیته محترم اختصاصی در مورد چنین ابراز نظر نموده اند!

فیصله کمیته اختصاصی محصلان مورخ 1399/6/11!

(از اتیکه موضوع اکادمیک است، به پوهنتوهای دولتی و خصوصی
غرض همکاری معلومات مورد نیاز تحقیق مورد نیاز معرفی گردد)

بناء موضوع بشما نگاشته شد در مورد طبق فیصله کمیته اختصاصی
امور محصلان اجراء اصولی نمایند.

پوهنوال دپلوم انجنیر محمد شریف امین
رئیس امور محصلان دولتی

جمهوری اسلامی افغانستان
وزارت تحصیلات عالی
Islamic Republic of Afghanistan
Ministry of Higher Education
ریاست امور محصلان خصوصی
امریت محصلان

تاریخ: 1399/ 6 / 15

شماره مکتوب: ۵۷۸
۵۸۴

به ریاست محترم پوهنتون / موسسه تحصیلات عالی (پ. ن. د. عمومی مکتب پابل)

نامه نمبر (1610) مورخ 1399/6/10 ریاست دفتر مقام وزارت واصل وچنین مینگارډ:

((توام این نامه، درخواست محترم محمدخالد (خاورین) محصل دیره دوکتورا پوهنتون کجرات هند به

ملاحظه محترم معین صاحب امور محصلان رسانیده در مورد چنین هدایت فرموده اند:

ریاست های محترم امور محصلان دولتی وخصوصی!

بملاحظه سوابق و اسناد اجراءات قانونی نمایید)

موضوع جهت اجراءات قانونی به شما گسیل است.))

مراتب فوق حسب هدایت مقام محترم وزارت نگاشته شد در زمینه پرسش

نامه تیزس دوکتورا با ایشان همکاری نموده از اجراءات خویش این اداره را

اطمینان دهید.

با احترام

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AFGHAN ETHNICITIES AND INTERNET SURFING CORRELATE WITH DIGITAL BULLYING AND VICTIMIZATION

Mohammad Khalid Khawrin

Dr. Kamayani Mathur

Dr. Kapil Kumar

Abstract

Ethnicity is the first identification topic in Afghanistan. However, the last five decades brought changes in the social and political scenario of Afghanistan. Due to these reasons diagnosing the demerits of ethnicity is the first step for a solution. On the other hand, this study showed that the Afghan ethnicities such as Pashtun, Tajik, Hazara, and other minorities do not have significant differences among one another based on Digital Bullying and Digital Victimization of the sample. This research data took from public and private universities of Kabul province through the standardized Revised Cyberbullying inventory II (RCBI-II) which was developed by Topcu & Erdur-Bakerb (Topcu and Erdur-Bakerb). There was 750 sample size who participated voluntarily through random sampling technique. Moreover, the sample consists of four groups of Ethnicities such as Pashtun, Tajik, Hazara, and other minorities (224, 267, 221, 38) respectively. A relationship was tested through Spearman's rho because data were not normally distributed. Besides that for finding differences among Afghan Ethnicities based on Digital Bullying and Digital Victimization one way ANOVA has been applied. All data were analyzed with the SPSS version 24. Furthermore, the result showed the relationship of internet surfing with digital bullying and digital victimization was positively significant with one another. On the other hand, the differences among Afghan Ethnicities were not significantly different from one another.

Key Words: Internet surfing, Afghan ethnicities, Cyberbullying, Cyber victimization, Ethnicity

Introduction

The annoyance of one another based on ethnicity is one of the new kinds of bias in Afghan society. Which has started practically by warlords in the 1990s civil war. Since 2001 ethnicity got an important role in the construction of social and political dimensions of Afghan society. Such as commonly recognizing two vice presidents and distribution of power based on ethnicity was practically seen in since 2001 up to 2021 of Afghan politics.

**A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INDIAN CASTES AND GENDER
WITH ETHNOCENTRISM AMONG ADULT STUDENTS IN
AHMEDABAD CITY**

**Mohammad Khalid Khawrin
Dr. Kamayani Mathur
Dr. Kapil Kumar**

Abstract

The lens of cultural conflict has many dimensions to examine diversity based on gender, caste, occupation, etc. It is highly needed to determine the appropriate system, which leads humans to further development and prosperity. There were both genders of male and female (42.8%, 57.2%) respectively. Furthermore, data was gathered with a sample using random sampling method from 2019-to 2021. There were 750 students with different castes such as Open/General category of caste (53.9%), Scheduled Tribe (9.5%), Scheduled Extremely Backward Caste (20.7%), Scheduled Caste (8.5%), Other Backward Caste (5.6%), and economically weaker section (1.9%) participants. This study evaluated the difference of variance of castes among one another and the mean score difference of gender was also evaluated. This study proved that there was not a significant difference among castes groups similarly the gender of the Ahmedabad city students' also was not significantly different.

Key words: Castes, Ethnocentrism, Gender, Students, Ahmedabad

Introduction

Methodological problems have hampered a thorough investigation of the relationship between caste and gender. The first is the difficulty of defining caste. The phrase has no commonly acknowledged definition. In Hindu literature, caste is associated with Varna, the ancient division of society for instance Brahmins are the priests, Kshatriyas are the kings and warriors, Vaishyas are the farmers and merchants, Shudras are the workers, and a fifth category of "untouchables" (Anderson et al. 358). However, the current Indian government has officially recognized different stratification such as Scheduled Caste (SC), Scheduled Tribe (ST), Backward Caste (BC), Extremely Backward Caste (EBC), and Other Backward Caste (OBC). These castes were formed for assuring privileges and reducing the essential deprivation furthermore, the caste is known as

RELATIONSHIP OF SELECTED CYBERBULLYING BEHAVIORS AMONG GUJARAT UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract

It is most important to indicate the cyber harmful behavior which can lead to poor academic achievement. Furthermore, it is significantly important to diagnose these problems and this would pave the way for effective and efficient prevention. Therefore, the selected items of cyberbullying behavior had massive importance for the University stakeholders and better achievement of academic performance and harmony. Gujarat University students voluntary (N=292) participated in the study which consisted of both gender males and females (139,153) respectively. A random sampling design was used for collecting data and its reliability was checked for cyberbullying and cyber victim items were (.794 and .834) respectively.

The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation and paired Samples t-test methods were used for analyzing the data through SPSS version 24. The results showed that all items with their reaction have significantly correlated with one another on .001 level. Moreover, overall cyberbullying and victim items had a significant relationship with one another ($p < .01$, $p < .01$) respectively. Similarly, cyberbullying items were significantly different from cyber victim behavior ($p < .000$) and cyberbullying items were less taken place compare to cyber victim behavior.

Keywords: Cyberbully, cyber victim, bystander, internet surfing

INTRODUCTION

Cyberbullying behavior is the digital behavior that could psychologically harm his peer (Khawrin, 2021). Moreover, taking advantage and hurting the cyber-prey person is called a cyber-victim. It is very important to study cyber activities at Gujarat University because there is very little research for showing the relationship between cyber activities. Furthermore, these activities have many psychological side effects. For example, Cyber Bullying behavior has many effects on victims' emotions and mental health. Some of these side effects are digital threatened, low self-esteem, migraine attacks, anxiety, loneliness, depression, suicidal thought, humiliation, unsecured, sad, rejection, insulted, hurt, helplessness, procrastination, friendship difficulties, hostile behavior, schizophrenia, academic self-concepts, low levels of academic achievement, and online harassment (Cuffy, 2015). Furthermore, it is proven that cyberbullying behavior has a side effect on cyberbully and bystanders such as anxiety, guilt, fear of safety, lack of support, uncontrolled situation (Cuffy, 2015). Coloroso (as cited in Duman & Bridge, 2020) said that cyberbullying has four elements. Such as, "power inequality, desire to hurt, a threat for further aggression, and bullying in a systematic violence with dominance". Furthermore, types of cyberbullying were mentioned as "flaming, harassment, cyber-stalking, denigration, impersonation, outing, and exclusion" (Duman & Bridge, 2020). Erdur-Baker and Kavrut (as cited in Duman & Bridge, 2020) the study proved that some students of 14 to 19 years of age were kicked out from common groups because they misused the password, read other messages, and revealed that male students became more victims of these actions. İçellioglu & Özden (2014) argued the cyberbullying types which are declared as follows. Sharing photos or video, sex messages, hacking profiles, threatening messages, and sending spam messages. However, some of the prominent cyber activities which happen daily are discussed here.

PASSWORDS MISUSING

Password is the unique identity through which a digital technology recognizes the owner. Kassabri, Gadalla, and Daciuk (as cited in Black, 2014) in the study some students told that they have given a password to peer and friends, and almost 24% of them became cyber victimized, 8% reported cyberbullied, and 25.7% reported both cyberbullied and cyber victimized. Digital space has many flows such as misusing password, sharing personal

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Appendix U: Second Conference certificate

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CERTIFICATE OF PRESENTATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Mr. Mohammad Khalid Khawari

(PhD Research scholar, Gujarat University)

for presenting the paper entitled
"Age and Internet surfing of the participants as predictors of
cyber bullying among the students in Ahmedabad city"
in the

"International Virtual Conference on Healthy Ageing"
on

10th to 12th MARCH 2022

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